

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

D3.1 Knowledge Exchange material

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Executive Summary

The BioRural project aims to empower rural areas across Europe by facilitating the transition to a circular bioeconomy. This transformation presents substantial economic, ecological, and social opportunities, but it also poses significant challenges, particularly for rural communities that often lack the necessary infrastructure, technological advancements, and knowledge to fully engage with and benefit from these opportunities. Recognizing these challenges, the BioRural project has implemented a dedicated work package (WP3) focused on knowledge exchange and capacity building, with a particular emphasis on bridging the knowledge and skills gap in rural areas. A key component of this work package is the organization of Knowledge Exchange Workshops (KEWs), which are the subject of this report.

Knowledge Exchange Workshops: Purpose and Structure

The BioRural Knowledge Exchange Workshops (KEWs) are designed as a critical tool to address the knowledge and skills gaps in rural areas, facilitating the successful deployment of bio-based solutions. These workshops are embedded in the overall concept of the BioRural project, which seeks to promote effective knowledge exchange and explore opportunities for integrating bio-based solutions in rural Europe. The KEWs specifically focus on the valorization of currently underutilized biomass residues from agriculture, forestry, and aquatic sources, aiming to unlock their potential in the circular bioeconomy.

The workshops are organized around five bioeconomy themes—food and agriculture, forestry and natural habitats, aquatic systems, bioenergy, and biomaterials—each addressing various technical, managerial, regulatory, and policy aspects critical to strengthening the circular bioeconomy in rural areas. The content of the workshops is structured into three dimensions: generic principles (e.g., circular bioeconomy, biorefining), theme-specific aspects (e.g., nutrient recycling, market trends), and cross-cutting issues (e.g., innovation management, regulation and certification).

Implementation and Outreach

The KEWs were conducted as online webinars, allowing for broad participation and interaction between participants and experts. The workshops were organized over three consecutive days, with each day dedicated to a specific aspect of the bioeconomy: foundational knowledge on day one, practical examples and success stories on day two, and cross-cutting themes on day three. This structure ensured a comprehensive and engaging learning experience, with materials presented in a digestible manner for all stakeholder types.

To maximize the outreach and impact of these workshops, the learning materials, including video lectures and presentations, are made publicly available through the [BioRural Toolkit](#), an online portal dedicated to supporting the rural bioeconomy. This open-access approach ensures that the knowledge shared during the workshops is accessible to a wide audience, fostering continuous learning and capacity building in rural areas.

Theme 1: Biochemicals and Biomaterials

The first workshop focused on biochemicals and biomaterials derived from various biomass streams, including forestry, agri-food, and aquatic systems. It provided participants with a comprehensive understanding of the structure and technological properties of these biomass side-streams, paving the way for innovative applications. Key technological pathways explored included the conversion of biomass into valuable biomaterials and small-scale biorefining solutions, which are pivotal for rural businesses aiming to enhance the sustainability of their operations.

The workshop highlighted successful innovations such as the production of food supplements from plant extractives by and the valorization side-streams in horticulture. Other notable examples included the development of soluble green packaging solutions and the creation of high-end solutions in fungi cultivation, demonstrating the commercial potential of diverse biomass streams.

With respect to the Cross-Cutting Topics, discussions on intellectual property management and the commercialization of biobased products were crucial in this workshop. Additionally, the role of bio-based content certification was emphasized as a means to enhance market credibility and consumer trust in biobased products.

Theme 2: Aquatic Systems

The second workshop delved into the bioeconomy potential within aquatic systems, with a particular focus on aquaculture and algal technologies. Participants were introduced to sustainable practices in aquaculture, such as Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture and the use of microalgae for nutrient recovery and biogas upgrading, both of which offer sustainable solutions for waste management in aquatic environments.

The workshop showcased several pioneering efforts, including the pilot plant specialized for biorefining of aquatic biomass and the development of sustainable local aquaculture practices. The role of microalgae in the circular economy was also underscored, highlighting its potential to create high-value products while addressing environmental challenges.

Among the cross-cutting topics, key discussions centered on the regulatory landscape and standardization for the algal sector, which are critical for scaling up innovative practices. The importance of regional material use of biogenic by-products and waste streams was also highlighted.

Theme 3: Agriculture and Food

The third workshop targeted the agricultural and food sectors, addressing the synergy between soil management and bioeconomy. Participants learned about innovative practices in organic farming, carbon farming, and agroforestry, which collectively contribute to ecological restoration and climate change mitigation. The workshop also explored the opportunities presented by green biorefinery technologies and nutrient recycling practices, which are essential for the sustainable transformation of agricultural systems.

Case studies presented during the workshop included the application of artificial intelligence in reducing plant protection chemicals and the use of mobile applications for rational fertilizer use by agricultural producers. These innovations demonstrate the potential for technology to enhance productivity while minimizing environmental impact.

As regards the cross-cutting topics, the workshop concluded with discussions on the valorization of waste streams in the food processing industry and the role of geographical information systems in assessing food biomass. These topics are critical for enabling institutions, such as policymakers and investors, to support the transition to a circular bioeconomy in the agricultural sector.

Theme 4: Forestry and Habitats

Focusing on forestry and habitats, the fourth workshop examined the opportunities for biomass valorization in forest ecosystems. Participants were introduced to the characterization and management of forest resources, including forest fire protection and automation in forest operations. The workshop also covered the potential of wood utilization in construction, highlighting both the advantages and challenges of using structural wood.

The workshop featured innovative approaches to biomass valorization, such as the collection of residual biomass at biomass collection centres and the production of birch bark extractives. These initiatives showcase the potential for creating high-value products from forest biomass, contributing to rural economic development.

Among the cross-cutting topics, sustainable forest management practices, including biodiversity conservation in private forests and certification schemes like PEFC, were emphasized as critical components of the circular bioeconomy in forestry. These practices not only ensure the long-term viability of forest resources but also enhance market access for sustainably produced forest products.

Theme 5: Bioenergy

The final workshop addressed the bioenergy sector, with a focus on sustainable energy production from biomass. Participants were exposed to various bioenergy technologies, including gasification, biogas and biomethane production, and biomass-based combined heat and power systems. These technologies are particularly relevant for rural areas seeking to reduce their carbon footprint and enhance energy self-sufficiency.

Notable innovations presented in this workshop included the technology for integrated solutions to decarbonize energy production and the development of advanced biofuels for transportation. The case studies illustrated the potential for bioenergy to contribute to the circular economy by providing sustainable energy alternatives.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and associated methods for sustainability evaluation were key cross-cutting topics of discussion. These tools are essential for assessing the environmental impact of bioenergy projects and guiding the development of sustainable bioenergy policies and practices.

Concluding remarks

The BioRural Knowledge Exchange Workshops play a crucial role in bridging the knowledge and skills gap that rural communities face in transitioning to a circular bioeconomy. By providing targeted, accessible, and practical knowledge, these workshops empower rural stakeholders—ranging from primary producers and businesses to policymakers and investors—to engage more effectively with bio-based solutions. The workshops not only support the immediate needs of rural communities but also contribute to the broader goals of the BioRural project: promoting sustainable rural development, fostering innovation, and building resilient, circular bioeconomy systems across Europe.

The continued dissemination and utilization of the knowledge and tools provided through the Knowledge Exchange Workshops and corresponding Training materials, accessible on the BioRural Toolkit, and active participation of rural bioeconomy stakeholders in the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) importantly contribute towards the successful and inclusive transition to a circular bioeconomy in rural Europe.

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
ERBN	European Rural Bioeconomy Network
KEW	Knowledge Exchange Workshop
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis

1 Introduction

1.1 Overcoming knowledge and skill gaps in rural areas to seize the opportunities of circular bioeconomy

The transition to a circular bioeconomy offers numerous opportunities for rural areas across economic, ecological, and social dimensions (Kardung et al., 2021). However, it also presents unique challenges.

From the economic perspective, the circular bioeconomy promotes the efficient use of biological resources, leading to significant economic advantages. By recycling and reusing materials, industries can reduce costs associated with raw material procurement and waste management. This model fosters innovation and the development of new bio-based products, creating new markets and job opportunities. For instance, the shift to bio-based materials can stimulate rural economies by increasing demand for agricultural and forestry products (Venkatesh, 2022). Additionally, the circular bioeconomy can attract investments in green technologies and infrastructure, further boosting economic growth (Holden et al., 2023).

Ecologically, the circular bioeconomy aims to minimize waste and reduce environmental impact. By utilizing renewable biological resources and promoting sustainable practices, it helps in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and conserving biodiversity. The focus on recycling and reusing materials ensures that fewer resources are extracted from nature, leading to less environmental degradation. Moreover, the circular bioeconomy supports the restoration of ecosystems and the sustainable management of natural resources, contributing to overall environmental health (Muscat et al., 2021).

Socially, the circular bioeconomy can enhance community resilience and well-being. It creates job opportunities in rural areas, reducing urban migration and supporting local economies (Refsgaard et al., 2021). The emphasis on sustainable practices can reduce pollution and promote cleaner environments. Furthermore, the circular bioeconomy encourages community engagement and education (Grande, 2022), fostering a culture of sustainability and environmental stewardship.

While the transition to a circular bioeconomy offers substantial economic, ecological, and social benefits, in particular rural areas are faced with a number of challenges that need to be successfully overcome for a successful and inclusive transition. Despite these benefits, rural areas face several challenges in transitioning to a circular bioeconomy. The obvious challenge is the lack of infrastructure and technological advancements needed to support bio-based industries. Rural regions often have limited access to funding and investment, making it difficult to implement new technologies and practices. Another challenge is the potential disruption to traditional agricultural practices (Muizniece et al., 2019). Farmers may need to adopt new methods and crops, which can be risky and require significant investment. There is also the issue of market access; rural producers may struggle to reach larger markets and compete with established industries. Lastly, policy and regulatory frameworks need to be supportive and adaptive to the unique needs of rural areas. Without appropriate policies, rural communities may find it challenging to transition smoothly to a circular bioeconomy (Brandao and Santos, 2022). Moreover, the transition to a circular bioeconomy must ensure that all members of rural communities benefit, addressing issues of social inequality and ensuring inclusive participation (Sanz-Hernández et al., 2019).

One of the most significant challenges in rural areas is the gap in knowledge and skills required for the circular bioeconomy (Skondras et al., 2024). Many rural communities and rural stakeholders lack access to education and training programs that provide the necessary skills for their successful integration into extended bioeconomy value chains. Addressing the knowledge and skills gaps is essential for ensuring that rural communities can fully participate in and benefit from this transition.

Recognising the need to empower rural stakeholders with specific knowledge and skills on specific technologies, modalities of business organization, policies and enabling institutions, the BioRural project set up a dedicated workpackage (WP3 - Knowledge exchange & capacity building on rural Bioeconomy). Its first Task, which is also a subject of this report, deals with the organization and implementation of a series of online courses on various

bioeconomy-related advancements applicable in rural areas, named in project jargon as Knowledge Exchange Workshops (KEWs).

1.2 Embedding Knowledge Exchange Workshops to the overall concept of BioRural project

BioRural KEWs can be seen as an essential tool in fulfilling the work program “...successful deployment of existing scientific and practical knowledge and more bio-based solutions introduced in rural areas” and achieving the project objective of “...promoting effective exchange of knowledge and investigating the possible opportunities ... of bio-based solutions integration in rural Europe¹”. Emphasis is given on addressing untapped opportunities of the valorisation of currently under-utilised locally sourced (agri-, forest-based, or aquatic) biomass residues. This can be seen from the specific objective SO4 of BioRural project, which explicitly mentions “knowledge exchange and capacity building workshops to train and connect rural stakeholders”, and to “...share relevant and impactful rural Bioeconomy science with specific interest on regional biomass streams”. As the project aims to expand knowledge on bio-based solutions for rural areas at a Europe-wide level, the KEWs were organized in online format, allowing for a direct interaction between workshop participants and lecturers. The outreach was extended by making the learning materials widely and publicly available after the workshops themselves.

Ebededness of the KEWs to the BioRural conceptual approach is presented in Figure 1. As presented in the lower part of the chart, BioRural conceptual approach is based on a three-pillar intervention scheme that (i) provides a framework to increase knowledge for the related stakeholders of rural areas (Pillar1 - Knowledge), (ii) creates a network of stakeholders to interconnect actors that can boost circular Bioeconomy growth in rural areas (Pillar 2 – Network) and (iii) assists rural development by blueprinting sustainable business models (Pillar 3 – Business models). KEWs relate primarily with Pillar 1 of the conceptual design by primarily addressing information gaps, then organising online knowledge exchange workshops and finally making presented knowledge and good practices widely accessible through an online BioRural Toolkit (WP4).

Figure 1: Role of Knowledge Exchange Workshops in the BioRural Conceptual Approach

¹ verbatim extract of the project summary

Consistent with the overall approach of the BioRural project, KEWs are designed along the five bioeconomy themes (food and agriculture, forestry and natural habitats, aquatic systems, bioenergy and biomaterials), covering several aspects of relevance (technical, managerial, regulative, marketing, policy) for strengthening the performance of circular bioeconomies in rural areas. In line with the Work Programme, the content of the training comprises of different dimensions: (1) generic principles (eg. circular bioeconomy, cascading use of biomass, biorefining, climate change and natural resources management), (2) theme-specific aspects (eg. Inland and aquatic production of bio-based resources, nutrient recycling, value chain management, market trends), and (3) cross-cutting issues (eg. new product development, regulation and certification, innovation management, for more see comprehensive list, see Table 2). Despite the volume and complexity of the contents of the KEWs, special attention has been paid to ensuring that teaching materials are prepared in a digestible manner for all stakeholder types, providing links for (individual) in-depth learning of themes presented at the KEWs.

As foreseen in the work programme, the workshops were held through the BioRural Toolkit. The presented information and knowledge on rural bio-based solutions remain openly available in the form of easily accessible end-user material.

1.3 Timeline of the task, steps and milestones

Breakdown of the work associated with the planning and implementation of Knowledge Exchange Workshops (KEWs) and corresponding lecture material is presented in Figure 2. As stipulated in the Work Programme, the work on T3.1 has been coordinated by UL, while partners CERTH, AU, AlgEn, GGP, UC, IUNG, LLU and NP actively contributed in the T3.1 activities. As the KEWs are designed around the five bioeconomy themes (agriculture and food, forestry and habitats, aquatic biomass, biochemicals and biomaterials, bioenergy), the project partners have agreed to share the work based on their expertise (more on this in Section 2.1). Division of the work was agreed early in the timeline of the Task (M2), which enabled a timely start of the activities, starting with the drafting of the generic format of the KEWs (see Section 2.2), alongside with an extensive list of cross-cutting themes relevant for rural bioeconomy practitioners, which should be presented at the KEWs, although they can not be attributed to the five bioeconomy themes. These cross-cutting themes were shortlisted and integrated into the syllabi of the five KEWs, which were drafted in M3 and served as a basis for contacting with the preferred lecturers and preparing lecture materials. This can be considered as one of the most critical stages, which required intensive work and frequent coordination between all partners involved in this task. To ensure the smooth running of the work, the core group, consisting of the (co-) leaders of the five KEWs (see Table 1) met regularly on a bi-weekly basis throughout the period M5-M9. Committed work of project partners, in particular the teams responsible for coordinating each of the five KEWs (IUNG, UC, CERTH, Algen, LLU and UL) contributed to the timely achievement of milestone M3.1 (Material for knowledge sharing workshops) in M9.

Figure 2: BioRural Task 3.1 – timeline, milestones and outputs

Lecture materials, whose minimum requirements were brief (2-slide) ppt outlines, were further developed to their final shape throughout the period of the promotion of the KEWs. The promotional activities, which included both active participation in the KEWs and the use of the learning materials, took place continuously during the period from three months before the first workshop (M10) to the last workshop (M20). In parallel with this, the lecture materials have been continuously integrated and made publicly available on the BioRural Toolkit. This allows for easy and permanent access of rural bioeconomy stakeholders and end-users to training materials with relevant scientific, commercial and regulatory information on innovations that contribute towards unlocking bioeconomy potentials in rural areas.

1.4 Structure of the report

The report starts with a detailed description of the approach undertaken in the planning and implementation of the KEWs – both in technical terms, as well in terms of the contents. Methodological description extends to the learning materials developed throughout the KEWs (summaries, course handouts, video presentations, links for further study). The core of the report is made up of workshop materials. For the sake of clarity of the report, the Results section is limited to essential information: technical information about the attendance of the KEWs, and one-page summaries of individual lectures, arranged along the programme of all five KEWs. Materials used at the KEWs are presented in the Annex, and the links to the online contents are visibly presented in dedicated tables. The report concludes by evaluating the outcomes of the KEWs both in terms of the project, and as stand-alone training materials.

2 Methodology

2.1 Internal organization of the work, setting-up of the Taskforce for Knowledge Exchange Workshops

As Task 3.1 is designed in a manner to lay foundations of the entire WP3 (Knowledge exchange and capacity building on rural Bioeconomy), it has been stipulated in the Work Program that the activities are coordinated by the University of Ljubljana (UL) as the leader of WP3. Activities within the Task 3.1 have been designed and performed by a team of experts and researchers with a wide span of expertise along applied life science research and extensive record in strategic research. Their professional background encompasses higher education institutions (AU, UC, LLU), RDI institutions (CERTH, IUNG) and technology developers (Algen, NP). Based on this, we can summarize that the lineup provided a good base for preparation of a consistent and comprehensive program of Knowledge Exchange Workshops.

As the initial step towards in-depth planning and delivery of Knowledge Exchange Workshops, the project teams' engagement in course creation and implementation was determined throughout a self-administered matrix (Table 1). The idea was to set up the teams responsible for the preparation of the training material in line with their key areas of expertise and professional interest.

Table 1: Teams engaged in virtual knowledge exchange workshops

Bioeconomy Theme	Partners engaged in workshop creation & implementation (X), workshop leads (L) and co-leads (L*)								
	UL	CERTH	AU	Algen	GGP	UC	IUNG	LLU	NP
Food&Agriculture	x	x	x	x	x		L		
Forestry&habitats	x					x		L	
Aquatic systems				L			x		
Biochemicals&biomaterials	L								x
Bioenergy		L*	x	x			L*	x	

Responsibilities for course creation and implementation were allocated in line with the outcome of the enquiry and taking into account some additional criteria such as balanced distribution of work and time availability. Table 1 presents the agreed distribution of work along the five Bioeconomy Themes, where L (and L*) represent the teams' (co-)leadership and x represents teams' participation in the preparation of the KEW materials and implementation of the workshops. By taking the lead, project partners also assumed responsibility for the preparation of the learning materials, implementation and reporting on the Knowledge Exchange Workshops.

2.2 Generic format of knowledge exchange workshops

2.2.1 Target audience

As stated in the Work Programme, "...the main objective of BioRural is to create a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network under which related stakeholders will cooperate to promote the currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas to increase the share of Bioeconomy, giving increased value in such remote areas." As presented in Figure 3, BioRural specifies five distinctive stakeholder groups who can benefit from a number of activities and services provided by the BioRural European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN). The T3.1 Knowledge Exchange Workshops as an integral part of the ERBN ecosystem are intended to fill the gaps in understanding and motivation of stakeholder groups that are currently less involved in cooperation networks. Evidence suggests that more attention should be paid to inclusive participation of the general public (Lynch et al., 2020) and the societal stakeholders (Dieken, 2021). We took this into account in designing the KEWs by narrowing down the focus on

general public and professional associations who possess a foundational understanding of conventional bioeconomy technologies (Figure 3). This audience typically has a baseline knowledge derived from exposure to common practices and mainstream applications in the bioeconomy sector.

Figure 3: Stakeholder groups represented European Rural Bioeconomy Network

Intended participants of the KEWs and users of the learning materials were assumed to be familiar with the basic principles and processes involved in utilizing biomass from sources such as agriculture, forestry, and aquatic environments in conventional manufacturing sectors, such as food & feed, wood industry, pulp & paper and similar. This might include awareness of first-generation biofuels, and elementary bio-based materials. However, their grasp on the more advanced aspects of the bioeconomy is limited. Most participants may not fully understand the complexities and innovations driving the circular bioeconomy. For instance, while they may have heard of bioenergy, their knowledge might not extend to cutting-edge technologies like advanced biorefineries or the latest biotechnological advancements in biochemicals and biomaterials. Additionally, they might not be well-versed in the potential market opportunities that arise from these advanced applications, such as bioplastics, bio-based composites, or the integration of bioeconomy principles into broader economic systems. BioRural Knowledge Exchange Workshops aim to bridge this knowledge gap, offering in-depth insights into the technological advancements and economic potentials of a sustainable, circular bioeconomy.

2.2.2 Organisation of the workshops

The structure of our five bioeconomy workshops was designed in a manner that provides comprehensive and engaging content while ensuring that participants can absorb and interact with the material effectively. All workshops followed a consistent format, ensuring that attendees can easily navigate and benefit from each session, regardless of the specific focus area.

Firstly, each workshop was conducted online in a webinar format. This approach allowed us to reach a broad audience while maintaining an organized and professional environment. Interaction during the sessions was facilitated through a chat feature, enabling participants to ask questions and engage with the presenters without disrupting the flow of the workshop. While the possibility of direct interaction was limited, this structure ensures that the most pertinent questions can be addressed efficiently.

The workshops were organized in the period of October 2023 to April 2024 throughout three consecutive days in order to enable a consistent learning experience in a condensed time format. The daily program for each workshop was capped at 120 minutes to strike a balance between providing substantial content and avoiding cognitive overload for the participants. The two-hour sessions were designed to be intensive yet manageable, keeping participants engaged and focused without overwhelming them.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the KEW webinar format

The first day of each workshop is dedicated to consolidating knowledge on the basic concepts and technical principles related to the specific biomass source or biobased application being discussed. This session typically features four to six lectures from experts in the field. These foundational lectures ensure that all participants, regardless of their prior knowledge, have a solid understanding of the key topics.

On the second day, the focus shifts to showcasing good practices. This day is dedicated to real-world examples and success stories. Between six to eight successful innovation adopters are invited to share their experiences. These practitioners outline the factors that contributed to their success, providing valuable insights and practical knowledge that participants can apply to their own projects. This session aims to inspire and educate by highlighting proven strategies and approaches.

The third day of the workshop addresses cross-cutting themes that are critical for the successful development and commercialization of circular bioeconomy products and services. These themes are not tied to any specific biomass source or technology but are essential for the broader bioeconomy landscape. Topics may include policy frameworks, market dynamics, sustainability considerations, and funding opportunities (Table 2). This session aims to equip participants with the knowledge and tools needed to navigate the complex ecosystem of the bioeconomy and to drive innovation and commercialization in their respective fields.

In summary, the KEWs were structured to provide a comprehensive, engaging, and practical learning experience. Each day builds on the previous one, moving from foundational knowledge to practical examples, and finally to broader, cross-cutting issues, ensuring that participants leave with a well-rounded understanding of the circular bioeconomy, enabling them to apply these principles in their own contexts.

Table 2: Cross-cutting themes identified as potentially relevant for presentation at the Knowledge Exchange Workshops

Thematic relevance (R) and actual presentation of the cross-cutting theme (P) at the KEW					
Cross-cutting themes	Food & Agriculture	Forestry & habitats	Aquatic systems	Biochem. & biomaterials	Bioenergy
LCA and associated methods for sustainability evaluation/proofing	R	R	R	R	R, P
Small-scale /versatile / modular biorefining solutions for rural areas	R	R	R	R, P	R
Business models, bioeconomy clusters, value chain management	R	R	R, P	R, P	R
Operations/logistic optimisation	R, P	R	R	R, P	R
Commercialisation and technology transfer of bio-based solutions	R	R	R	R, P	R
Nutrient recovery and biobased fertilisers	R, P	R	R	R, P	R
Use of biogenic by-products&waste streams			R, P	R	R
Opportunities for aqua-&algal technologies	R		R,P	R	R
Intellectual Property Regulation	R	R	R	R, P	R
Regulatory aspects, certification	R, P	R, P	R	R, P	R
IT tools for biobased value chain management	R	R	R, P	R	R
Policy instruments&measures	R, P	R	R	R	R
Private enabling instruments (accelerators, business incubators, venture capital)	R	R	R	R, P	R
Economic modelling in decision making, evaluation	R	R	R	R, P	R
Use of Design Thinking approach	R	R	R	R, P	
Advanced biofuels		R		R	R
Remote sensing and use of GIS for land monitoring and biomass assessment	R, P	R	R		
Extraction of bioactive compounds	R	R, P	R, P	R	
Economic valorization of ecosystems	R	R, P	R		

2.2.3 Preparation of the Knowledge Exchange workshops (from the selection of lecturers and presenters to the preparation of learning materials)

In organizing the KEWs, the selection of lecturers and presenters was conducted with careful consideration. Priority was given to members of the project consortium, leveraging their inherent understanding and commitment to the project goals. However, to enrich the workshops with diverse perspectives and specialized knowledge, external speakers were invited when specific expertise was necessary. This was particularly important to address various regional and technological contexts. Importantly, these external speakers participated voluntarily and without remuneration, showcasing their genuine dedication to advancing rural bioeconomies.

For the selection of showcase practices, two main criteria guided our choices: territorial mix and transferability. We aimed to present a diverse array of examples from different regions, ensuring a broad geographical representation. Additionally, the chosen practices needed to be transferable, offering practical insights that participants could adapt to their own contexts.

Presenters were required to prepare PowerPoint presentations, along with brief, but instructive lecture summaries and a list of resources for those interested in a deeper understanding of the content. This approach ensured that participants had access to both the immediate and extended learning materials. Presentations whose authors have given their explicit permission to be published have been made publicly available on the BioRural Toolkit

2.2.4 Implementation of the Knowledge Exchange Workshops

The time planning for BioRural Knowledge Exchange Workshops ensured they were evenly spread over the designated period from October 2023 to May 2024 (Figure 5). This approach allowed for a balanced and manageable schedule for both participants and organizers.

Figure 5: Timing of the BioRural Knowledge Exchange Workshops

Promotion of the workshops followed a unified strategy. The first phase, starting three months before each workshop, involved announcing the event through various channels (project webpage, BioRural social networks, other sources of online information at the discretion of the project partners). Extended information in a printable format (see example, Figure 6) was added to the announcement with brief information about the workshop and registration details. Upon their registration, the participants received outlook calendar bookmarks with webinar link. The second phase of promotion activities was launched three weeks before the workshop. Registered participants received the final programme of the workshop, augmented short CVs of the speakers. Same information was forwarded through the online campaign (BioRural webpage, social networks of BioRural project, BioRural project partners and partner projects/initiatives).

The image shows three pages of a workshop program for 'Biochemicals and Biomaterials'. The first page is the cover, featuring the BioRural logo and the title 'BioRural Knowledge-exchange Workshops: Advancing the European Rural Bioeconomy'. It includes details for Workshop 1 on 25-27 October 2023, an online event, and a list of benefits such as inspiration for rural businesses and gaining insights into the European rural bioeconomy. The second page is the 'Draft Programme' for Day 1 (25 October 2023), listing sessions from 14:00 to 15:55 with topics like 'Introduction to the workshop', 'Structure and technological properties of biomass (side streams: forestry & wood processing)', and 'From biomass to biomaterials - technological pathways and applications'. The third page is for Day 2 (26 October 2023), listing sessions from 14:00 to 15:15, including 'Brief introduction of the Showcase Tour', 'Ars Pharmea - Food supplements from wood extracts', and 'Circular Paper - paper from biomass waste streams'. Each page includes a 'SPEAKERS' section with small portraits and names of the presenters.

Figure 6: Example of a printable information about the workshop (Workshop 1: Biochemicals and biomaterials)

Webex webinar platform was used to prepare and conduct the workshops. This enabled efficient participant management with automated updates and targeted information exchange with speakers. To ensure smooth execution, presenters are asked to test the platform and check their audio/video equipment one week prior to the workshop.

The workshops are conducted live on Webex Webinar platform, with some presentations pre-recorded as a backup. Recordings have been made available for a vast majority of the presentations, subject to express permission of the presenters. Other parts of the workshops were not recorded to prevent unauthorized use of personal data.

2.2.5 Preparation of learning materials and their integration to the BioRural Toolkit

To further support the learning process, recorded webinars and other lecture materials (powerpoint presentations, lecture summaries, resources for further study) have been made available in a dedicated section 'Online Tutorials' of the BioRural Toolkit (Figure 7). Recognizing the potential language barriers, the recorded webinars (available also on the dedicated BioRural Youtube channel are currently being subtitled in the languages of the countries participating in BioRural project.

The screenshot displays the BioRural Toolkit website interface. On the left, there is a map of Europe with red and orange circles indicating project locations, accompanied by a search bar and filter options for 'Stakeholder Type' and 'Bioeconomy Theme'. The main content area features a grid of nine tiles: 'FACTSHEETS', 'BIOECONOMY INVENTORIES', 'SUCCESS STORIES', 'ONLINE TUTORIALS', 'SKILL BUILDING WORKSHOPS', 'PRACTICE ABSTRACTS', 'BUSINESS BLUEPRINTS', and 'POLICY AND RESEARCH'. The 'ONLINE TUTORIALS' tile is highlighted with a green border. Below this, a detailed view of the 'ONLINE TUTORIALS' section is shown, featuring a header, a descriptive paragraph, and five topic cards: 'Forestry and Habitats', 'Bioenergy', 'Biochemicals & biomaterials', 'Agriculture and food', and 'Aquatic Systems'. Each card includes a representative image, a title, and a date range.

Figure 7: Integration of the Knowledge Exchange Workshop materials into BioRural Toolkit

In the following chapter, we present the programs of the five knowledge exchange workshops, together with the links to online resources and brief descriptions of the contents. Full Powerpoint presentations are annexed to this report.

3 Results

3.1 Participation at the Knowledge Exchange Workshops

Our aim was to target participants with little to no prior knowledge about the selected Bioeconomy topics (see chapter 2.2.1), therefore all lecturers were instructed to share some basic knowledge to ignite a spark in the interest on participants. Table 3 presents the number of registered participants for each knowledge exchange workshop. For each day of each workshop on average between 150-200 participants were registered, while between 50 and 100 participants a day actually attended the workshops. In order to extend the outreach and provide afterlife of the webinars and the teaching materials, all webinars were recorded, post-produced and uploaded on @biorural YouTube channel and fed into BioRural toolkit, together with short bios of lecturers and panelists. Each webinar was the responsibility of the project partner, who selected a suitable facilitator to lead and moderate the whole webinar.

Participants were invited to write any questions they had in the chat during the event, and the answers followed after all presentations at the end. Overall, participants were very satisfied with the content presented in all webinars, highlighting interesting and innovative success stories and new scientific insights in the field of bioeconomy. Easily digestible course outlines equipped with sources/links for further study were prepared. The exception to this is the (small number of) presentations whose authors have not explicitly given permission for their publication. The topics that are not made publicly available are most clearly shown in the summarised tables of Knowledge exchange Workshops (see Tables 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8).

Table 3: Participation at the BioRural Knowledge Exchange Workshops

Theme ('Bioeconomy Pillar')	Leading partners	Contributing partners	Registered participants
Biochemicals&Biomaterials (25-27 Oct'23)	UL	NP, Algen	165
Aquatic systems (28-30 Nov'23)	Algen	IUNG, UL	201
Food&Agriculture (14-16 Feb'24)	UING	UL, CERTH, AU, GGP	156
Forestry&Habitats (12-14 Mar'24)	UC, LLU	UL, UC	177
Bioenergy (16-18 Apr'24)	CERTH, UC	AU, Algen, IUNG, UL	158

Throughout the 5 KEWs we managed to attract 857 participants from 22 countries (UK, Portugal, Spain, France, Belgium, Netherlands, Denmark, Germany, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Finland, Czech Republic, Austria, Slovenia, Croatia, Italy, North Macedonia, Greece, Romania and Moldova). The structure of the participants was very diverse, ranging from students, farmers, entrepreneurs, government officials, teaching staff, to the general public and anyone interested in learning more about the bioeconomy. We reached out to participants through several media to maximise the number of registrations. Each participant was informed about the work of the project and its content, and was invited to register in the BioRural toolkit where they can further foster their professional networks and advance their expertise by exchanging with their counterparts through the ERBN.

The remainder of this chapter is devoted to presenting the learning topics covered in Knowledge Exchange Workshops 1 (Biochemicals and Biomaterials) to 5 (Bioenergy). Topics covered in each of the five workshops are first outlined in summary tables, listing all the titles of the lectures in their order of sequence, a list of all the lecturers with an active link to a short description of each one of them. This is complemented by active links to the lecture handouts (BioRural Toolkit), and to the recording of the lectures (YouTube channel @BioRural). This report briefly describes each lecture with a summarized (up to 1 page) description of the purpose and content of the lecture, an image from the handout and active links to the sources recommended further reading for those who wish to learn more about the topic presented.

3.2 Workshop 1: Biochemicals and biomaterials

Table 4 presents summarized information of the KEW on Biochemicals and biomaterials that was held from 25th to 27th October 2023, with active links to relevant workshop materials on BioRural Toolkit and YT channel @BioRural.

Table 4: Agenda of the Knowledge Exchange Workshop for Biochemicals and Biomaterials

Day 1 - Generic principles	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Structure and technological properties of biomass(side-) streams: forestry & wood processing	Primož Oven (University of Ljubljana)	Link to .pdf	Video
Structure and technological properties of biomass(side-) streams: agri-food sector	Gasan Osojnik (University of Ljubljana)	Link to .pdf	Video
Structure and technological properties of biomass streams: aquatic systems	Maja Berden Zrimec (AlgEn)	Link to .pdf	Video
From biomass to biomaterials - technological pathways and applications	Sabina Berne (University of Ljubljana)	Link to .pdf	Video
Small-scale biorefining solutions - overview, challenges	Blaž Likozar (National Institute of Chemistry)	Link to .pdf	Video
Day 2 - Theme-specific aspects	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Ars Pharmae - food supplements from wood extractives	Marko Domazet (Ars Pharmae)	Link to .pdf	Video
Olea4Value - valorising side streams from olive production	Jakub Sandak (Innorenue)	Link to .pdf	Video
High-end solutions in fungi cultivation	Andrej Gregori (MycoMedica)	Link to .pdf	Video
Circular Paper - paper from biomass waste streams	David Ravnjak (Pulp & Paper Institute)	Link to .pdf	Video
Soluble green packaging solutions	Callum O'Connell (Notpla)	Link to .pdf	Video
Green chemicals from pyrolysis oil as wood preservative and adhesives	Bror Sundqvist (Vinnova)	Link to .pdf	Video
Day 3 - Cross-cutting issues	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Application of design thinking in new product development	Blaž Zupan (University of Ljubljana)	Link to .pdf	Video
Bio-based content certification: Better Biomass Certificate	Harmen Willemse (NEN)	Link to .pdf	Video
Intellectual property management, commercialisation of innovative biobased products	Gabriela Droga Mazovec (University of Ljubljana)	Link to .pdf	Video
Biobased start-up ecosystem management – learning Food ecosystems accelerator	Janne Saarikko (Nat. Resources Institute Finland (Luke), Founder Institute)		Video
Circular Economy and Value Chains Transformation	Bart Stegeman (EIT Climate)	/	/

3.2.1 Structure and technological properties of biomass(side-) streams: forestry & wood processing

First lecturer was professor dr. Primož Oven from University of Ljubljana, Department of Wood Science. His lecture delves into the crucial topic of biomass side streams in forestry and wood processing. It places these discussions within the framework of the circular bioeconomy concept, offering an alternative to the conventional linear economy that has led to adverse climate and environmental outcomes. An audit by the European Court of Auditors highlighted the need to focus on circular product design and production processes rather than waste management, signaling the urgency for change. The lecture emphasizes the potential for integrating biobased solutions, particularly in rural regions, by first addressing fundamental concepts related to biomass in forestry and the wood industry.

It provides insights into the structure and properties of woody biomass, underlining the importance of understanding this versatile material. The discussion then moves to the potential of biorefining, offering a path to harness the diverse utility of woody biomass. An exploration of cascading valorization exemplifies how low-quality woody biomass residues can be transformed into high-value products. This involves extracting valuable compounds, such as extractives and nanocellulose. Extractives, defined by their solubility in polar and non-polar solvents, serve as low-volume, high-value bio-based materials. Nanocellulose, derived from extractive-free woody biomass, emerges as a high-tech material with virtually limitless applications.

In conclusion, the lecture delivers three core takeaways: woody biomass, as a renewable resource, can participate in cascading processes and diversified small-scale biorefining, even in rural settings. The key lies in adhering to circular bioeconomy principles, which offer sustainable, eco-friendly alternatives to conventional practices. This lecture plays a vital role in advocating for the valorization of biomass side streams in forestry, furthering the cause of the circular bioeconomy.

Figure 8: Nanocellulose production (detail from KEW1 presentation, Oven, 2023)

Figure 9: Nanocellulose application (detail from KEW1 presentation, Oven, 2023)

Suggested further reading:

- [IAWA list of microscopic features for hardwood identification](#)
- [Long-term transcriptomic and chromatin memory in embryonic stem cells](#)
- [Study on the environmental implications of the increased use of heavy-duty vehicles for the transport of goods](#)
- [Special report 17/2023: Climate spending in the 2021-2027 EU budget](#)

3.2.2 Structure and technological properties of biomass(side-) streams: agri-food sector

The second lecturer was assist. Prof. Ilja Gasan Osojnik Črnivec from University of Ljubljana and National Institute of Chemistry. His lecture provides a comprehensive overview of biomass streams in the Agri-food sector. The study addresses the vulnerabilities, properties, and opportunities related to efficiently harnessing these resources. The environmental impact of the food system is undeniable, with European food consumption alone responsible for a significant portion of the overall climate impact. The European food system, in its current form, places an unsustainable demand on planetary resources, requiring 3.6 times the Earth’s ecological capacity.

Key to addressing this issue is understanding the biomass generated in the agriculture and food production processes. The European agriculture sector yields one billion tons of biomass, which, when converted to energy equivalents, represents a substantial energy resource, with one-third coming from food waste. Surprisingly, energy crops contribute significantly less, raising questions about resource allocation. Food processing generates diverse production residues and by-products, which can offer valuable bio-based solutions. Identifying and categorizing these streams is essential for optimizing their utilization. Processing residues, including everything that isn’t a primary product, generate a staggering 55 million tons of waste in the European Union.

This study emphasizes the importance of preventing food waste, reducing it, and putting surplus to human or animal use. Any remaining biomass should be processed into valuable fractions, such as bioactives, fibers, and materials for chemical transformation. This cascading approach ensures the most efficient and sustainable use of Agri-food biomass. Promising applications are emerging, such as functional food ingredients, combining dietary fibers and protein-rich by-products for new food formulations, innovative extraction technologies, and natural fiber solutions for non-wood-based paper and packaging production. Additionally, the study highlights opportunities for energy farming and the production of biogenic chemicals without disrupting traditional food production.

In conclusion, this research offers a comprehensive understanding of Agri-food biomass streams and presents innovative solutions to address environmental concerns while capitalizing on the potential of these resources. These insights are invaluable for moving toward a more sustainable and circular Agri-food system.

VALORISATION OF AGRIFOOD RESIDUES

EXAMPLES OF RECENTLY PUBLISHED STUDIES

Hop shoots, stems and leaves

Olive leaves, branches and pomace

Pomegranate peels

Onion cuttings and peels

Research performed in the scope of national research programme 'Biochemical characterisation of natural compounds' (ARRS, P4-0121)

<p>Microbial activity between hop</p>	<p>Enhanced yield of oleuropein from olive leaves using ultrasound-assisted extraction</p>	<p>Extraction of Polyphenols and Valorization of Fibers from Istrian-Grown Pomegranate (<i>Punica granatum</i> L.)</p>	<p>Waste streams in onion production: use of antimicrobial and antioxidant</p>
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Figure 10: Valorisation of agrifood residues (detail from KEW1 presentation, Osojnik Črnivec, 2023)

Inedible food parts as an ingredient or functional food additive

Figure 11: Inedible food parts as an ingredient or functional food additive (detail from KEW1 presentation, Osojnik Črničev, 2023)

Suggested further reading:

- [A global database for emissions from the food system](#)
- [Consumption Footprint Platform: Food](#)
- [Infographics: Biomass sources and uses in EU-27](#)
- [EU biomass use in a net-zero economy](#)
- [Climate impact of edible food waste management: A review](#)
- [Food waste management](#)

3.2.3 Structure and technological properties of biomass streams: aquatic systems

The third lecturer is an expert in Aquatic systems, dr. Maja Berden Zimec from AlgEn. The focus of her lecture was on various aquatic systems, ranging from ponds and rivers to oceans, and their vital role in providing diverse bio materials and bioactive compounds. These resources, with their unique properties, offer promising applications in industries such as agriculture, food production, and biotechnology. The presentation emphasizes the importance of transitioning from waste to resource utilization, following established technologies like anaerobic digestion, fermentation, and extraction. It introduces a novel approach to wastewater management, utilizing algae. Algae-based wastewater treatment not only reduces costs but also enhances treatment quality, removes pathogens, and reduces emissions significantly.

Case studies from around the world illustrate the practicality of this approach in turning wastewater into biomass for agricultural purposes and beyond. The versatility of algae is highlighted, from biofuels and animal feed to cosmetics and food additives. The discussion also addresses the challenges facing algae-based biofuels in terms of cost competitiveness and outlines their enormous potential in agriculture. Algae are more than simple fertilizers; they enhance soil quality, water retention, and offer biological benefits for plant health. As Europe moves toward a circular economy, algae technology is recognized as a valuable solution.

Algen collaborates with various partners in research projects, contributing to the ongoing development and implementation of algae technology in diverse applications, such as carbon capture, biofuel production, and resource utilization. The presentation underscores the promising prospects of algae in revolutionizing our approach to waste management, energy production, and sustainable agriculture.

Producing algae on wastewater

- Produced on wastewater
- Produced on non-arable land
- Recycle nutrients
- Recycle, reuse CO₂
- Water treatment:
 - Reduced treatment cost
 - Improved treatment quality
 - Remove pathogens, odours

www.biorural.eu

Figure 12: Producing algae on wastewater (detail from KEW1 presentation, Berden Zimec, 2023)

Classical aerobic WWT

Figure 13: Scheme for producing algae on wastewater (detail from KEW1 presentation, Berden Zimec, 2023)

3.2.4 From biomass to biomaterials - technological pathways and applications

The fourth lecturer on the first day was assist. Prof. Sabina Berne, from University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical faculty, Department of Agronomy. Her presentation was about our current economy heavily reliant on non-renewable resources, the depletion of these resources and the acceleration of climate change through the release of sequestered carbon into the atmosphere pose significant challenges. In the pursuit of a circular bioeconomy, biomass emerges as a sustainable feedstock to produce bio-based products, reducing our dependence on fossil fuels. When biomass enters the conversion system, the resulting bio-based products can be considered carbon-neutral, as the carbon released is already part of the biogenic carbon cycle.

Bio-based products, derived partially or wholly from biomass, encompass a range of intermediates, including fibers, composites, polymers, chemicals, as well as semi-finished and final products. Standards for bio-based products play a crucial role in increasing market transparency, providing common reference methods and requirements for verifying claims regarding bio-based content and sustainability criteria. Bio-refining, a key strategy in the circular bioeconomy, involves the sustainable processing of biomass into a spectrum of marketable products. This approach enables the closure of feedstock material, water, and carbon cycles, ensuring optimal and sustainable use of biomass on a large scale, with positive social, economic, and environmental impacts. The IEA Bioenergy Task 42 developed a bio-refinery classification system, outlining various platforms for bio-refining processes.

Examining the status of bio-refineries in the EU27, countries like Finland, Netherlands, Sweden, and Italy lead in the number of bio-refineries, predominantly utilizing secondary biomass. Different types of feedstocks, including primary (aquatic biomass, dedicated specialty crops) and secondary biomass (microbial biomass, residues from agriculture and forestry, recycled bio-based products), contribute to bio-refining processes. Conversion processes involve biochemical, chemical, thermal-chemical, and mechanical methods. Notably, biochemical processes like fermentation are widely employed, with anaerobic digestion being a prominent example.

The diversity of bio-refinery conversion pathways is highlighted, with both bottom-up (upgrading existing biomass processing facilities) and top-down approaches (new highly integrated industrial value chains) shaping the future landscape. The market for bio-based chemicals and polymers is growing annually, driven by green chemistry requirements and increased demand for sustainable alternatives in various sectors. In conclusion, the adoption of biomass as a feedstock in bio-refining processes holds promise for achieving sustainability goals in the circular bioeconomy.

Figure 14: Key enabling strategy of bioeconomy (detail from KEW1 presentation, Berne, 2023)

Biochemical conversion processes

Figure 15: Biochemical conversion processes (detail from KEW1 presentation, Berne, 2023)

Suggested further reading:

- [The role of the EU bioeconomy in climate change mitigation and the transition to a circular economy](#)
- [Bio-based products – Vocabulary](#)
- [Biorefining](#)
- [Biorefining brochure](#)
- [Biorefining databases](#)
- [Life cycle assessment of a lignocellulosic biorefinery for bioethanol production: A case study](#)
- [Life cycle assessment of biogas production from food waste](#)
- [Advances in biocatalytic processes for the production of biofuels and chemicals](#)
- [The role of nanocellulose in the development of sustainable materials and technologies](#)
- [Overview of current technologies for the management of bio-waste](#)

3.2.5 Small-scale biorefining solutions - overview, challenges

The last lecture of the first day was held by prof. Blaž Likozar, who is leading the Department of Catalysis and Chemical Reaction Engineering at the National Institute of Chemistry (NIC). His lecture delves into the concept, relevance, and challenges of small-scale verified solutions in the realm of bio-refining. Addressing the imperative of transitioning away from fossil fuels, the authors explore the state of biomass technology in Europe and globally. Notably, they highlight the predominant focus of bio-refineries on energy and biofuel, emphasizing the challenges posed by the economy of scale.

The presentation underscores the necessity of localized bio-refining solutions, aligning with industrial structures and minimizing carbon footprints associated with material transportation. Drawing insights from the Slovenian context, where biomass resources are comparatively abundant, the authors argue for a paradigm shift toward materials and chemicals in bio-refining. Key considerations include the scarcity of technologies catering to the fractionation of biomass and the need for hands-on processes.

The author presents a case study of a Slovenian pilot bio-refinery, outlining its strategic importance in addressing the bottleneck of biomass resource availability. They stress the relevance of establishing such facilities along the value chain of processing industries. The relevance of bio-refining in regions with underexploited waste or residual biomass becomes evident. The lecturer proposes a shift in focus from energy-centric bio-refining to material-centric bio-refining, aligning with the strengths of the local industrial structure. This approach, the authors argue, would bridge the gap between strong industrial demand for bio-based products and the need for locally sourced materials. In conclusion with a call to address the challenges of scaling up bio-refining operations, emphasizing the need for intermediate-scale infrastructure. A focus on delivering high-quality lignin and cellulose, along with the flexibility to cater to diverse biomass compositions and sizes, is crucial for fostering sustainable bio-based materials.

The professor present ongoing efforts to tackle these challenges, citing a reference case in China and outlining plans for a pilot bio-refinery in the Valencia region. Despite facing administrative hurdles, the lecturer express optimism about overcoming these obstacles and realizing the potential of bio-refining for sustainable material development.

The Concept

- The utilization of **biomass** as a **versatile raw material** for **different industrial products** – advancing in approaching bio-economy faster.
- The **Local2Local** principle – **abundant, diverse and mixed residual biomass** as a feedstock for **locally-sourced materials' production**.
- Sustainability, efficiency and flexibility – **modular equipment design/the integration of best available mature techniques**.
- Eliminate the bottleneck of biomass resource fractionation, while downstream value chains have already been established.**
- Modularity** mostly applies to **appending operations upstream or downstream**, the heart being the **production of cellulose**.

Figure 16: Key concepts for unlocking bioeconomy potentials in rural areas (detail from KEW1 presentation, Likozar, 2023)

Results

Numerous **innovations** have been developed (15 innovations, 7 patents pending, 8 new products) and 5 **new value chains** created. Joint research (over 250 researchers from academia and industry) on **technology and product lines** are performed:

- Comprehensive **database** of over 60 different biomass residual streams validated for potential use
- **Advanced processes** of biomass fractionation and converting; **nanocellulose** produced from residual biomass sources, **green chemicals** to be used in coating, resin and adhesive industries
- **Bio-based packaging** with improved **barrier properties** and **functionalities**
- **Bio-based functional products**; high performing **filtering and insulating materials**, lightweight and thermostable **bio-composites** for different applications (automotive, electrical industry)
- **Enzymes** produced from **biological decomposition** of waste
- **Advanced processes** for end waste treatment and **material recovery**; mechanical, biological decomposition, innovative **Waste-to-Energy system**

Figure 17: RDI contributions to biobased solutions applicable at small scales (detail from KEW1 presentation, Likozar, 2023)

Suggested further reading:

- [Advanced biocatalytic strategies for sustainable chemical production](#)
- [Recent advances in the valorization of food waste](#)
- [Recent developments in biogas production from agricultural waste](#)
- [Advances in catalytic conversion of lignocellulosic biomass to biofuels](#)
- [Sustainable strategies for bioenergy production: Advances and challenges](#)

3.2.6 Ars Pharmae - food supplements from wood extractives

The first lecturer of the second day of the Knowledge Exchange Workshop was Marko Domazet, the CEO of Ars Pharmae, a Slovenian company dedicated to innovating natural food supplements for human health. His lecture was about the company he founded and the bio-based products they developed, their core mission is to offer high-quality, natural products for families, including food supplements for both children and adults. Ars Pharmae's commitment to excellence is underscored by their research-driven approach, with a particular focus on developing ingredients and products backed by clinical studies. The overarching goal is to enhance people's quality of life and well-being. Marko emphasized their collaboration with esteemed institutions, including universities in Ljubljana and Maribor.

Their patent for abanol, a natural ingredient derived from silver fir bark, underscores their dedication to innovation. The company maintains the highest quality standards in their product manufacturing process. Their products are readily accessible in Slovenia through pharmacies and specialized health shops, and they also have an online presence, enabling global access. Notably, their product against fatigue and burnout has earned recognition as the number one product in Slovenia. Additionally, the company has been honored in the United States as one of the five most innovative products in 2010 and 2016. The company's dedication extends to the realm of sports, where they actively support athletes in basketball and skiing. This includes partnerships with the Slovenian Ski Association and the national basketball team. Ars Pharmae's origin story is rooted in their dissatisfaction with conventional treatments, which often led to side effects and superficial symptom relief.

This drove their quest for a more holistic and natural approach to health. Their work also aligns with the growing demand for integrated well-being solutions and a desire for healthier, longer lives. Recognizing the aging population and the widespread presence of chronic diseases, Ars Pharmae has delved into bioactive compounds that have a positive impact on various aspects of health, from the brain to the cardiovascular system, and even mitigating silent inflammation in the body. Their research has culminated in the extraction of valuable bioactive compounds from silver fir bark, which they incorporate into their food supplements. Their manufacturing process, starting with the careful selection of silver fir trees, ensures the highest quality of raw materials. The extraction process utilizes only water, avoiding solvents in line with sustainable practices. Rigorous quality control and traceability from sourcing to commercialization are central to their commitment to maintaining product consistency.

Ars Pharmae takes pride in their range of products, all of which contain their unique extract, offering a wide array of health benefits. This includes addressing fatigue and stress, preventing cardiovascular diseases, and boosting immunity. The high antioxidant properties of their extract enable its versatile use in various applications. In conclusion, Ars Pharmae, under Marko's leadership, is a pioneering company with a strong commitment to innovation and improving the quality of life for individuals and families.

Figure 18: 7 pillars of health and Potential health benefits of Polyphenols (detail from KEW1 presentation, Domazet, 2023)

3.2.7 Olea4Value - valorising side streams from olive production

The second lecture was held by Jakub Sandak, who is leading the research group in Advanced Manufacturing at the InnoRenew Centre of Excellence and is associate professor at the Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Science and Information Technology at the University of Primorska. His presentation explores a vital initiative aimed at maximizing the utilization of olive by-products. The project, aptly named “Olea For Value,” represents a collaborative effort with partners across Europe and focuses on developing a comprehensive valorization system for olive leaves and other by-products. Olive cultivation, one of humanity’s most enduring practices, yields not only the renowned fruits but also a significant volume of leaves. These leaves are often overlooked, despite their potential value across multiple industries, including food, feed, pharmaceuticals, and cosmetics.

The composition of these leaves, however, can vary widely due to seasonal, genetic, and cultural factors. The heart of this project lies in understanding the variability of olive by-products, particularly the leaves, and how they can be leveraged efficiently. The aim is to transform what is often considered agricultural waste into a valuable resource for diverse applications. Jakub explains that there are two main sources of olive leaves: spring pruning to allow more light for the trees and autumn harvesting when leaves naturally fall. These processes generate substantial biomass, but farmers often struggle with disposing of it. The dilemma is that these olive leaves harbor an abundance of valuable chemicals, more than a thousand of which are wasted each year when the biomass is burned to prevent insect infestation. “Olea4Value” seeks to change this narrative. The project involves the development of a “smart biorefinery” concept, with a primary focus on a Biomass Suitability Index (BSI). This index acts as a critical guide in determining the most suitable valorization processes for the diverse biomass resources. The BSI, ranging from 0 to 1, assesses the biomass’s suitability for biorefinery.

A high value does not necessarily indicate a one-size-fits-all solution; instead, the selection of valorization processes considers factors such as sustainability, economics, and environmental impact. To measure the quality properties of the biomass, spectroscopic solutions are employed. Portable instruments, which are capable of determining origin, moisture content, chemical composition, and more, are utilized to streamline the assessment process. The success of this technique is evident in its ability to predict the content of essential compounds, such as oleuropein. In summary, the “Olea4Value” project is a sustainability initiative aimed at unlocking the untapped potential of olive by-products. The incorporation of a Biomass Suitability Index and spectroscopic solutions provides a comprehensive framework for valorization, emphasizing sustainability and efficiency. This project marks a promising step toward a greener, more sustainable future in the olive industry.

www.innorenew.eu

OLEAF4VALUE

- is a three-year project that will develop a **complete valorization system for the olive leaf**
- The goal of OLEAF4VALUE is to set up the basis of **six smart value chains** based on a newly developed 4.0 concept:
 - Smart Dynamic Multi-Valorisation-Route Biorefinery (**SAMBIO**) for the cascade valorisation of the olive leaf biomass
 - according to its initial composition (Biomass Suitability Index – **BSI**)

Biomass Suitability Index (BSI)

- is a numerical indicator (0 - 1) of raw resources quality, used for determining how a given set of biomass characteristics corresponds to the specific requirements for given biorefinery valorisation route.

Figure 19: Valorization cascade in olive sector, and Biomass suitability Index for olive leaves (Potential health benefits of Polyphenols (detail from KEW1 presentation, Sandak, 2023)

3.2.8 High-end solutions in fungi cultivation

The third lecturer of the second day was assist. Prof. dr. Andrej Gregori who has been engaged in applied mycology for more than twenty years. His lecture provides insights into the remarkable journey of a company that originated in a century-old barn in northwestern Slovenia, close to international borders. The founder, a former student specializing in medicinal compounds, embarked on a small-scale venture involving the cultivation of mushrooms from agricultural leftovers, such as olive oil pomace and spent brewery grains. The company’s journey is marked by collaborations with various academic institutions and extensive research projects. The research initiatives cover a wide spectrum, including the investigation of antioxidant compounds in mushrooms, revealing variations even within strains of the same species.

Beyond their culinary use, mushrooms offer incredible potential, such as the production of enzymes that contribute to sustainable paper production. Innovative applications of mushroom mycelium are also explored, ranging from creating materials for furniture and lamps to developing various composites. Collaboration with international faculties and institutions furthers the research in this domain. One of the company’s primary focuses is on the medicinal properties of mushrooms, particularly those related to addressing metabolic syndrome and preventing tumor proliferation. Collaborative projects span regions from Serbia and Turkey to Russia, China, and Switzerland. Maintaining a diversified collection of medicinal and cultivated mushroom strains, the company is equipped to lead pioneering projects.

For example, ongoing research involves the extraction and purification of compounds from mushrooms for addressing metabolic syndrome. Despite being a small company, the business is highly tech-oriented. This enterprise operates in a tourist area, categorized as an agricultural enterprise, and boasts organic and vegetarian products. With a stringent focus on research and quality, the company avoids heavy marketing and invests heavily in R&D. This approach has sustained the business for over two decades. The company’s product range encompasses food supplements for humans and animals, and it supplies raw materials to other supplement producers. The overarching theme of the presentation underscores a commitment to research, innovation, and sustainable practices, which has been the cornerstone of the company’s remarkable journey.

The image displays a collage of presentation slides and product images. The slides are from the 11th International Medicinal Conference in Belgrade, Serbia. One slide, titled 'A NEWLY DEVELOPED SUPPLEMENT WITH ERINACINE A CONTENT', is for LECTURE 08 and lists speakers Marija Gregori¹, Erik Bir, Boštjan Jančar², and Tinka I. Another slide, titled 'COPRO PROJECT: DEVELOPMENT OF STANDARDIZED FOOD SUPPLEMENT', is for LECTURE 09 and lists speakers Erik Biri¹, Marija Gregori¹, and razel², Rok Pilon². The slides mention funding from the European Union (NextGenerationEU) and the Republic of Slovenia (Ministry of Economic Development and Technology). Product images show bottles of 'HERICUM ERINACEUS' and 'CORDYCEPS' supplements.

Figure 20: Medicinal mushroom products (detail from KEW1 presentation, Gregori, 2023)

3.2.9 Circular Paper - paper from biomass waste streams

The fourth lecture on the good-practices day was held by dr. David Ravnjak who is the managing director of the Pulp and Paper Institute. His presentation highlights the journey of paper innovation that is centered around utilizing residual biomass, specifically cellulose-rich materials, for sustainable paper production. The discussion emerges from the background of the Pulp and Paper Institute, an institution specializing in the development of materials and products from biomass. The core challenge addressed is the growing need for cellulose fibers, as the paper industry relies significantly on recycled fibers. This led to the quest for alternative sources and the exploration of non-wood fibers. Insights from the European Association of Paper Industry's recognition of non-wood fibers as an innovation frontier for Europe set the stage.

The Pulp and Paper Institute explores diverse sources of biomass, including fast-growing plants cultivated intentionally for cellulose production, waste streams from agriculture and food processing, and invasive alien plants targeted for removal. A chemical analysis reveals that these alternative biomass sources contain significant cellulose, lower lignin, and valuable hemicellulose. Assessment of the quality of paper produced from these alternative sources indicates mechanical and printing properties on par with conventional paper. Moreover, these cellulose sources offer opportunities for producing cardboard and packaging materials, demonstrating the versatility of these innovations. Challenges encompass seasonal and geographical variations in biomass availability, the limited presence of specialized biorefineries for conversion, and the economic feasibility of utilizing materials with low cellulose content.

Additionally, the high variability in paper properties from these alternative cellulose sources necessitates strategic use in partial exchange for conventional fiber materials, depending on the desired paper characteristics. The Pulp and Paper Institute not only delves into these innovative approaches but also provides a valuable entry point into further research and exploration, setting the stage for a sustainable and diversified future in the paper industry.

Potential sources of biomass

- Fast growing plants cultivated for cellulose production (miscanthus, silphie)
- Waste streams from:
 - ❖ wood processing (sawdust, pruning residues)
 - ❖ agriculture (straw, reeds & grasses, hemp, kenaf, tomato stems, hops, bamboo)
 - ❖ food processing (beetroot pulp, wheat bran, onion peelings, fruit pulps)
- Invasive alien plant species (Japanese Knotweed, Canadian Goldenrod, Black Locust)
- **Pulp and paper institute has built a database containing key material properties of more than 50 non-wood biomass sources of cellulose**

Figure 21: Potential sources of residual biomass for sustainable paper production (detail from KEW1 presentation, Ravnjak, 2023)

Figure 22: Paper produced from invasive plants (detail from KEW1 presentation, Ravnjak, 2023)

Suggested further reading:

- [Energy production and management in the 21st century](#)
- [Part II: Bioeconomy-Biorefinery](#)
- [Evaluation of different agricultural residues as raw materials for pulp and paper production using a semichemical process](#)
- [Non-wood fibre is a new innovation frontier for Europe's paper and board sector, shows nova-Institute study](#)

3.2.10 NotPla - Soluble green packaging solutions

The fifth lecture was held by Callum O’Connel, who has a MPhil in Marine Science. His lecture was about the pressing issue of plastic pollution, particularly its proliferation in single-use plastic packaging. While plastics are incredibly versatile and useful, their persistence in the environment poses a significant problem. Microplastics have even been found within living organisms, exemplifying the scale of the issue. The talk introduces seaweed as a sustainable and biodegradable alternative to address this problem. The journey begins with a company founded in 2017, committed to making single-use plastic packaging disappear.

They initially developed edible water capsules made from seaweed, designed to replace single-use plastic bottles. This simple concept evolved into a broader exploration of seaweed’s diverse properties. The company utilizes both seaweed extracts and less refined seaweed materials in their product development. Seaweed extracts have proven valuable in creating films, pouches, and coating boxes with outstanding water and oil barrier properties. These innovations aim to displace traditional plastic products and reduce plastic waste in the environment. Sustainable sourcing of seaweed remains a significant challenge. Engaging with rural communities and community-owned seaweed farms, like Carry More, is a crucial step in promoting sustainable seaweed cultivation and benefiting local communities.

Notably, these initiatives have generated jobs and improved well-being in rural areas. The environmental impact of seaweed-based products is substantial, with millions of single-use plastics being replaced. Seaweed is emerging as a versatile and eco-friendly resource. The presentation emphasizes the importance of continuing to replace traditional plastics with seaweed-based alternatives to foster a more sustainable future. This journey towards sustainable packaging solutions has garnered recognition, such as the Shop Prize, and has provided opportunities to raise awareness of seaweed as a valuable resource. Resources are provided for those interested in exploring the economic, industrial, and environmental aspects of seaweed utilization.

Figure 23: Societal challenge as a business opportunity (Article about microplastics, the Guardian, 2023)

Figure 24: Seaweed and shellfish farm structure in NotPla (detail from KEW1 presentation, O’Connell, 2023)

3.2.11 Green chemicals from pyrolysis oil as wood preservative and adhesives

The last lecture of the second day of the Knowledge Exchange Workshop was held by Dr. Bror Sundqvist, from Luleå University of Technology, Department of Engineering Sciences and Mathematics. His presentation outlines a research project supported by the Swedish government, focusing on innovative alternatives to fossil-based chemicals. With only 2% of global chemicals derived from non-fossil sources, the project explores the untapped potential of forest residues, viewed from both a technical and market feasibility perspective. Situated in a rural area, the initiative is perfectly aligned with the local ethos. The project, part of a broader innovation program, encompasses two phases and has a consortium of three agencies working together.

The budget for this endeavor is 4.2 million Swedish crowns, and the project is slated to continue from the present until 2025. The first phase successfully evaluated pyrolysis oil produced as a byproduct by a high-quality biochar company, revealing promising results in terms of the potential applications of the compounds in various chemical processes. As a next step, the project required downstream partners within the value chain. After overcoming challenges, such as risk assessments and non-disclosure agreements, the second phase was approved in March 2023. In this phase, the project will investigate potential applications of these compounds as additives in paint formulations and other products, with the participation of prominent companies like Sherman Williams. The project is structured into six work packages, aimed at addressing coordination, dissemination, technical feasibility, techno-economy, sustainability, and market analysis.

Challenges on the horizon include ensuring oil stability, managing seasonal variations, determining the effectiveness and economic feasibility of chemical conversions, and evaluating market acceptance and product performance. The ultimate goal of this project is to contribute to the sustainable production of green chemicals and demonstrate that stable pyrolysis oil production from forest residues is a viable endeavor. Moreover, the growing demand for environmentally friendly additives due to stricter environmental regulations makes this project even more relevant. This presentation offers insight into the current status of the project and its future objectives, encouraging questions and discussions for those interested in its progress.

Hypothesis step 1 project

- commercial producer of high quality biochar (Envigas AB)
- find valuable compounds from pyrolysis oil
- initial university tests of pyrolysis oil
- initial university tests of compounds as wood protection agent

Pre - Hypothesis step 2 project

- value chain formation – May 2022 to November 2022
- NDA for accessing step 1 results – presumptive partners
- addition of chemical companies
- addition of skills and competence
- addition of downstream partners for evaluation and and validation
- addition of competence for LCA

Promising technical results
 Interesting wood mold protection results
 Difficult to asses further technical feasibility
 Difficult to asses market potentials

Application March 2023

- Value chain from forest company to paint manufacturer and wooden board producer
- Potential and feasibility of green chemical compounds
- Additive in paint formulations and/or in matrix for wooden boards

Figure 25: Pyrolysis oil - steps in new product development and commercialization (detail from KEW1 presentation, Sundqvist, 2023)

Suggested further reading:

- [Bio-oil valorization](#)
- [GC/MS Characterisation of liquids generated from low-temperature pyrolysis of wood](#)
- [Production and purification of crystallized levoglucosan from pyrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass](#)
- [Bonding performance of wood bonded with adhesive mixtures composed of phenol-formaldehyde and bio-oil](#)

3.2.12 Application of design thinking in new product development

The first lecture of the third day of the Knowledge Exchange Workshop, where we presented cross-cutting themes, was held by prof. dr. Blaž Zupan, from University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Economics, Department for Entrepreneurship. He talked about design thinking, the world of research, product development can be an enigma, but it's also an opportunity to bring innovative solutions to the market. This presentation delves into the realm of new product development, showing how design thinking can expedite the process while enhancing efficiency and success rates. Driven by a decade of experience as a mentor, professor, consultant, and entrepreneur, the speaker explores how to convert market opportunities into viable products that cater to real needs. Dr. Blaž Zupan emphasizes that understanding the problem at its core is pivotal.

He introduces the design thinking methodology, a structured approach to problem-solving that comprises five key stages: understand, define, ideate, prototype, and test. For the sake of brevity, we'll focus on the understand and test stages here. Understanding begins with data collection and research, fostering an informed foundation for decision-making. The speaker stresses the importance of data in making effective, rational choices. The subsequent test phase is where ideas and prototypes are put to the test, iterating and improving the product as data reveals insights. Research experience is invaluable in these stages, as it aligns with the process of experimenting, testing hypotheses, and basing decisions on data. Dr. Zupan highlights that the best entrepreneurs often consist of two key individuals: a data-oriented researcher and a sales-savvy extrovert. Combining these skills can create a successful entrepreneurial partnership, underscoring the role of teamwork in product development.

In essence, new product development is a structured journey where understanding the problem and rigorous testing pave the way for innovative solutions. The presentation provides a glimpse into the world of entrepreneurial research, offering valuable insights for those embarking on this endeavor.

Figure 26: Application of design thinking in new product development I (detail from KEW1 presentation, Zupan, 2023)

Suggested further reading:

- [6 Resources to help you learn design thinking](#)
- [Top 9 design thinking books in 2024](#)
- [10+ best articles on design thinking](#)
- [35 best design thinking blogs and websites in 2024](#)
- [Design thinking articles](#)

3.2.13 Bio-based content certification: Better Biomass Certificate

The second lecturer of the third day was Harmen Willemse, he is a Scheme manager of the Better Biomass certificate of the Dutch Standardisation Institute. His presentation sheds light on two certification schemes in the sustainability domain. As a freelance consultant, he manages these schemes, one dedicated to the sustainability of biomass and the other to bio-based materials. The journey begins with a glimpse into Harmen's extensive background, including his tenure at the Dutch standards institute and his present freelance consultancy role. This segues into an exploration of the certification schemes he currently oversees.

The focus is on answering two pivotal questions in the realm of bio-based products: What is the bio-based content, and is the biomass used from sustainable sources? The first question delves into the bio-based share in a product, as defined by European standards. Here, companies can gain certification to display a label denoting their product's bio-based content percentage, which may range from 1 to 100. This approach ensures clarity in conveying a product's bio-based attributes, considering factors beyond carbon to include hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, and more. The second question revolves around biomass sustainability, as it's paramount to ensure that the benefits of using sustainable biomass aren't negated by negative impacts.

The certification scheme here focuses on all forms of biomass, excluding food and feed. It encompasses applications like electricity, heating, and transport fuels. The sustainability criteria extend beyond environmental factors to encompass socio-economic aspects like labour conditions and local economic prosperity. Companies aiming for certification must adhere to comprehensive requirements that cover aspects of greenhouse gases, carbon sinks, biodiversity, soil quality, and socio-economic sustainability. Certification involves a rigorous audit process to ensure compliance with these criteria, with surveillance audits conducted annually.

The presentation offers valuable insights into the importance of sustainability in biomass use and the role of certification in communicating these sustainability practices to the market. The documents and resources available on the website provide further details on these certification schemes, enhancing understanding and transparency in the bio-based industry.

Determination of bio-based content

- EN 16785-1 specifies a method of determining the bio-based content in products, based on the **radiocarbon analysis and elemental analysis**.
 - Involves not only the **bio-based carbon content**, but also the other elements **hydrogen, oxygen** and **nitrogen**
- EN 16785-1 is applicable to any solid, liquid and gaseous product containing carbon, provided that a statement is available about the elemental composition and the bio-based content of the product(s).

Figure 27: Determination of bio-based content & How to get the better biomass certificate (detail from KEW1 presentation, Willemse, 2023)

3.2.14 Intellectual property management, commercialisation of innovative biobased products

The third lecturer of the third day was dr Gabriela Droga Mazovec, from Jožef Štefan Institute. Her presentation offers a comprehensive overview of intellectual property management and the commercialization of novel bio-based products. Intellectual property encompasses a realm of legally protected creations, from patents to trademarks, copyrights, and industrial designs. These protections not only grant recognition but also financial benefits to inventors. The focus of this presentation centers on patents, which bestow exclusive rights to the patent holder for a limited period, typically up to 20 years. Novelty is at the heart of patents. An invention must be genuinely innovative, including at least one inventive step.

This presentation clarifies the distinction between patentable subject matter (e.g., processes, machines, chemicals, and physical mixtures) and non-patentable concepts like ideas or laws of nature. A crucial point emphasized is the importance of not prematurely publishing your invention, as this can jeopardize your patent eligibility. It is imperative to conduct thorough research, engage with relevant authorities or transfer offices, and explore patent protection strategies. The speaker underscores that the innovator should play a central role in the initial search, as no one knows their invention better in the early stages. The presentation provides valuable resources for patent searches, including major patent databases like Google Patents, Espacenet, and others. The necessity of conducting a wide and comprehensive search is stressed to ensure novelty.

Furthermore, the speaker highlights that patent protection can be an essential driver of innovation, as demonstrated by historical examples, like the impact of the assembly line in the automobile industry. In the field of life sciences, with a particular focus on bio-based products, patents play a significant role in protecting novel production processes. However, the presentation emphasizes that each case is unique and may require consultation with a patent attorney. Notably, the presentation goes beyond patents and discusses alternative approaches such as trade secrets, where the Coca-Cola recipe serves as a prominent example. The final part of the presentation highlights the necessity of seeking partners and preparing for the market as a patent's publication deadline approaches. In the field of life sciences, especially in the development of bio-based products, this preparation is critical as most production processes are patentable.

The presentation offers a comprehensive guide for innovators in the life sciences sector to navigate the complex landscape of intellectual property management. In conclusion, the speaker makes a valuable offer to address any questions post-conference, demonstrating a commitment to furthering the understanding of intellectual property in the field of bio-based products.

Patent

- Creation of human Intellect
- Patent is a **negative right**
- **Intangible** property
- Exclusive rights given by the Govt.
- Comes with **limitations** and **exceptions**
- Both **product** and **process** patents are allowed
- Time-bound (**20 years**)
- **Territorial**

- A legal title which grants the holder **exclusive right** to **prevent others** from making, using or offering for sale, selling or importing a product that infringes his patent without his authorisation, in **countries** for which the patent was granted for a limited time (up to **20 years**).
- In return, the holder **has to disclose the invention** to the public.

Figure 28: Patent definition (detail from KEW1 presentation, Droga Mazovec, 2023)

Can plants be patented ? YES

- If the technical feasibility of the invention is not confined to a particular plant variety.

Rule 27(b) EPC

Also

- Microbiological or other technical process, or a product obtained by means of such a process other than a plant variety.

Rule 27(c) EPC

Example:

- Not allowable: A plant variety such as durum wheat type wh222 deposited at a seed depository.
- Allowable: A transgenic plant and its seeds containing an exogenous bacterial gene encoding Bt toxin.

Figure 29: Can plants be patented (detail from KEW1 presentation, Droga Mazovec, 2023)

Suggested additional reading on **patent databases**:

- [Espacenet](#)
- [Patentscope](#)
- [EP Register](#)
- [SIPO.DS](#) Database of Slovenian patents, models, trademarks
- [Google patents](#)
- [Patent LENS](#)

Suggested additional reading on **patent classifications**:

- [International patent classification– IPC](#)
- [Cooperation patent classification – CPC](#)
- [IPCCAT - Categorization Assistant in the International Patent Classification](#)

3.2.15 Biobased start-up ecosystem management – learning Food ecosystems accelerator

The fourth lecturer was Janne Saarikko, who is a multifaceted entrepreneur, a marketing strategist and visionary, a creator and builder of new businesses and innovations, and an explorer of future living. Based in Helsinki, Finland, he works, speaks, coaches and writes all around the world, always meeting interesting people and projects. Janne has extensive international experience and network from several industries. In this presentation, he discusses the journey of innovation, specifically within the context of startups, and how it differs from traditional entrepreneurship. He emphasizes that startups are expected to grow rapidly, which often necessitates external funding, and highlights the importance of understanding the various stages of growth.

Startups usually begin by identifying a problem (problem-solution fit) and subsequently developing a solution. Once these stages are validated, the product is built, leading to the crucial phase of product-market fit. Scaling and substantial funding typically come after achieving this fit. The presentation also introduces support frameworks for startups, including accelerators, incubators, and venture studios. Accelerators help entrepreneurs navigate early stages of growth, while incubators provide facilities and resources. Venture studios are more hands-on and often seek a significant share of ownership in return for rapid development and support.

Investors play a crucial role in the startup ecosystem. Business angels invest personally, while venture capitalists manage funds with specific rules and return expectations. Corporate VCs invest based on strategic alignment with their parent companies, and crowdfunding relies on individuals who expect to receive products or benefits in return for their investment. The speaker underscores the importance of matching the nature of innovation (local, regional, national, continental, or global) with the right type of investors and support. Furthermore, he points out the differences between the startup and research mindsets, emphasizing the need for adaptability and a willingness to embrace uncertainty in the startup world.

The presentation concludes by highlighting that the startup ecosystem is diverse and complex, with specific requirements often related to highly specialized fields. Collaboration and seeking the right help within these ecosystems can greatly aid innovators in their journey.

Suggested further reading on enabling services for startups in food sector (business accelerators, start-up incubators, venture capital, business angels):

[Incubator List](#)

[EBAN](#)

[FI Network](#)

Suggested further reading on the leading European initiatives on new product development in food systems and circular (bio)economy:

[EIT Food](#)

[EIT Climate KIC](#)

Circular Economy and Value Chains Transformation

The last speaker of the third day was Bart Stegeman, who is a multi-talented people manager with a strong drive for analytic processes and workflows. Currently, he is the Slovenian Orchestrator - Circular Economy and Value Chains Transformation at EIT Climate KIC. He is responsible to bring systems innovation for the Slovenian transition to a circular, regenerative and low-carbon economy. With an extensive work experience in complex supply chains and digitalisation, he is connecting the needs from the Slovene environment with the current regional /European challenges. In his presentation he talks about systemic exploration of the transition to a circular and regenerative country, Slovenia has aimed for a sustainable and circular future. Despite efforts in Europe, the transition has faced challenges. The crux of the issue lies in the lack of a dynamic approach for implementation, given that natural resources are finite.

Transitioning from the current system to a circular economy is not a leap from one step to another. Instead, it necessitates a gradual, step-by-step transformation at local, national, and regional levels in Europe. The process is a work in progress, with promising developments emerging. To tackle this challenge, the focus shifts to an in-depth methodology that delves into the reasons behind certain events. The "iceberg model" is introduced, providing insights into why systems may resist transitioning to a sustainable future. Drawing from personal experience, this model proves instrumental in understanding why certain systems persist.

The transition from a systemic approach to implementation is evident in Slovenia's Deep Demonstration Project. This initiative not only promotes sustainability but also clarity in the goals set. Circularity is recognized as a means to secure a sustainable future, emphasizing the efficient use of resources, bio-based materials, and value chains, particularly in the built environment and food sectors. Highlighting the importance of the circular economy, the presentation underscores the "Refuse, Rethink, and Reduce" principles before reaching the recycling stage. Emphasis is placed on the significance of efficient product design, which can significantly impact the environment.

Efforts also focus on the entrepreneurship pillar, where the Climate Impact Forecast service assists entrepreneurs and researchers in assessing the climate impact of their products and services. The goal is to attract investors and public funding through a third-party validated methodology, providing a sturdy foundation for developing products that genuinely contribute to climate change mitigation. This presentation showcases the transition from a systemic view of sustainability to a concrete implementation, providing a roadmap for regions seeking to make a substantial environmental impact. For those seeking further information, additional data and insights are available.

3.3 Workshop 2: Aquatic systems

Table 5 presents summarized information of the KEW on Aquatic systems that was held from 28th to 30th November 2023, with active links to relevant workshop materials on BioRural Toolkit and YT channel @BioRural.

Table 5: Agenda of the Knowledge exchange workshop for Aquatic systems

Day 1 - Generic principles	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Overview presentation of aquacultures and bioeconomy / circular economy	Koushik Roy (Uni. South Bohemia, FROV, Czechia)	Link to .pdf	Video
Status and perspective of algal technologies	Robert Reinhardt (Algen, Slovenia)	Link to .pdf	Video
IMTA , a circulatory approach to aquaculture	Erik Malta (CTAQUA, Spain)	Link to .pdf	Video
Microalgae related processes for nutrients recovery from wastes	Gabriel Acien (Uni. Almeria, Spain)	Link to .pdf	Video
Microalgae-based biogas upgrading : a sustainability driven technology	Raul Muñoz (Uni. Valladolid, Spain)	Link to .pdf	Video
Algae market and value chains	Vitor Veldeho (European Algae Biomass Association)	Link to .pdf	Video
Day 2 - Theme-specific aspects	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
High sustainability aquafarming	Irena Fonda (Fonda aquaculture, Slovenia)	Link to .pdf	Video
Sustainable local aquaculture by PUSTELNIA	Anna Pać (Pustelnia, Poland)	Link to .pdf	Video
Alternative protein sources obtainable as partial replacement of dietary ingredients in fish feed: a case study on sea bream	Katia Parati (Istituto Spallanzani, Italy)	/	/
Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant - biorefinery valorisation of aquaculture biomass	Tanja Meyer (BioBase Europe Pilot Plant, BEL)	Link to .pdf	Video
Towards more sustainable aquaculture: alternative fish feed based on BSFL and microalgae	Siggi Penno-Winters (Arava, Israel)	/	/
Microalgae as part of the circular economy	Carole Llewellyn (Swansea University, UK)	Link to .pdf	Video
Locality : "Nature-positive algae-based food, agriculture, aquaculture and textile products made in North and Baltic Sea ecosystems"	Margarida Costa (Niva, Norway)	Link to .pdf	Video
Innovative hybrid INTensive – EXTensive resource recovery from wastewater	Ivan Blanco (Aqualia, Spain)	Link to .pdf	Video
Day 3 - Cross-cutting issues	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Opportunities for aquacultures in circular (bio)economy	Ana Gavrilović (Uni. Zagreb, Croatia)	Link to .pdf	Video
Sustainable agriculture : integration of algae in agricultural biomethane plants to produce bio-stimulants	Valeria Mezzanote (Uni. Milano-Bicocca, Italy)	Link to .pdf	Video
EU regulation and standardisation for the algal sector	Silvio Mangini (Archimede, Italy)	Link to .pdf	Video
Innovation space BioBall - Regional material use of biogenic by-products & waste streams	Jochen Michels (BioBall, Germany)	Link to .pdf	Video
Value Chain Generator for circular bioeconomy	Jon Goriup Dermastia (VCG.ai, Germany)	Link to .pdf	Video
Clusters role in circular economy and Bioeconomy hubs (CEE2ACT)	Mateja Dermastia (Anteja ECG, Slovenia)	Link to .pdf	Video

3.3.1 Overview presentation of aquacultures and bioeconomy / circular economy

In this insightful presentation, Koushik Roy delves into the transformative practices reshaping aquaculture in Central Europe, with a particular focus on the innovative use of fishponds. Highlighting success stories from the Czech Republic, Roy explains how these ponds, traditionally known for their resilience and circular nature, are now at the forefront of sustainable aquaculture and bioeconomy. Central European fishponds are being revolutionized through a bioeconomic approach that emphasizes the use of circular feeds and efficient resource utilization. The presentation outlines the critical understanding of pond dynamics, especially the seasonal changes in nutrient availability and fish feeding patterns. He introduces a novel feeding concept where the ponds are fed not just to nourish the fish but to enhance the entire ecosystem. This involves a strategic addition of carbohydrates, fibers, proteins, and energy at different times of the season to optimize the natural food cycle and promote a balanced growth of aquatic life.

The presentation details the development and testing of specific feed formulations composed of locally sourced, circular ingredients. These feeds are designed to complement the natural diet of fish, ensuring better protein utilization and a reduced ecological footprint. The presentation emphasizes the importance of creating feeds that are not only nutritionally complete but also environmentally sustainable, with careful consideration of factors like phosphorus content to avoid ecosystem disruption. Results from trials demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach, showing significant improvements in fish yield and nutrient efficiency. The approach also aligns with the broader goals of bioeconomy, as it promotes the reduction of waste, enhances nutrient recycling, and contributes to a more sustainable food production system.

Koushik Roy concludes the presentation by stressing the potential of this approach to transform aquaculture practices in Central Europe and beyond. He extends an invitation for collaboration and knowledge exchange to further advance the field of sustainable aquaculture and bioeconomy. Listeners are encouraged to access additional resources and detailed information through provided QR codes and to engage with the ongoing projects and networks that are pioneering these innovative practices in the Czech Republic and other regions.

Design of pond feeds

- Low protein feed <25-28% designed on digestible amino acids basis (DIAAS criteria).
- Balance lysine and methionine quality to complement zooplankton and zoobenthos lysine-methionine.
- Add starch and lipid to supply non-protein energy to fish.
- Add plant fibers to supply carbon (energy) to pond food web.
- While adding fibers make sure NDF:ADF ratio is >2:1 (carp can ferment those), and Starch content >20-30%
- Limit P content to <0.9% to respect EU-WFD and stay below zooplankton-zoobenthos P content (1% DM)

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2023.739906>

Kuebutornye, F.K.A., Tellbüscher, A.A., Dvorak, P., Roy, K., Mraz, J. 2024. Valorising local agri-food by-products for circular pond feeds in Central European fishponds: evaluation of protein, fillers, and energy feed resources for ponds. *Animal Feed Science and Technology* (under review).

Figure 30: Design of pond feeds (detail from KEW2 presentation, Roy, 2023)

Designed and lab-validated pond feeds

Figure 31: Designed and lab-validated pond feeds (detail from KEW2 presentation, Roy, 2023)

Suggested further reading:

- [The concept of balanced fish nutrition in temperate European fishponds to tackle eutrophication](#)
- [End-of-season supplementary feeding in European carp ponds with appropriate plant protein and carbohydrate combinations to ecologically boost productivity: Lupine, rapeseed and, triticale](#)
- [Nutrient footprint versus EPA + DHA security in land-locked regions—more of local pond farmed, imported marine fish or fish oil capsules?](#)
- [Circular and sustainable fish nutrition](#)

3.3.2 Status and perspective of algal technologies

The presentation provides an extensive exploration of algal technologies, delving into the potential, challenges, and pragmatic outlook of large-scale algal cultivation. It commences with an examination of the diversity within the algal species, encompassing both eukaryotic and prokaryotic types, including microalgae and macroalgae, and their broad applications ranging from biofuels to high-protein food sources. The presentation underscores the notable protein content and environmental sustainability of algae as an alternative to animal protein. A substantial segment of the presentation is devoted to the transition from lab-scale algal growth to pilot and extensive production. It underlines the marked discrepancies between controlled lab environments and real-world conditions.

Principal challenges in large-scale cultivation involve light penetration, thermal management, purity of culture media, oxygen management, predator deterrence, and the creation of a stable and sanitized environment for algae growth. One of the pivotal challenges discussed pertains to harvesting, which entails moving vast volumes of water to collect a modest mass of algae. The presentation describes diverse techniques like sedimentation, flotation, and filtration, each necessitating a customized approach contingent on the algal species being cultivated. Another notable challenge is the dewatering process, pivotal for generating consumable algae products. This process must be efficient and rapid to maintain the quality of the algal biomass. The presentation also acknowledges the economic aspect, noting that while high-quality algal biomass can be produced, its cost remains significantly elevated compared to traditional commodity crops, partly due to the absence of subsidies for algal production.

While the presentation recognizes the immense potential of algae across various sectors, it offers a realistic perspective on the challenges and economic factors that need to be addressed in large-scale algal cultivation. It illuminates the necessity for ongoing innovation and development in the domain to render algal technologies a feasible and sustainable choice for the future.

Figure 32: What are Algae (detail from KEW2 presentation, Reinhardt, 2023)

Figure 33: Algal products (detail from KEW2 presentation, Reinhardt, 2023)

3.3.3 IMTA, a circulatory approach to aquaculture

The presentation offers an insightful exploration of Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA), positioning it as a pivotal solution to the escalating global food demand in the face of resource constraints. It sheds light on the environmental and economic challenges plaguing conventional aquaculture and fisheries, introducing IMTA as a groundbreaking approach that harmonizes different trophic levels (carnivores, herbivores, primary producers, etc.) within the production cycle.

Key Points: 1. **Global Food Challenge:** The presentation highlights the urgency of developing sustainable food production systems against the backdrop of a rapidly growing global population and diminishing natural resources. It points out the insufficiency of traditional agriculture and overexploited fisheries in meeting the future food requirements.

2. **IMTA as a Solution:** IMTA is portrayed as a sustainable method that optimizes resource utilization by incorporating diverse species across various trophic levels. This system ensures the transformation of waste products from one species into valuable inputs (feed or nutrients) for another, thus enhancing resource efficiency and minimizing environmental footprints.

3. **Nutrient Dynamics in Aquaculture:** The inefficiencies in nutrient usage within conventional aquaculture, where a substantial portion of feed nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus) is lost as waste, are discussed. IMTA addresses this issue by facilitating the recycling and utilization of these nutrients by other species within the ecosystem.

4. **Circularity in IMTA:** The concept of circularity in IMTA is centered on nutrient recycling within the production cycle. While true circularity encompasses the entire value chain, encompassing feed production and processing, IMTA primarily focuses on the production phase. Different methodologies for assessing nutrient use efficiency in IMTA systems are introduced, ranging from straightforward mass balance models to intricate flux models and tracer techniques.

5. **Commercial Uptake and Challenges:** Despite its potential, the commercial implementation of IMTA faces several hurdles, including the necessity for vertical integration among businesses specializing in different species and the development of spatial planning strategies to ensure nutrient recycling without triggering environmental concerns, such as eutrophication.

6. **Diverse Applications and Examples:** Various instances of IMTA systems are presented, from open sea configurations involving fish, shellfish, and seaweed to land-based setups integrating fish with algae or plants. The adaptability of IMTA systems to different environments and scales is underscored.

7. **Educational Resources:** The availability of an online course on IMTA, developed under the INTEGRATE project and accessible through their YouTube channel, is mentioned. This course aims to spread knowledge and encourage the adoption of IMTA practices.

The presentation advocates for the adoption of Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture as a means to achieve sustainable and circular aquaculture practices, addressing environmental concerns and the imperative for heightened food production. It underscores the importance of collaboration, innovation, and education as crucial elements in propelling IMTA forward and sustainably meeting the global food demands of the future.

IMTA, a circulatory approach to aquaculture

Problem definition

Increase in world population: 9 billion people by 2050 (UN)

Challenge: provide protein (food) for this population in a world that is already facing resource limitations (water, space, fertilizer, etc.) under pressure of climate change

Unlikely that agriculture can meet the demand

Global fisheries landings have fallen drastically since the mid-1980s, mainly due to overexploitation of fish stocks

World is looking towards aquaculture (in particular marine aquaculture) as potential solution: **blue revolution**

Figure 34: IMTA, Problem definition (detail from KEW2 presentation, Malta, 2023)

IMTA, a circulatory approach to aquaculture

Application of circularity to IMTA systems, generally more limited to circularity (RECYCLING) of nutrients during production part

Figure 35: IMTA, application of circularity (detail from KEW2 presentation, Malta, 2023)

3.3.4 Microalgae related processes for nutrients recovery from wastes

The presentation delves into the promising prospects of microalgae-based processes for nutrient recovery from diverse waste streams and the subsequent production of biomass. It highlights the pivotal role these processes play in addressing environmental issues and fostering sustainability.

Key Points: 1. **Diverse Waste Streams:** The presentation emphasizes the variety of effluents, including wastewater and agricultural runoff, rich in organic matter, nitrogen, phosphorus, and total solids. The primary challenge involves tailoring the composition of these effluents to align with the nutritional demands of microalgae cultivation, especially concerning nitrogen and phosphorus levels.

2. **Consortium of Microalgae and Bacteria:** The effluent treatment process is a synergistic effort between microalgae and bacteria. This collaboration is instrumental in driving crucial functions like carbon fixation, oxygen production, denitrification, and nitrification, which are integral to effective nutrient recovery.

3. **Large-scale Operation and Resilience:** Examples of large-scale continuous reactors functioning under real-life conditions are showcased, illustrating the robustness of these systems against environmental fluctuations. These reactors are proficient in processing significant volumes of wastewater daily, generating purified water and biomass.

4. **Commercial Viability and Sustainability:** The presentation points out the successful commercial operations of facilities in Spain, where reactors efficiently treat wastewater. It underscores the technology's practicality and reliability, noting substantial energy savings in comparison to conventional wastewater treatment methods and the generation of commercially valuable biomass.

5. **Innovative Approaches for Nutrient Recovery:** Innovative techniques for nutrient recovery from agricultural runoff are introduced, stressing the importance of proximity to nutrient sources. These systems hold the potential to yield biofertilizers, biostimulants, and other high-value products.

6. **Validation of Water Quality for Irrigation:** Collaborative efforts with agricultural faculties have confirmed the suitability of water treated through these processes for irrigation purposes. Such validation is evidenced by enhanced crop productivity and health.

7. **Final Thoughts:** The presentation concludes by reaffirming the commercial readiness of microalgae-based technologies. It accentuates their versatility in treating various effluents, fostering sustainability, and making significant contributions to the bioeconomy.

The presentation effectively showcases the potential of microalgae processes as a sustainable avenue for nutrient recovery and biomass production, underscoring its critical role in advancing environmental sustainability and the circular economy within the broader context of bioeconomy.

Figure 36: Microalgae treatment of wastewater (detail from KEW2 presentation, Acien, 2023)

Figure 37: First industrial demonstration (detail from KEW2 presentation, Acien, 2023)

3.3.5 Microalgae-based biogas upgrading: a sustainability-driven technology

The presentation delves into the potential of microalgae-bacteria processes in purifying biogas and transforming it into biomethane, highlighting the significant global and particularly European interest in biogas production. It underscores the need for innovative and environmentally friendly technologies, especially for small to medium-scale plants.

Key Points: 1. Biogas Production Trends: The presentation provides an overview of the global and European biogas production landscape, noting the increase in biogas plants and the volume of biomethane produced. It references advancements in purification technologies, including membrane separation and pressure swing adsorption.

2. Technology for Biogas Purification: The technology introduced involves microalgae-bacteria processes where biogas, primarily composed of methane and carbon dioxide, is fed into a photobioreactor. The carbon dioxide is fixed by microalgae, resulting in oxygen production, which bacteria utilize to oxidize hydrogen sulfide into elemental sulfur. This process yields purified biomethane and algae biomass, which may be used as bioenergy feedstock or biofertilizer.

3. Operational Parameters and Scalability: Key operational parameters like the liquid-to-gas ratio and pH are discussed. The presentation describes the technology’s scalability from laboratory scale to semi-industrial scale, highlighting its efficiency in nutrient recovery and robustness.

4. Environmental and Economic Benefits: It points out the environmental advantages, such as lower energy consumption and reduced greenhouse gas emissions compared to conventional methods. The potential economic benefits due to lower operational costs are also highlighted.

5. Future Perspectives: The presentation concludes by focusing on the promising future of microalgae-bacteria processes in biogas purification, suggesting that with further refinement, this technology can offer a sustainable and economically viable solution for biogas purification across various scales.

The presentation provides insight into the innovative use of microalgae-bacteria processes for biogas purification, showcasing the technology’s environmental benefits and promising economic prospects, marking a significant stride towards sustainable and efficient energy production.

Figure 38: The biogas upgrading market (detail from KEW2 presentation, EBA, 2022)

PROCESS CONTROL

Figure 39: Process control of the Photosynthetic biogas upgrading (detail from KEW2 presentation, Munoz, 2023)

3.3.6 Algae market and value chains

The presentation offers an insightful overview of algae biomass and its diverse value chains, focusing on the complexity and vast potential of algae, including both microalgae and macroalgae (seaweeds). It explores their various applications across multiple industries.

Key Points: 1. Defining Algae: The broad categorization of algae, encompassing both microalgae and macroalgae, is clarified. The presentation highlights the significant diversity within these groups and advises against generalizing their applications or benefits due to their varied characteristics.

2. Industry Status: An overview of the algae industry is provided, illustrating the scale of biomass production globally. It's noted that despite the existence of thousands of algae species, only a few are cultivated on a large scale.

3. Product Types: Three main product types derived from algae are outlined: paste (which may be wet or frozen), dried biomass, and extracts. Each product type has distinct processing requirements and market applications.

4. Market Applications: The potential applications of algae products are vast, spanning across eight broad categories, including food, animal feed, cosmetics, biofertilizers, bioenergy, pollution control, bioplastics, and pharmaceuticals.

5. Value Chain Analysis: The concept of value chains in the algae industry is explained, emphasizing the increase in product value from primary production to end-user applications. The distinction is made between the product value chain (from production to processing) and the business value chain (from market positioning to final application).

6. Importance of Value Chain Positioning: The significance of positioning in the value chain is underlined. Products increase in value as they move from the production stage to the final application, highlighting the importance of understanding and navigating through these stages effectively.

The presentation brings to light the complexities and vast potential of the algae industry, stressing the importance of recognizing the diversity within algae species and understanding the value chain dynamics to fully harness the potential of algae biomass in various sectors.

Figure 40: Macro vs Micro Algae (detail from KEW2 presentation, Wijffels, 2019)

Applications

www.eaba-association.org

Figure 41: Applications of algal technologies (detail from KEW2 presentation, Vieira, 2023)

3.3.7 High sustainability aquafarming

The presentation delivers an in-depth overview of sustainable aquaculture, drawing from firsthand experience in running a family fish farm. It emphasizes the importance of sustainability in the seafood industry and shares the innovative approaches adopted by the farm.

Key Points: 1. Family Legacy in Aquaculture: The legacy of the family in aquaculture is introduced, including the establishment of their brand, which emphasizes quality and sustainability. This brand has received significant media attention and recognition, becoming a well-respected name in the industry.

2. Key Trends in Aquaculture: The presentation highlights critical aspects of sustainable aquaculture, including the need to reduce antibiotic usage, address environmental degradation, manage nutrient feeds more effectively, and minimize the impact on wild gene pools.

3. Evolution of Aquaculture Systems: The evolution of aquaculture systems is discussed, transitioning from traditional wooden cages to modern steel cages, and shifting towards more technologically advanced and sustainable practices, including offshore farming and improved feed systems.

4. Importance of Molluscs: The significant role of molluscs, particularly mussels, in sustainable aquaculture is pointed out. Mussels do not require feed or fertilizers and have minimal environmental impact, making them an ideal choice for sustainable farming.

5. Aquaculture and Biodiversity: The farm focuses on creating an environment that not only farms fish but also enhances biodiversity. Their underwater structures serve as habitats for various marine species, demonstrating a commitment to environmental stewardship.

6. Future Endeavors in Aquaculture: The presentation outlines future plans, including developing pilot systems for researching and farming species not yet known for aquaculture. The aim is to create self-sustaining ecosystems that contribute positively to biodiversity and offer new aquaculture opportunities.

7. Educational Initiatives for Sustainability: The importance of education in promoting sustainability is recognized, mentioning the establishment of educational initiatives. These aim to involve the public and the younger generation in understanding and supporting sustainable aquaculture practices.

The presentation illuminates the principles of sustainable aquaculture and the innovative approaches adopted by the family farm to promote environmental stewardship, biodiversity, and quality seafood production. The initiatives and future plans discussed underscore the importance of sustainability in the aquaculture industry.

Figure 42: Trends in aquaculture (detail from KEW2 presentation, Fonda, 2023)

3.3.8 Sustainable local aquaculture by PUSTELNIA

The presentation offers insights into sustainable local agriculture, focusing on the experience with the Pustelnia fish farm, which specializes in carp and trout farming. It underscores the integral role of agriculture in the local ecosystem and the importance of sustainable practices. Key Points: 1. Pustelnia Fish Farm Overview: The farm is introduced as deeply rooted in the local area, with a history dating back to the 19th century. It is dedicated to carp and trout farming, complementing natural fish production with grain sourced from local farmers, highlighting the farm’s commitment to sustainability and community support.

2. Ecosystem-Based Approach to Farming: The farm’s operations are intricately linked with the local ecosystem, providing a habitat for a diverse range of animals and plants that thrive in water environments. The maintenance of these water bodies for fish farming plays a crucial role in supporting local biodiversity.

3. Local Market Integration: Differing from many fish farms that supply large processing plants, this farm focuses on the local market, delivering fresh fish directly to nearby restaurants and shops. The farm also operates its own shop and restaurant, prioritizing the freshness and quality of their fish.

4. Adaptation and Innovation during COVID-19: In response to the pandemic, the farm introduced mobile shops to ensure continuous delivery of fresh fish to local communities, thereby overcoming the challenges posed by COVID-19 and maintaining a steady supply of diverse fish products.

5. Future Potential and Vision: There is seen potential in offering innovative, fresh, and locally farmed fish products to the market. While the farm does not intend to intensify production, there are opportunities to add value through innovative products and serve appealing and healthy fish dishes in their restaurant and other outlets.

In conclusion, the presentation highlights the sustainable practices of the Pustelnia fish farm, showcasing its dedication to the local ecosystem and community. With an approach that is harmoniously integrated with nature and focused on delivering fresh, high-quality products, the farm exemplifies sustainable local agriculture.

PUSTELNIA –short value chain

Our market:

- HoReCa (restaurants, gastro) within range of approx. 100km
- own fish shop 1km away from fish processing plant and fish farm
- 3 mobile shops – FishTrucks
- PUSTELNIA restaurant 1km away from fish processing plant and fish farm

Figure 43: Pustelnia's short value chain (detail from KEW2 presentation, Pyć, 2023)

3.3.9 Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant - biorefinery valorisation of aquaculture biomass

The presentation revolves around the biorefinery concept, with a particular focus on the utilization of aquatic biomass. It draws parallels between traditional oil refineries and biorefineries, highlighting the sustainable approach of using biomass as feedstock. Key Points: 1. Biorefinery Concept: Similar to traditional refineries, biorefineries process various forms of biomass instead of oil or fossil-based materials. This includes diverse sources of biomass, particularly underutilized aquatic biomass like algae.

2. Industrial Biotechnology (White Biotechnology): This field involves leveraging microorganisms or their components (such as bacteria, yeast, fungi) to produce industrial products, chemicals, materials, and fuels in a more sustainable manner than conventional chemical processes.

3. BBEPP – An Open Access Pilot Facility: The Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant (BBEPP) is presented as an independent open access pilot facility focusing on process development, scale-up, and custom manufacturing of bio-based products and processes. BBEPP helps bridge the lab-scale research to industrial production gap, known as the ‘valley of death’, by providing shared infrastructure to minimize risks and costs associated with scale-up.

4. Project CircAlgae: The presentation introduces the CircAlgae project, aiming to valorize industrial waste streams into high-value products and promote sustainable biorefineries in Europe. The project specifically targets underutilized biomass from aquatic sources to derive valuable ingredients for the food, feed, and cosmetics industries.

5. Technologies and Services: A range of technologies and services provided by BBEPP is showcased, including biocatalysis, fermentation, green chemistry, and more. The facility’s ability to convert various feedstocks, including aquatic biomass, into high-value products is emphasized.

6. Conclusion and Outreach: The presentation concludes by highlighting the facility’s contributions and inviting the audience to explore their YouTube channel for educational content about their work in biorefinery. In summary, the presentation sheds light on the potential of biorefineries to convert biomass, especially from aquatic sources, into a wide array of sustainable and high-value products. Facilities like BBEPP are instrumental in scaling up biotechnological innovations, fostering a more sustainable and bio-based economy.

Figure 44: Bio-based products based on aquatic biomass (detail from KEW2 presentation, Meyer, 2023)

Figure 45: Circalgae application (detail from KEW2 presentation, Meyer, 2023)

Video:

- [A swirling and sensational virtual visit of the Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant](#)
- [Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant: A one-stop-shop](#)

3.3.10 Microalgae as part of the circular economy

The presentation centers on the ALG-AD Project, a collaborative initiative spanning the UK, France, and Belgium, financially backed by EU Interreg North-West Europe. The project’s core objective was to employ digestate from anaerobic digesters as a medium to cultivate microalgae, opening up fresh market possibilities while tackling the issue of surplus digestate leading to pollution. Key Points: 1. Circular Economy Model: The initiative aligns with a circular economy model by utilizing agricultural waste in anaerobic digestion processes, generating digestate enriched with nitrogen and phosphorus. This by-product then serves as a nutrient source for cultivating microalgae, which can subsequently be transformed into sustainable animal feed or other high-value commodities.

2. Project Objectives: The endeavor sought to carve out new market niches by converting liquid digestate into valuable biomass. Emphasis was placed on producing sustainable feed for animals and fish and extracting valuable compounds from microalgae.

3. Pilot Facilities: The project established three pilot facilities across the UK, France, and Belgium. Each site experimented with different species of microalgae and embraced varied cultivation techniques, including autotrophic and mixotrophic methods.

4. Microalgae Analysis and Trials: A comprehensive analysis of microalgae cultivated under varied conditions was undertaken, examining differences in protein and lipid compositions. The project incorporated trials for piglet and fish feed, assessing the effects of microalgae-enriched feed on animal health and well-being.

5. Decision Support Tools: The initiative developed decision-making tools to guide interested stakeholders in adopting this technology. This included mapping out anaerobic digestion plants and formulating best practice protocols for microalgae cultivation and application.

6. Outcomes and Resources: The project yielded an array of publications, reports, and guidelines advocating best practices. These materials are accessible on the project’s website, serving as a treasure trove of information for the broader community invested in sustainable methodologies involving microalgae.

In essence, the presentation underscores the ALG-AD project’s pioneering strategy in utilizing anaerobic digestate for microalgae cultivation. This approach not only contributes to the circular economy but also paves the way for novel market opportunities in the realm of sustainable animal and fish feed. Moreover, the project addresses ecological concerns while offering tangible tools and directives for future ventures in this domain.

Figure 46: Application of algal technologies in circular value chain – an example (detail from KEW2 presentation, Llewellyn, 2023)

WP-Cap: Fatty acid analysis of fish fed on algae

Advantage of including microalgal ingredients grown on digestate in the diet of Nile Tilapia, with **added value to the aquaculture sector**.

Figure 47: Fatty acid analysis of fish fed on algae (detail from KEW2 presentation, Llewellyn, 2023)

3.3.11 Locality: "Nature-positive algae-based food, agriculture, aquaculture and textile products made in North and Baltic Sea ecosystems"

The presentation delves into the Locality project, a forward-thinking initiative focusing on establishing circular and sustainable value chains. The project harnesses waste by-products from various industries to cultivate microalgae, concentrating on regions where aquaculture, agriculture, and textiles are vital economic sectors. The primary aim is to forge algae-based products tailored for these markets while safeguarding and rejuvenating aquatic ecosystems. Key Points: 1. Project Objectives: The Locality project is committed to fostering collaborative efforts among industries for effective waste management, encouraging the joint creation of new algae-based products, and maintaining minimal emissions throughout the entire value chain.

2. Algae Cultivation: At the heart of the project is the cultivation of microalgae utilizing waste by-products from industries linked to aquaculture, agriculture, and textiles. The generated algae biomass is earmarked for the creation of market-ready products.

3. Market Penetration: The project’s goal is to introduce ground-breaking algae-based products into the textile, agriculture (bio-stimulants and fertilizers), and food sectors. This encompasses crafting alternatives for protein sources like egg substitutes, fish and meat alternatives, and nutritional supplements for the food industry.

4. Consortium Composition: The project is steered by a consortium consisting of 28 diverse partners, spanning industry stakeholders, research entities, and business collaborators. The consortium’s focus lies in research, development, and the commercial aspects, guaranteeing the successful market launch of the developed products.

5. Circular Economy Model: The project champions a circular economy model by converting waste from industries into valuable resources, thereby circumventing additional waste treatment costs. By integrating algae cultivation, the project aims not only to treat wastewater but also to valorise it into novel products.

6. Progress Update: Currently, the project is in the phase of wastewater analysis and algae biomass production. The findings from the upcoming months are set to lay the groundwork for product development in the subsequent phase.

The presentation spotlights the Locality project’s dedication to promoting sustainable and circular value chains in pivotal industries like aquaculture, agriculture, and textiles. Through leveraging waste streams for microalgae cultivation and pioneering algae-based products, the project is making significant strides towards environmental sustainability and unlocking new market potentials.

Figure 48: Locality - context (detail from KEW2 presentation, Costa, 2023)

LOCALITY - concept

Figure 49: Locality - concept (detail from KEW2 presentation, Costa, 2023)

3.3.12 Innovative hybrid INTensive – EXTensive resource recovery from wastewater in small communities

The speaker is a leading international water service provider, presents their cutting-edge approach to wastewater treatment, concentrating on solutions tailored for small communities. He emphasizes the company’s dedication to research in biomass harvesting and algae-based solutions, particularly in wastewater treatment contexts. Key Points: 1. Company Profile: Aqualia stands out in the water service sector, catering to about 44 million people globally and earning the title of Water Company of the Year 2023. Despite its large scale, Aqualia commits to delivering wastewater treatment solutions suitable for small communities and collaborates closely with small and medium-sized enterprises.

2. INTEXT Platform Introduction: Near Madrid, Aqualia operates the Life INTEXT platform, designed to bridge the divide between energy-intensive technologies and costly methods requiring substantial surface areas. Positioned within a wastewater treatment facility, the platform exhibits a spectrum of technologies, including hybrid systems for wastewater treatment and biomass harvesting.

3. Collaborative Efforts: The project thrives on a consortium model, incorporating partners, research institutions, and small to medium enterprises, all joining forces to pioneer algae-based solutions for wastewater treatment.

4. Diverse Technological Offerings: The INTEXT platform showcases up to 16 distinct technologies, offering an expansive perspective on treatment options. This comprehensive platform acts as a valuable guide for municipalities to comprehend the processes and contemplate their implementation at the local level.

5. Technological Highlights: The presentation underscores various innovative technologies such as high-rate algae ponds, floating wetlands, and hybrid setups that merge algae ponds with vertical flow wetlands for fine-tuning. The platform also benchmarks these against more traditional systems to facilitate comparison and performance assessment.

6. Invitation for Exploration: Ivan Blanco welcomes interested parties to visit the facility and directly engage with the diverse treatment systems. He underscores the opportunity to benchmark efficiencies, grasp operational and maintenance demands, and acquire deeper insights into a spectrum of wastewater treatment solutions.

Ivan Blanco’s presentation underlines Aqualia’s commitment to pioneering wastewater treatment solutions, with a particular focus on small communities. Through the INTEXT platform, the company is at the forefront of exploring and deploying various technologies, enhancing understanding of wastewater treatment methodologies, and nurturing collaborative efforts in the domain.

Figure 50: LIFE INTEXT Project (detail from KEW2 presentation, Blanco, 2023)

Life INTEXT
Footprint vs Energy consumption

Figure 51: Footprint vs Energy consumption (detail from KEW2 presentation, Blanco, 2023)

3.3.13 Opportunities for aquaculture in circular (bio)economy

The presentation delves into the integration of aquaculture within the European Union’s circular economy and bioeconomy strategies. It is meticulously structured around EU policies and their influence on funding opportunities for sustainable aquaculture practices. Key Points: 1. EU Missions and Policies: The presentation introduces five EU missions dedicated to providing tangible solutions by 2030, encompassing missions centered on restoring oceans and waters, adapting to climate change, and realizing a climate-neutral and smart city. The significance of these missions in molding project calls and funding opportunities is emphasized.

2. Aquaculture’s Significance: The rapid expansion of aquaculture, recognized as the fastest-growing food production sector, is highlighted. The challenges accompanying this growth, such as water and land limitations, environmental impacts, and the necessity for technological innovations in farming, are underscored.

3. Sustainable Aquaculture Practices: The presentation underscores the criticality of sustainable practices in aquaculture, discussing various production methods, including traditional technologies, recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS), and aquaponics, which synergize fish farming with plant cultivation.

4. Aquaculture in the Circular Economy: Details on how aquaculture waste can be repurposed in a circular economy are provided, showcasing the conversion of waste into valuable by-products, such as biogas or compost. The potential for harnessing aquaculture wastewater for algae cultivation, further enhancing sustainability, is also suggested.

5. EU Funding Opportunities: Resources and links are furnished, guiding participants to explore EU funding avenues related to aquaculture and the circular economy. The formation of partnerships and consortia to capitalize on these opportunities is encouraged.

6. Engagement with EU Missions: Insights on how stakeholders can actively participate in EU missions, endorse mission charters, and partake in cross-basin projects to tackle challenges associated with oceans, waters, and climate change are shared.

The presentation maps out the synergy of aquaculture with the EU’s circular economy and bioeconomy strategies. It accentuates the sector’s growth, its sustainability challenges, and prospective remedies, alongside offering valuable resources for stakeholders keen on accessing EU funding and support for sustainable aquaculture initiatives.

Figure 52: State of world aquaculture and fisheries in 2020 (detail from KEW2 presentation, Gavrilović, 2023)

Sustainable Aquaculture

- Sustainable aquaculture is a dynamic concept and the sustainability of an aquaculture system varies with species, location, social norms and the state of knowledge and technology.
- The application of new aquaculture technologies and the introduction of technologies known in other industries **are one of the ways** for developing ecologically, socially, financially and energetically sustainable aquaculture production.

Figure 53: Sustainable aquaculture (detail from KEW2 presentation, Gavrilović, 2023)

Suggested additional reading:

- [EU Missions in Horizon Europe](#)
- [EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change](#)
- [EU Mission: Cancer](#)
- [EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters](#)
- [EU Mission: Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities](#)
- [EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe](#)
- [European Commission: Annual work programme for grants and procurement](#)
- [European Commission: LIFE - Calls for proposals 2023](#)

3.3.14 Sustainable agriculture: integration of algae in agricultural biomethane plants to produce bio-stimulants

The presentation focuses on the integration of microalgae into sustainable agricultural practices, emphasizing the potential of these organisms in transforming waste into valuable resources and contributing to the circular and bioeconomy. It addresses the economic and environmental challenges of microalgae cultivation, particularly in regions with less optimal weather conditions for growth. Key Points: 1. Characteristics of Microalgae: Microalgae are versatile organisms capable of operating autotrophically, mixotrophically, or heterotrophically. They play a crucial role in nutrient removal and can produce valuable molecules for a range of industries.

2. Economic Sustainability of Cultivation: Cultivating microalgae can be economically challenging, especially in areas with unfavorable weather. However, using waste as a growth medium, optimizing biomass productivity, and focusing on high-value end products can enhance the cost-effectiveness of cultivation.

3. Integration in Agriculture: The presentation outlines how microalgae can be integrated into agriculture by utilizing agri-food byproducts and the liquid fraction of digestate as nutrient-rich substrates for their growth.

4. Project Overview: The presentation describes a project aimed at integrating microalgae cultivation in agricultural setups. The project’s strategy involves producing biogas and biomethane from agri-food waste and utilizing the resulting liquid digestate for cultivating microalgae. The ultimate goal is to produce biofertilizers and foster a circular economy model.

5. Cultivation Approach: The approach includes gradual acclimation of algae to the digestate, cultivation in photobioreactors under controlled conditions, and use of raceway ponds. Maintaining the culture’s purity is emphasized to ensure consistent quality for biofertilizer production.

6. Encouraging Results: Initial results demonstrate promising growth rates and nutrient removal efficiencies. The project successfully cultivates microalgae using digestate, and ongoing work aims to test the bioactivity of the produced biomass.

The presentation highlights the potential of microalgae in sustainable agriculture by utilizing waste streams as a valuable resource. The described project serves as an example of how microalgae can be integrated into agricultural practices, promoting principles of a circular economy, and developing valuable products like biofertilizers.

Figure 54: Integration of algal technologies in biomethane plants - biostimulants I. (detail from KEW2 presentation, Mezzanotte, 2023)

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INTEGRATION OF ALGAE IN AGRICULTURAL BIOMETHANE PLANTS TO PRODUCE BIOSTIMULANTS

Figure 55: Integration of algal technologies in biomethane plants - biostimulants I. (detail from KEW2 presentation, Mezzanotte, 2023)

3.3.15 EU regulation and standardisation for the algal sector

The presentation delves into the regulatory and standardization landscape for the algal sector, highlighting the distinction between scientific, economic, and practical classifications of algae. It emphasizes the importance of understanding these classifications to navigate the complex web of European regulations and standards that govern the algal sector. Key Points: 1. Classification of Algae: Algae are classified differently for scientific, economic, and practical purposes. For regulatory, scientific, commercial, and production purposes, algae are considered a functional group of organisms, including microalgae, seaweed, cyanobacteria, and some heterotrophic organisms.

2. European Regulations: Algae are mentioned in over 2000 European texts, with key regulations covering aquatic organism health, water environment, and trade. The presentation highlights specific regulations like the Invasive Alien Species Regulation and the European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Policy, which have direct implications for the algal sector.

3. Product Classification: For product classification, algae are included in the customs classification with oilseeds, cereals, and other vegetable products. The statistical classification for production activity differentiates between agriculture and aquaculture, with further distinctions for freshwater and marine sectors.

4. Novel Food Regulations: The presentation discusses the impact of the Novel Food Regulation on algae, explaining the criteria for determining whether a product is considered novel. It outlines the process for food business operators to consult with authorities and potentially gain authorization to market their algal products.

5. Standards and Technical Documents: Various standards and technical documents underpin European legislation for algae. These standards provide requirements and guidelines for businesses, ensuring quality and consistency in the market. The presentation mentions standards from European standardization bodies, FAO, and private standards, highlighting their role in supporting legislation and promoting best practices.

6. Future Developments and Challenges: The presentation acknowledges the need for specific rules for certain challenges, such as issues with cyanobacteria. It advocates for targeted regulation only when necessary, to avoid imposing additional constraints on stakeholders. The availability of standards for various applications, including food, fuel, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals, is also highlighted.

In summary, the presentation provides a comprehensive overview of the regulatory and standardization environment for the algal sector, underlining the importance of understanding these frameworks for stakeholders involved in the production, processing, and marketing of algal products. It points to the availability of standards and technical documents as crucial tools for maintaining quality and compliance in the industry.

Classification
Regulation
Standardisation
Conclusions

Algae farming has no specific legislation but occurs in 2454 EU acts

- Algae are aquatic organisms (Reg. 708/2007 EU)
«...any species living in water belonging to the animalia, plantae and protista kingdoms...»
- Algae farming is part of aquaculture (Reg. 1379/2013 EU Annex1)
« 'aquaculture products' mean aquatic organisms at any stage of their life cycle resulting from any aquaculture activity »
- Algae products bear origin declaration obligation (Reg. 1379)
« ... may be offered for sale to the final consumer ... only if appropriate marking or labelling indicates ...the area where the product was caught or farmed »

Figure 56: Algae regulations (detail from KEW2 presentation, Mangini, 2023)

ALGAE AND NOVEL FOODS

Classification
Regulation
Standardisation
Conclusions

- 10 categories of novel foods
 - "... (vi) foods consisting of, isolated or produced from cell or tissue cultures derived from animals, plants, microorganisms, fungi or **algae** "
 - Biomass as such (bulk, powder, frozen paste, tablets, ...)
 - Algae extracts
 - Protein concentrates
- Not Novel Foods:
 - Food Enzymes
 - Additives
 - Flavourings
 - Extraction solvents
 - GMOs (genetically modified organisms)

Figure 57: Algae and novel food (detail from KEW2 presentation, Mangini, 2023)

3.3.16 Innovation space BioBall - Promoting technologies for regional material use of biogenic by-products and waste streams

The presentation provides an overview of BioBall, an action funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research with a focus on fostering innovation, sustainability, and value creation in the circular bioeconomy. BioBall emphasizes the integration of urban and rural areas, aiming to leverage biogenic residues, waste materials, and carbon dioxide to create sustainable products and close material cycles. Key Points: 1. Regional Focus: BioBall targets the Frankfurt Rhine-Main metropolitan area, characterized by its dense urban agglomeration, strong infrastructure, and significant biogenic residues due to industrial activity. The area serves as a fertile ground for bioeconomy activities due to its combination of urban and rural characteristics.

2. Project Goals and Funding: With a budget of 20 million euros, BioBall funds projects that are environmentally compatible and adhere to sustainability criteria. The focus is on transforming biomass or residual materials into enduring materials, thus avoiding carbon release into the atmosphere and supporting climate protection goals.

3. Circular Bioeconomy Projects: BioBall supports a variety of projects that utilize different biogenic carbon sources, aiming to create value-added products. Examples include: insect-based shrimp feed, food waste valorization, carbon dioxide utilization and processing waste into chemicals.

4. Infrastructure and Policy Support: The initiative seeks to develop infrastructure and adapt framework conditions to support the transition to a bio-based and fossil-free economy. This includes efforts to make carbon capture and utilization financially viable and to amend waste legislation.

5. Community Engagement and Networking: BioBall emphasizes community management and networking, hosting events and webinars, and maintaining an active online presence. The project aims to inspire collaboration among society, business, academia, administration, and politics to accelerate the transformation toward a circular bioeconomy.

6. Challenges and Opportunities: The presentation acknowledges the need for political support and the adjustment of legislative frameworks to facilitate the growth of the bioeconomy sector. It also highlights the potential of the region as a hub for bio-based industries, given the right support and infrastructure. BioBall represents a concerted effort to integrate circular bioeconomy principles in a metropolitan setting, fostering innovation, sustainability, and value creation through the transformation of biogenic waste and residues into valuable products. The initiative seeks to build a network of stakeholders and create an enabling environment for the bioeconomy to thrive.

BIOBALL FOCUSES ON INNOVATION, ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY AND VALUE CREATION

Environmental compatibility

- Increase resource efficiency & reduce emissions
- Combining climate protection and value creation

Utilizing biogenic carbon sources

- Developing new products and technologies to recycle residuals, waste and CO₂
- Closing material cycles

Contributing to the transformation of the FRM metropolitan region

- Inspire society, business, academia, administration & politics in the region
- Accelerate the transformation to a circular bioeconomy

Figure 58: Key targets in valorisation of biogenic by-products and waste streams - BioBall action (detail from KEW2 presentation, Michels, 2023)

ACTIVITIES OF THE INNOVATION SPACE BIOBALL

Figure 59: Key activities in valorisation of biogenic by-products and waste streams - BioBall action (detail from KEW2 presentation, Michels, 2023)

3.3.17 Value Chain Generator for circular bioeconomy

The presentation focuses on addressing bioeconomy and circular economy challenges through data-driven solutions. VCG.ai, a Stuttgart-based company, leverages data and smart technologies to identify and scale circular economy opportunities across regions and industries. They have developed a smart data platform and an algorithm called BioLink, which understands the connections between various material streams, technologies, and processes. Key Points: 1. Scalability Through Data: VCG.AI emphasizes the scalability of bioeconomy solutions through data analytics, enabling simultaneous exploration of opportunities for thousands of companies across various regions.

2. BioLink Algorithm: The BioLink algorithm is central to VCG.AI’s approach. It analyzes connections between material streams, technologies, and market requirements, helping to map out and prioritize bioeconomy opportunities.

3. Regional and Industrial Focus: VCG.AI works with regions, municipalities, and industrial supply chains to facilitate the transition to circular industry business models. They analyze material flows and market requirements to provide a detailed map for prioritizing solutions.

4. Validation and Data Sharing: The company ensures the validation of prioritized solutions by facilitating secure data sharing between companies. This process involves collecting data about current waste management practices and coordinating new development projects.

5. Economic and Environmental Impact: VCG.AI showcases the significant economic and environmental impact that bioeconomy solutions can have. For example, the valorization of brewery by-products can increase value significantly while reducing the footprint related to waste and by-product management. VCG.AI is driving forward the bioeconomy and circular economy by leveraging data and smart technologies. Their approach not only identifies and scales opportunities but also ensures that these solutions are economically viable and environmentally beneficial. The company invites collaboration and discussions on how their platform and services can support industry partners and regional developers in their bioeconomy initiatives.

Figure 60: Potential of circular economy (detail from KEW2 presentation, Dermastia, 2023)

Figure 61: VCG's Austrian study case (detail from KEW2 presentation, Dermastia, 2023)

3.3.18 The role of clusters role in Circular economy and Bioeconomy hubs (CEE2ACT)

The presentation delivers insights into the circular bioeconomy from a business perspective, emphasizing the importance of transforming current economic systems into more sustainable and environmentally friendly models. It highlights the need to reduce dependency on virgin material, utilize advanced technologies, and create new income streams and profits within companies.

Key Points: 1. **Global Environmental Impact:** The presentation starts with a stark reminder of the global environmental impact caused by wasteful practices, particularly in the extraction of virgin biomass and food waste. It highlights the adverse effects these practices have on marine life and people in non-European countries, emphasizing the need for a more sustainable approach.

2. **Circular Bioeconomy:** The concept of a circular bioeconomy is introduced, focusing on reducing waste and energy consumption and repurposing biogenic resources like bio-residues, by-products, and biowaste. The goal is to create new products for existing markets, such as the high-value applications in pharma, chemical, food, and packaging industries.

3. **Challenges in Europe:** Despite having the technologies and opportunities, the presentation notes that Europe is moving slowly in adopting a more sustainable circular bioeconomy. Challenges include administrative burdens, limited funding opportunities for market-level technologies, and the tendency for technologies developed in Europe to be deployed outside of Europe.

4. **Opportunities and Partnerships:** To address these challenges, the presentation suggests creating new partnerships and pushing for the implementation of sustainable technologies within European countries. It introduces the Interreg InnoBioVC Project, which aims to deploy new funding schemes supporting the deployment of technologies for high-value bioproducts.

5. **Integrated Value Chain Generator:** The project will integrate an integrated value chain generator and a sustainability assessment tool to help investors, bankers, and other stakeholders understand the profitability, return on investment, and positive environmental impact of green and circular projects.

6. **Engagement and Collaboration:** The presentation calls for engagement with various stakeholders, including banks, ministries, funding agencies, clusters, suppliers, buyers, and technology providers. It emphasizes that impactful partnerships are crucial for taking sustainable technologies to the market. The presentation stresses the urgency of transitioning to a circular bioeconomy, leveraging advanced technologies, and fostering collaborations to ensure a sustainable and profitable future for businesses and the environment alike. It highlights the need for systemic change and the role of strategic partnerships in driving this transformation.

Figure 62: Extraction and waste (detail from KEW2 presentation, Dermastia, 2023)

Figure 63: Circular bioeconomy by Antea ECG (detail from KEW2 presentation, Dermastia, 2023)

3.4 Workshop 3: Agriculture and food

Table 6 presents summarized information of the KEW on Agriculture and food that was held from 14th to 16th October 2024, with active links to relevant workshop materials on BioRural Toolkit and YT channel @BioRural.

Table 6: Agenda for the Knowledge exchange workshop on Agriculture and food

Day 1 - Generic principles	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Synergy of soil management with bioeconomy	Grzegorz Siebielec (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video
Key challenges in organic farming	Jaroslaw Stalenga (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video
Carbon farming - an answer to the challenges of the XXI century agriculture	Jerzy Kozyra (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video
Agroforestry - ecological restoration and climate change mitigation	Robert Borek (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video
Green Biorefinery opportunities for agriculture	James Gaffey (MTU)	Link to .pdf	Video
Value chains in food systems	Paweł Chmieliński (IRWIRPAN)	Link to .pdf	Video
Nutrient recycling practices - new opportunities for agriculture - MainstreamBio	Piotr Skowron (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video
Day 2 - Theme-specific aspects	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Artificial Intelligence in reducing plant protection chemicals – Ribes Technologies	Lukasz Kopinski (Ribes Technologies)	Link to .pdf	Video
Robot application in field cultivation - Agointelli	Michał Zabost (Agointelli)	Link to .pdf	Video
Use of mobile applications for rational fertiliser use by agricultural producers	Beata Jurga (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video
Innovative methods of plant simulation using mineral fertilizers and bio-stimulants	Anna Ogar (INSIGNES LABS)	Link to .pdf	Video
Plant and animal extraction service	Mateusz Galiński (Creoplus)	Link to .pdf	Video
Agriculture Drought Monitoring System (ADMS) in Poland	Katarzyna Żyłowska (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video
Circularity in the food processing industry – valorisation of various waste streams originating from wine production	Slavcho Aleksovski (University of Skopje)	Link to .pdf	Video
Day 3 - Cross-cutting issues	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Invention support and commercialization in the field of agriculture and food production of scientists from public research centres on the example of Poland	Piotr Jurga (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video
RAMAS -Remote Agriculture Monitoring and Advisory System for improvement of agri production and resources optimization	Mario Petkovski (AgFutura Technologies)	Link to .pdf	Video
Remote sensing for land monitoring	Rafał Pudelko (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video
Satellite monitoring for agricultural drought	Anna Jędrejek (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video
Geographical Information System - for food biomass assessment	Małgorzata Kozak (IUNG)	Link to .pdf	Video

3.4.1 Synergy of soil management with bioeconomy

The presentation provides detailed information about the EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe”. The main goal of the Mission is to establish 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030. Life on Earth depends on healthy soils. Soil is the foundation of our food systems. However, it is estimated that between 60 and 70% of EU soils are unhealthy.

The Mission leads the transition towards healthy soils by:

- i. funding an ambitious research and innovation,
- ii. programmes with a strong social science component,
- iii. putting in place an effective network of 100 living labs and lighthouses to co create knowledge, test solutions and demonstrate their value in real life conditions,
- iv. developing a harmonised framework for soil monitoring in Europe,
- v. raising people’s awareness on the vital importance of soils.

Also featured in the presentation soil – bioeconomy synergies, which includes Circular bioeconomy understood as optimized resource management to close nutrient, energy and biomass circles; innovative technologies for processing and upgrading biological resources to produce the carbon (C)-based products and services demanded by society without fossil carbon or crop residues to produce soil amendments and through pyrolysis, gasification, torrefication, fermentation and co-products (bio-oil, syngas, biogas, bioethanol).

It was mentioned that phosphorus recovery plays important role:

- i. about 85-90% of phosphate rock mined in the world is intended for food production (the rest is used for industrial applications such as the production of detergents),
- ii. it is estimated that at the current rate of use, the phosphorus resources may be sufficient for 100 – 470 years (FAO, 2008),
- iii. this means that the total global phosphorus resources are very limited. Estimates indicate that the increase in phosphorus demand will reach a global peak around 2030,
- iv. therefore, phosphorus has been included in the list of critical raw materials by the European Commission.

At the same time, the degree of phosphorus recycling is still low. Part of presentation was dedicated to the drought. The share of farms affected by drought in the most unfavourable growing seasons is extremely large, and the share of municipalities experiencing drought reaches 90% in critical periods. This means that up to 9 million hectares may be affected by drought in some years.

The EU Mission A Soil Deal for Europe

What this EU Mission deals with

The main goal of the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' is to establish 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030.

Life on Earth depends on healthy soils. Soil is the foundation of our food systems. However, it is estimated that between 60 and 70% of EU soils are unhealthy.

The Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe': 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils

The Mission leads the transition towards healthy soils by:

- **funding** an ambitious **research and innovation programmes** with a strong social science component
- putting in place an effective network of **100 living labs and lighthouses** to co-create knowledge, test solutions and demonstrate their value in real-life conditions
- developing a harmonised framework for **soil monitoring** in Europe
- raising people’s awareness on the vital importance of soils

Figure 64: A Soil Deal for Europe (detail from KEW3 presentation, Siebielec, 2024)

Soil – bioeconomy synergies

Circular bioeconomy

- ❑ Optimized resource management to close nutrient, energy and biomass circles
- ❑ Innovative technologies for processing and upgrading biological resources to produce the carbon (C)-based products and services demanded by society without fossil carbon
- ❑ Crop residues to produce soil amendments and through pyrolysis, gasification, torification, fermentation and co-products (bio-oil, syngas, biogas, bioethanol)

Phosphorus recovery need

- ❑ About 85-90% of phosphate rock mined in the world is intended for food production (the rest is used for industrial applications such as the production of detergents).
- ❑ It is estimated that at the current rate of use, the phosphorus resources may be sufficient for 100 - 470 years (FAO, 2008).
- ❑ This means that the total global phosphorus resources are very limited. Estimates indicate that the increase in phosphorus demand will reach a global peak around 2030.
- ❑ Therefore, phosphorus has been included in the list of critical raw materials by the European Commission. At the same time, the degree of phosphorus recycling is still low.

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Figure 65: Soil - bioeconomy synergies (detail from KEW3 presentation, Siebielec, 2024)

3.4.2 Key challenges in organic farming

The presentation provides detailed information about organic farming, which is an environmentally-friendly practice that needs to be further developed. The Commission will boost the development of EU organic farming area with the aim to achieve 25% of total farmland under organic farming by 2030. EU countries have targets for share of organic farmland in 2030 to reach. EU aims to reach in many countries nearly 30% of organic land. Until 2021 most of countries are not even in middle way.

The highest share was reported by Austria 26.5%, while Denmark 11.4%, Czech Republic 15.8%, Croatia 8.1%; Finland 14.4%, France 9.6%, Germany 10.8%, Italy 16.7%, Spain 10.8%. Scenarios of organic farmland development in Poland until 2030 were also presented. Realistic scenario -determined on the basis of the trend of changes in the area of organic farmland from 2004 to 2020 shows possibility of growth in 2030 by (1 mln ha) – 6%. While Optimistic scenario -determined on the basis of the trend of changes in the area of organic farmland from 2004 to 2013 shows Share of organic farmland in 2030 (2 mln ha) – 13%. A share of organic farmland in 2022 was (555 000 ha) – 3.8%.

The key challenges in organic farming discussed in the presentation:

- i. yield gap and low competitiveness of organic farming in relation to conventional agriculture,
- ii. increasing specialization of organic agricultural production,
- iii. conventionalisation and globalisation of organic market (increasing carbon footprint of BIO products).

Figure 66: The role(s) of organic farming in delivering the goals of European green deal (detail from KEW3 presentation, Stalenga, 2024)

How to improve crop yielding in organic farming? (A concept)

Eco-functional intensification (EFI) (Halberg et al., 2015)

1. Using the self-regulating mechanisms of organisms and of biological or organizational systems in a highly intensive way
2. Intensification of the beneficial effects of ecosystem functions, including biodiversity, soil fertility and homeostasis
3. Closing material cycles in order to minimize losses (e.g. compost and manure)
4. Searching for the best matches between environmental variation and the genetic variability of plants and crop

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Figure 67: How to improve crop yielding in organic farming (detail from KEW3 presentation, Stalenga, 2024)

Suggested further reading:

- [The importance of soil organic matter \(som\) on soil productivity and plant growth](#)

3.4.3 Carbon farming – a strategy to address the challenges of the XXI century agriculture

The presentation is devoted to the topic of carbon farming as one of the answers to the problems of the XXI century agriculture: the biggest of which is climate change that entails droughts, heat waves, and fires. First, dr hab. Jerzy Kozyra presented definitions of carbon farming as a land management practice and as a green business model for farmers, both involving reduction of carbon emissions from agriculture. To understand carbon farming and implement it right, it is important to know how to close the carbon cycle in agriculture and to know the processes carbon is involved in. Carbon farming models can be divided into three categories: action-based, results-based, and hybrid one.

An example of a practice-based model is the one included in the eco-schemes introduced in Poland as part of the CAP Strategic Plan for the years 2023-2027. The speaker presented a list of related practices which are eligible for payment under the carbon farming and nutrient management action. Carbon farming practices are also promoted under the Interreg Central Europe programme, for instance, the Carbon Farming CE project, whose objective is to test chosen practices in several European countries and evaluate them, among others, in terms of avoided C/CO₂ losses. The project intends also to test farming business models and mainstream the results across Europe.

The Biorural logo is repeated in the top left corner of the slide.

Carbon farming is a land-management activity that removes carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and results in increased carbon storage in living biomass, dead organic matter and soil by increasing or reducing carbon release into the atmosphere.

[COM\(2022\) 672 final](#)

Carbon farming can be defined as a **green business model for farmers** who undertake to improve agrotechnics, resulting in increased carbon sequestration from the atmosphere, carbon sequestration in living biomass, dead organic matter and soils, and/or reduction of carbon dioxide emissions into the atmosphere respecting ecological principles, biodiversity and natural resources.

[European Parliament \(UE\) 2018/841](#)

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Figure 68: Carbon farming definition (detail from KEW3 presentation, Kozyra, 2024)

Action-Based Carbon Farming: A scheme under which a farmer or landowner receives payment for the implementation of specific cultivation activities, regardless of the resulting impact.

Results-based carbon farming: a scheme under which a farmer or landowner receives a payment for reducing net greenhouse gas emissions from land, either through direct reductions in their greenhouse gas emissions or through the capture and accumulation of carbon dioxide in the soil. The amount of payment depends on the reduction results achieved.

Hybrid model of carbon farming: a scheme combining support for cultivation activities performed and support for direct reduction of greenhouse gases on the same area of agricultural land.

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Figure 69: Types of carbon farming (detail from KEW3 presentation, Kozyra, 2024)

Suggested additional reading:

- [Glossary:Eco-schemes](#)
- [Interreg: Carbon Farming CE](#)

3.4.4 Agroforestry - ecological restoration and climate change mitigation

This presentation is devoted to the topic of agroforestry and possibility of ecological restoration and climate change mitigation. The speaker opened his lecture with a provocative question: Is agriculture good or bad and how can we evaluate that? Agriculture is partially blamed for climate change and therefore subjected to many restrictions: the nitrogen policy, farm-to-fork strategy, and agro-ecological scenario are among those mentioned by the speaker. After presenting the limitations imposed on agriculture, dr. Robert Borek discussed the opportunities related to agricultural transformation and combining agroecology and bioeconomy, an example of which is agroforestry. According to the speaker, agroforestry is an excellent tool for such a transformation, as it allows to protect crucial resources such as water, soil, and biodiversity at the same time.

There is a huge potential for developing agroforestry in Europe, especially on degraded agricultural soils, as part of restoration practices. Introduction of trees on arable land has a significant potential to revitalize degraded areas, and produce additional biomass at the same time. Agroforestry is also a very potent tool when it comes to C sequestration. Trees can also protect water intakes from pollution from agricultural areas while, on the other hand, offering protection to agricultural fields by mitigating floods. Some examples showed how agroforestry can be adjusted to different context-specific needs in different landscapes. Dr Borek discussed the special role of trees in the nitrogen circulation, depending on tree species, which is particularly beneficial around agricultural farms. Some other examples included planting trees for animal feed or, in silvopastoral systems, to provide wind and heat protection to farm animals, among other benefits.

Figure 70: Agricultural transformation pathway (detail from KEW3 presentation, Borek, 2024)

Agroforestry

“Land use system in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land” (EC Regulation 1305/2013)

“Agroforestry practices include all forms of association of trees and crops (silvoarable systems) and/or animals (silvopastoral systems), on a parcel of agricultural land, whether in the interior of the parcel or on its edges (hedges)” (European Agroforestry Federation)

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Figure 71: Agri-forestry systems (detail from KEW3 presentation, Borek, 2024)

Suggested additional reading:

- [Combining agroecology and bioeconomy to meet the societal challenges of agriculture](#)
- [Agroforestry creates carbon sinks whilst enhancing the environment in agricultural landscapes in Europe](#)
- [Current extent and stratification of agroforestry in the European Union](#)
- [Online fodder tree database for Europe](#)

3.4.5 Green Biorefinery opportunities for agriculture

This presentation discusses green biorefinery opportunities for agriculture. The speaker started his presentation with a definition of a biorefinery. He also explained how it translates into GHG emissions reduction, which is one of key requirements farmers are facing nowadays. When it comes to possible feedstock for green biorefineries from agriculture, the speaker focused on the grass resources from grassland areas in EU, which is underutilised at the moment.

He discussed the processing of grass which leads to obtaining different products, namely: press cake, which in form of silage can become ruminant feed; and press juice, which can be further processed to extract (1) protein concentrate, (2) fructo-oligosaccharides, and (3) residual stream of nutrient-rich whey, which can be used respectively for (1) animal feed, (2) food and feed nutritional products, and (3) biogas production. The speaker presented a study based on feeding cake silage to dairy cows, it's effect on milk production and the emissions of methane from digestion, which results, although at an early stage, are quite promising. A similar study is being conducted for pigs, and the results suggests it could be beneficial to produce grass protein concentrate to be used as a feed additive for animals.

Another issue mentioned by the speaker was the importance of engaging farmers e.g. into Operation Groups and encouraging their participation in the whole process, based on the case of Irish dairy and pig farmers. By bringing the local farmers and producers on board they can increase the resilience of rural areas. The next steps include implementation of a demo-scale biorefinery on a sustainable dairy farm in Cork, Ireland, with an integrated AD unit and further integration of other renewable energy sources, aiming at developing a sustainable feedstock supply chain for the benefit of local farms and communities.

Green Biorefinery opportunities for agriculture

Share of total area by type and land cover (%), 2018

	Total area (km2)	Woodland and shrubland	Cropland	Grassland	Water areas and wetland; bareland	Artificial
EU	4 125 107	46.8	24.2	17.4	7.3	4.2
Belgium	30 666	27.8	29.1	28.2	3.3	11.7
Bulgaria	110 996	48.8	32.3	14.7	2.0	2.3
Czechia	78 871	39.3	33.7	20.1	2.4	4.4
Denmark	42 925	21.9	47.7	19.7	3.8	6.9
Germany	357 669	35.7	32.3	20.8	3.7	7.6
Estonia	45 336	58.7	12.9	16.2	10.5	1.7
Ireland	69 947	24.2	5.5	57.7	8.5	4.2
Greece	131 694	57.6	20.5	13.8	4.1	4.0
Spain	498 502	50.1	27.4	12.8	6.0	3.7
France	549 060	36.0	29.9	24.6	3.8	5.7
Croatia	56 594	59.2	16.6	17.4	3.7	3.2
Italy	302 072	41.2	31.7	16.4	4.2	6.6
Cyprus	9 253	46.5	30.4	10.9	6.0	6.2
Latvia	64 585	56.0	15.4	20.9	5.9	1.7
Lithuania	65 284	39.6	32.0	21.9	4.3	2.1
Luxembourg	2 595	36.9	21.8	32.9	1.1	7.4
Hungary	93 012	28.2	43.5	17.5	6.8	4.0
Malta	316	16.9	28.7	18.5	8.4	27.5
Netherlands	37 377	16.8	23.0	34.2	13.3	12.6
Austria	83 878	48.5	15.9	24.2	7.3	4.2
Poland	311 929	37.6	34.7	20.7	3.3	3.8
Portugal	89 103	56.2	16.3	15.8	5.3	6.4
Romania	238 398	37.0	32.6	22.9	4.7	2.8
Slovenia	20 273	65.8	11.0	17.8	1.2	4.3
Slovakia	49 035	49.5	27.5	17.6	2.0	3.4
Finland	338 411	69.6	5.3	5.7	17.6	1.7
Sweden	447 424	68.5	4.0	5.5	20.1	1.8

Source: Eurostat (online data code: lan_lcv_0vv)

- Grasslands account for 26% of the world's total land area and 70% of its agricultural area
- PG represents approximately 34% of the UAA and 14% of the TLU in the EU-28
- Additionally, 23 of the EU-28 countries, had >20% of their arable land in the form of PG

Figure 72: Green Biorefinery opportunities for agriculture (detail from KEW3 presentation, Gaffey, 2024)

Production of biogas from various sidestreams

		Grass press cake	Grass whey	de-FOS whey	Grass silage	Dairy whey
C:N ratio		19:1	17:1	9:1	17:1	-
Biogas and biomethane production (L/kg)	VS	510.7 (300.3)*	895.8 (544.6)*	597.4 (520.3)*	808.1 (479.0)*	(510-600)*
	DM	486.9 (286.2)*	707.7 (438.9)*	478.2 (416.5)*	737.2 (436.9)*	(280-330)*
	FM	189.9 (111.6)*	14.3 (8.7)*	41.5 (36.1)*	132.9 (78.8)*	-
Final weighted biogas composition	CH ₄ (%)	Open Access Article Biogas, Biomethane and Digestate Potential of By-Products from Green Biorefinery Systems by Rajeev Ravindras ¹ , Kwame Donkor ² , Lalitha Gottumukkala ³ , Ashay Maron ¹ , Amila Jacob Guneratnam ¹ , Helena McMahon ¹ , Sybrandus Koopmans ⁴ , Johan P. M. Sanders ^{3,4} and James Gaffey ^{1,5}				
	CO ₂ (%)					
	O ₂ (%)					
	H ₂ S (ppm)					
	NH ₃ (ppm)					

Biogas, Biomethane and Digestate Potential of By-Products from Green Biorefinery Systems

Clean Technol. 2022, 4(1), 35-50. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cleantechnol4010003>

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(This article belongs to the Special Issue Feature Papers for Clean Technologies 2021)

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Abstract

Global warming and climate change are imminent threats to the future of humankind. A shift from the current reliance on fossil fuels to renewable energy is key to mitigating the impacts of climate change. Biological raw materials and residues can play a key role in this transition through technologies such as anaerobic digestion. However, biological raw materials must also meet other existing food, feed and material needs. Green biorefinery is an innovative concept in which green biomass, such as grass, is processed to obtain a variety of protein products, value-added co-products and renewable energy, helping to meet many needs from a single source. In this study, an analysis has been conducted to understand the renewable energy potential of green biorefinery by-products and residues, including grass whey, de-FOS whey and press cake. Using anaerobic digestion, the biogas and biomethane potential

Article

Synergetic Benefits for a Pig Farm and Local Bioeconomy Development from Extended Green Biorefinery Value Chains

James Gaffey^{1,2,3,*}, Cathal O'Donovan¹, Declan Murphy⁴, Tracey O'Connor^{1,5}, David Walsh⁶, Luis Akijandara Negrón⁷, Kwame Donkor⁸, Lalitha Gottumukkala⁹, Sybrandus Koopmans⁹, Enda Buckley⁹, Kevin O'Connor¹⁰ and Johan P.M. Sanders¹

Abstract: As the global population rises, agriculture and industry are under increasing pressure to become more sustainable in meeting this growing demand, while maintaining impacts on global emissions, land use change, and biodiversity. The development of efficient and synthetic local bioeconomies can help to respond to this challenge by using land, resources, and side streams in efficient ways tailored to the needs of different regions. Green biorefineries offer a unique opportunity for regions with abundant grasslands to use this primary resource more sustainably, providing

[Check for updates](#)

Citation: Gaffey, J.; O'Donovan, C.

Figure 73: Production of biogas from various sidestreams (detail from KEW3 presentation, Gaffey, 2024)

Suggested additional reading:

- [Biorefined press cake silage as feed source for dairy cows: effect on milk production and composition, rumen fermentation, nitrogen and phosphorus excretion and in vitro methane production](#)
- [Production of Green Biorefinery Protein Concentrate Derived from Perennial Ryegrass as an Alternative Feed for Pigs](#)
- [Synergetic Benefits for a Pig Farm and Local Bioeconomy Development from Extended Green Biorefinery Value Chains](#)
- [Biogas, Biomethane and Digestate Potential of By-Products from Green Biorefinery Systems](#)
- [Green Biorefinery systems for the production of climate-smart sustainable products from grasses, legumes and green crop residues](#)

3.4.6 Value chains in food systems

The presentation provides a definition of food systems and explanation, why it is important to analyse them using a systemic approach, as opposed to sectoral, monofunctional, and fragmented analyses. Food systems are an interesting and valid topic of deliberations in the context of rural and agricultural development, contemporary agrarian change, European (dis) integration, global challenges, and societal transformation in EU and worldwide. Different elements of food systems that need to be taken into account when analysing include: food supply chains, food economy environment, individual factors and consumer behaviour, as well as external factors that can influence the system. In the context of a food value chain, the role of a strategic alliance of farmers and other supply-chain partners was underlined.

Partner alliances recognize that value of products depends on interdependence, collaboration and mutual support. Communicating shared values to customers differentiates products, expands market share and builds loyalty. The operational values guiding interactions between food chain partners are: accountability, long-term commitment, open and ongoing communication, and transparency. Among the values connected with environmental mission, it is worth to mention: local economy, preserving farmland, animal welfare, community access to fresh food, landscape and environmental services.

A separate part of the presentation was devoted to food systems based bioeconomy and the role of agriculture in sustainable food systems, taking into account the ambitious goals of the Green Deal and the Farm to Fork strategy. The speaker finished his presentation discussing the fundamentals for the transition to sustainable food systems, the challenges and possible ways to overcome them.

Food systems at the heart of the Green Deal

Greening the CAP - a farm-to-fork strategy

Conservation and **protection of biodiversity**

Climate objectives - climate neutrality by 2050 Link to the European Climate Pact - exchange of information on risks, joint measures, bottom-up initiatives

Clean, affordable **energy** - relying on renewable sources

Striving for **zero emissions** - monitoring air, water, soil pollution,

Industrial strategy for a **closed loop economy** - reducing material consumption. **NEW bio-based materials and products!**

Sustainable and intelligent **mobility** - reduce transport emissions by 90% by 2050

Sustainable development issues in all EU policies - "green": funding, investment, budgets, research, education, public procurement, above and beyond the "do no harm" principle
www.biorural.eu

Figure 74: The core role(s) and strategic significance of food systems in rural bioeconomies (detail from KEW3 presentation, Chmielinski, 2024)

Suggested additional reading:

- [Strategic concept paper for bioeconomy in Poland: executive summary](#)
- [Policies for the Future of Farming and Food in the EU \(.pdf\)](#)
- [Policies for the Future of Farming and Food in the European Union \(website\)](#)
- [Sustainable Food Systems](#)
- [Research and innovation challenges for better policies in food systems and bioeconomy transitions – evidence from Poland](#)
- [Delivering the European Green Deal](#)

- [Quantifying carbon for agricultural soil management: from the current status toward a global soil information system](#)
- [Carbon Farming](#)
- [The Big Idea: Creating Shared Value. How to Reinvent Capitalism—and Unleash a Wave of Innovation and Growth](#)
- [Food systems dashboard](#)
- [Toward a Healthy Sustainable Food System](#)
- [The food value chain](#)
- [Climate-smart agriculture](#)
- [Global diets link environmental sustainability and human health](#)
- [Food value chains](#)

3.4.7 Nutrient recycling practices- new opportunities for agriculture – MainstreamBio

The speaker discussed nutrient recycling practices, as well as research projects and policies connected with this subject. He started with defining nutrient recycling and nutrient recycling practices, which allow for recovering nutrients. Nutrient recycling practices are sustainable practices that help reduce waste and pollution while improving soil health. They reduce the use of non-renewable resources and thanks to that can reduce emissions into the environment. The huge demand for food combined with food production needs for nutrients creates a high need for fertilisers. The production and transportation of mineral fertilizers requires consuming large amounts of energy from fossil fuels and in case of e.g. phosphorus – depleting resources of a long-term renewable minerals. Nutrient recycling practices allow for solving those problems and many others.

The importance of sustainable nutrient management and recovery is highlighted in the recent European policy:

- i. the Green Deal formulates ambitious targets for sustainable food production, and reduction of nutrient losses by 50% accompanied by 20% reduction in the use of fertilisers is one of them,
- ii. the Integrated Nutrient Management Plan aims to ensure sustainable application of nutrients and stimulating markets for recovered nutrients,
- iii. the Common Agricultural Policy provides a unified policy regarding fertilisation and nutrient management
- iv. the EC Circular Economy Action Plan aims at reducing waste, dependence on raw materials as well as GHG emissions,
- v. the Water Framework Directive & Nitrates Directive preventing pollution of groundwater and surface water by nitrates from agricultural sources,
- vi. regulation (EU) 2019/1009 harmonizing standards for fertilizing products derived from organic and secondary raw materials,
- vii. waste Framework Directive regarding organic waste streams and their possible use for nutrient recovery,
- viii. Helsinki Convention: on prevention of pollution from agriculture and on nutrient recycling,
- ix. Baltic Sea Regional Nutrient Recycling Strategy promoting nutrient recycling in a closed loop and reduction of nutrient losses to water and atmosphere, among others.

The speaker discussed the new kind of RENURE fertilisers derived from livestock manure and its examples. He also presented research projects dealing with the topic of nutrient recycling, which are for instance: Mainstream BIO – Mainstreaming small-scale bio-based solutions across rural Europe; one of the objectives of which is to establish best practices for improved nutrient recycling. The project collected and described 30 nutrient recycling practices, some examples of which were briefly presented (slurry acidification, Manure & digestate separation). OrgSafety – introduction of innovative, cheap, and environmentally friendly method of hygenization of organic waste enabling its use in fertilisation CiNURGi – Circular Nutrients for a Sustainable Baltic Sea Region.

Nutrient recycling (NR) – the overall process where biomass or other nutrient-rich matter is utilized and/or managed to end up back in the cycle for the use of plants.

Nutrient recycling practice (NRP) – the activity of recovering nutrients from organic waste and wastewater and returning them to agricultural land as **recycled nutrient fertilizers (RNFs)**.

- NRP is a sustainable practice that helps reduce waste and pollution while improving soil health and increasing crop yields.
- NRP reduces the use of non-renewable natural resources and can reduce nutrient emissions into the environment.

Challenges:

- Food production needs nutrients – mainly N, P, K
- The huge demand for food = a high need for fertilizers
- The production and transportation of mineral fertilizers require high amounts of energy from fossil fuels
- The resources of phosphorus **are limited** ?, and long-term renewable.

Treatment processes that allow the upcycling of organic waste streams to nutrients and organic products
 Source: <https://www.vcm-mestverwerking.be/en/manureprocessing/10305/techniques-and-end-products>

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Figure 75: The importance of nutrient recycling (detail from KEW3 presentation, Skowron, 2024)

3.4.8 Artificial Intelligence in reducing plant protection chemicals – Ribes Technologies

The presentation focuses on the problem of pesticides used in agricultural production and possibilities of reducing them without affecting the yield. Pesticides help to protect agricultural crops against yield losses caused by pests, but they also have detrimental influence on the environment, leading to problems such as destruction of biodiversity, pollution of water bodies, decline in numbers of pollinators. They are also present in the food consumed by people. The problem of pesticides is recognised by the European Union and reflected in the European Green Deal which sets a goal to reduce the use of pesticides by 2030 by 50%. It means new strict regulations and monitoring of PPP but also new possibilities of financial support for innovations in this area.

The speaker presents an innovative machinery developed by Ribes Technologies: the autonomous electrically powered platform automatically applying selective pesticides. The prototype of the machine is tested on the currant plantation. Based on plant observation, the machine can recognise infected bushes (with insects and fungi) and apply conditional spraying with PPP. It allows reduction of pesticide use by up to 50%, as well as reduction of costs. Spraying takes place at night, not to affect pollinators on the plantation. Based on own experience, the speaker presented three conclusions, as follows:

- 1) Technological solutions of agriculture 3.0, 4.0 and 5.0 provide the best support for the development of business models in fruit production.
- 2) The Green Deal legal regulations are ahead of reality and technological solutions available for agriculture.
- 3) Technology for agriculture should be co-created with the support of EU funds rather than expected to use ready-made solutions.

Figure 76: How does the AI in reducing plant protection chemicals work? (detail from KEW3 presentation, Kopinski, 2024)

3.4.9 Robot application in field cultivation – Agointelli

The speaker presents Robotti – autonomous farming robot developed by AgroIntelli, which enables transition to sustainable farming by reducing labour cost, while increasing its precision. The success of the machine is based on four pillars:

- 1) Precision of machinery which is much higher in comparison to human labour,
- 2) Efficiency – Robotti can work 24/7 (up to 60h of continuous work, depending on the diesel tank capacity),
- 3) Reliability – the machine is built on high quality components and proven technology,
- 4) Safety is ensured by safety systems keeping the robot on track and monitoring the surrounding area to react to unforeseen obstacles. The robot is already 24 years old, it has undergone substantial improvements over time.

The present design allows for:

- i. Fully autonomous work
- ii. Implementation of precision farming
- iii. Reduction of soil compaction (weight of 3 tons)
- iv. Accurate and precise navigation

The robot is driven by standard diesel engine & hydraulics, and is equipped by a standard tractor 3-point hitch. It can work with the equipment existing on the farm. Robotti solves the most common problems of farmers: – Takes over repetitive tedious work – Allows for cost optimisation – Reduces soil compaction and degradation – In line with higher requirements for food safety and its documentation – Starting the season earlier (entering the field) thanks to light weight of the machine – The only agricultural robot compatible with standard implements on the market.

ROBOTTI

Our fully-automated farming robot enables high-value crop farmers to transition towards sustainable farming by reducing labour cost and adding an autonomous and precise capacity utilizing standard implements.

Robotization is instrumental in meeting these challenges by increasing efficiency and precision and *ROBOTTI is pioneering this new solution.*

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Figure 77: Presentation of autonomous farming robot ROBOTTI (detail from KEW3 presentation, Zabost, 2024)

Virtual Filed Walk – CROP EYE

AGROINTELLI Robotti Live Create Plan View Plans
Guide EN User 1

Filter Options

Fields: Boogers

Plans: KUL.L7 5 Row Hoe

Operations

2022-07-30 09:04:25 1% 31min

Operation overlay

Coverage

Virtual field walk

Show all image markers

cropmyn2
cropeye3

Tasks Sort all

Task 1

Start	2022-07-30 09:04:08
Finish	2022-07-30 09:25:49
Covered area	3.01 ha

Task 2

Start	2022-07-30 09:26:17
Finish	2022-07-30 10:17:07
Covered area	3.71 ha

Task 3

Start	2022-08-01 07:47:52
Finish	2022-08-01 09:11:09
Covered area	3.82 ha

Task 4

Start	2022-08-01 08:29:29
Finish	2022-08-01 10:23:44
Covered area	5.17 ha

Map Satellite
Map

Name: 50771209-0f25-4b1-f86c58165c7582782

Lat: 52.0218248581757819 Long: 11.250246977722812

Download

www.agrointelli.com

www.biorural.eu

Figure 78: Virtual field walk - visualisation (detail from KEW3 presentation, Zabost, 2024)

3.4.10 Use of mobile applications for rational fertiliser use by agricultural producers

The presentation is devoted to the issue of rational fertilisation based on the example of INTER-NAW application. This application is a free of charge decision support tool, available in desktop and online version. It is in line with the current legal requirements, e.g. the Nitrate programme regulating N-application in Poland. The tool calculates required doses of N-fertilisers based on the nutrient balance, taking into account N-sources such as: manures, other organic fertilisers, biological fixation, soil resources, plant by-product of pre-crop left on the field, and mineral fertilisers, as well as Nitrogen output.

The tool is also used to calculate PKMg fertiliser doses based on the balance method. Mineral fertilisers are recommended only as a supplement to nutrients provided from other sources. The speaker presented the structure of the tool, discussed its functionalities, and required data input. The advantages offered by the INTER-NAW tool are as follows: – Balanced fertilisation – Addressing the nutritional requirements of plants – Taking into account availability of nutrients – Importing data from existing systems – Practical implementation of the “Nitrate Programme” – Meeting EU requirements

Figure 79: Manure management and fertilizer rate calculation (detail from KEW3 presentation, Jurga, 2024)

Figure 80: Inter-naw's effects (detail from KEW3 presentation, Jurga, 2024)

3.4.11 Innovative methods of plant simulation using mineral fertilizers and bio-stimulants

This presentation is devoted to bio-stimulants and mineral fertilisation of plants. The speaker discussed various regulatory limitation imposed on farmers and climate induced risks they have to face at the same time. The answer to this challenge is making use of innovative technology to improve crops resilience, allowing for limiting the use of plant protection products and fulfilling the targets set by EU regulations. The product focuses on empowering crops, not fighting pathogens.

It (1) activates enzymes and metabolic pathways to enhance crop growth and productivity, (2) stimulates natural immunity of crops, (3) mitigates abiotic stresses caused by drought and frost, (4) enhances carbon sequestration through intensifying photosynthetic activity of plants, and biomass accumulation in roots and shoots. Pure Technology has been tested for safety in Poland and abroad. It's effectiveness has been proven both in laboratory and field trials. The product is said to reduce carbon footprint in agriculture as well. The product is already available on the market.

The benefits for farmers and consumers enumerated by the speaker include: (1) Higher crop yields (5-30%) without extra strain on the environment (2) Producing more and better with less (3) Driving productivity of high-quality food while increasing the humus content in soil.

PURE® TECHNOLOGY: our solutions answers areas

01 ENHANCED CROP GROWTH, MINIMIZE LOSSES, MAXIMIZE FARMS PROFITABILITY:

- Guarantees healthy plant development and increased, consistent yield
- Improved quality of the yield (higher protein, starch, oil and sugar content)
- Reduction of synthetic fungicides by 20-50% & nitrogen by 20% while keeping high yield

02 SUSTAINABLE & ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY SOLUTION:

- Mineral based solution: PURE safe for human & nature – no pesticides, no residues
- Decreases carbon footprint & CO₂ emission
- Very low carbon footprint & Global Warming Potential (GWP: 2,25 CO₂ eq./ha)
- No microplastic – all formulations components EU approved

03 PURE AS A PART OF INTEGRATED CROP MANAGERMENTS

- PURE formulation compatible with crop protection products and fertilizers
- PURE can be applied solo or as a tank mix partner (0,6-1,2l/ha)
- Excellent miscibility (tank-mix partner) with available fungicides (compatibility tested with over 150 different active substances), fertilizers and biostimulants

INSIGNES LABS

Figure 81: Technological advantages of the Pure® technology (detail from KEW3 presentation, Ogar, 2024)

Value Proposition & Benefits For Farmers & Consumers

01 Improved productivity by up to 30% without putting extra strain on the environment
3 in 1 (fertilizer + stimulation + complementary with fungicides)

02 Help farmers to produce “more and better with less”
Residues reduction & Reduction of synthetic fungicides by 30-50% & nitrogen by 20%, while maintaining plant health protection efficiency- Green Deal

03 Maximize productivity and farm profitability - higher crop yields & better yield quality
Higher protein content - cereals; higher starch content - potato; higher sugar content - sugar beet; higher oil content - OSR

Figure 82: Value proposition of the Pure® technology (detail from KEW3 presentation, Ogar, 2024)

3.4.12 Adding value through extraction of bioactive compounds in agriculture

The presentation is devoted to plant and animal extraction services, using ultrasound extraction and selective sorbents. The speaker presented the offer and expertise of the company Creo Plus, and discussed specific case studies where their technology was successfully used. The first case study was shrimp shell extraction. Shrimp shell is a huge amount of waste in seafood industry and has a large untapped potential. The Creo Plus company developed a process of astaxanthin and chitin extraction. The second case study concerned developing an extraction process of valuable substances from plants.

Figure 83: Bioactive compounds of plant extracts and their advantageous properties (detail from KEW3 presentation, Galinski, 2024)

3.4.13 Agriculture Drought Monitoring System (ADMS) in Poland

The presentation discussed the phenomenon of agricultural drought and the Agricultural Drought Monitoring System. The speaker presented different types of drought: atmospheric, hydrological, agricultural, focusing on the last one and its implications for agriculture. One of them is the loss of yield and therefore loss of farmers' income. To deal with this problem, the Polish Ministry commissioned development of a drought monitoring system, to keep track of the losses and support farms affected. The Agricultural Drought Monitoring System (ADMS) was developed and implemented by the Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation – State Research Institute in Puławy (IUNG-PIB).

The purpose of ADMS is to identify areas where drought losses have occurred in crops included in the “Act on Subsidies for Crop and Livestock Insurance in Poland” (Dz. U No.150, item 1249, 2006, No. 120, item 825). The following crops (or group of crops) are specified: winter cereals, spring cereals, grain maize, silage maize, rape and turnip rape, potato, sugar beet, hops, tobacco, fields grown vegetables, fruit shrubs, fruit crops, strawberries leguminous crops. This Act introduces the definition of agricultural drought as follows: Drought is indicated by damage caused by the occurrence of a climatic water balance below a certain value for various species or groups of cultivated plants and soil categories during any six-decade period from 21 March to 30 September.

Climatic water balance (CWB) was defined as difference between precipitation and potential evapotranspiration (ETP) for a six consecutive ten-days period. In the vegetation season 14 monitoring reports are produced. The first report evaluating CWB in the season of ADAMS is presented for the period from 21 March to 20 May, the next and following reports in the year is issued every 10 days. In the second step, based on the CWB map, an exceedance of the CWB drought threshold defined for crops covered by the monitoring system and four classes of soils with different vulnerability to drought are performed, based on this analysis, the map of the area affected by drought is made.

The ADMS indicate the area affected by drought based on climatic water balance map and soil categories map. The information is available at LAU-2 level (municipalities). The analyses are updated every 10 days from 20 May to 30 September. The analyses of the ADMS are available for farmers on the web service (<https://susza.iung.pulawy.pl/en/>), where they can check information on the use of maps or interactive tables at municipality level (LAU-2).

Figure 84: Example of drought monitoring system: map of potential drought zones in Poland (detail from KEW3 presentation, Żyłowska, 2024)

3.4.14 Circularity in the food processing industry – valorisation of various waste streams originating from wine production

This presentation is devoted to the topic of food circular economy and possibilities of waste streams valorisation from wine production. The speaker discussed the circular economy as opposed to the linear one, which depletes finite resources and pollutes the environment. Circular economy is based on recycling and reusing instead of generating waste streams. The process of wine production from grapes is a very old process. Grapes are rich in sugars, organic acids, vitamins, bioactive compounds and minerals, significant amounts of which are found in peels and seeds. Those are considered waste and as such have not been adequately used till now, usually deposited on landfills in huge amounts each season.

The speaker presented the process of wine production and discussed each step, leading to obtaining the product but also large amounts of waste in form of grape pomace, including peels, seeds, and stalks. Grape seeds are rich in oil and polyphenols, grape skins contain antioxidants, while grape stalks can be a source of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. This waste can be valorised using new technologies, such as oil extraction, extraction of cellulose and other hydrocarbons, phenols and natural colorants, or bioethanol, biofertilizer, and biochar production. Adoption of such technologies can have both socio-economic and environmental benefits.

Figure 85: Red wine products and by-products (detail from KEW3 presentation, Aleksovski, 2024)

Figure 86: One of the possible biorefining schemes in the valorisation grapeseed (detail from KEW3 presentation, Aleksovski, 2024)

3.4.15 Invention support and commercialization in the field of agriculture and food production of scientists from public research centres on the example of Poland

This presentation is devoted to the topic of commercialization of research and support of invention in the field of agriculture and food production, based on the example of research centres in Poland.

Figures reflecting the intensity of innovation transfer from R&D effort in Poland are unfavourable. According to the study conducted by the Supreme Audit Office in 2013, where sixteen universities were analysed, out of almost 5,000 research projects, only 95 projects resulted in successfully commercialised outputs.

In 2015, major national research and higher education institutions established a partnership, The Polish Association of Centers for Technology Transfer (PACTT.pl). This is a voluntary association of representative units of Polish universities responsible for the protection, management and commercialization of university Intellectual Property (IP).

Key institutions providing support to public RDI institutions in terms of innovation management and commercialisation of R&D outputs, are the Centers for Technology Transfer (TTO), which are pursuing the following objectives:

- supporting research by academics and students at universities,
- shaping an environment conducive to innovation and commercialization
- promoting cooperation between industry and the scientific sector, or making laboratories and other research resources available to universities,
- Assistance in the development and transfer of new technologies to industry.

Since the introduction of the Centers for Technology Transfer, the situation is gradually improving. The system of intellectual property management or the change of existing procedures concerning the technology transfer process is working better and better in practice, giving a real chance for the success of the organisation. The services that are realised by TTOs are characterised by increasing professionalism and thus the parameters and results realised by them are more and more promising. The sales from the implemented scientific projects are becoming more and more popular and thus other innovation centres, such as technology parks or academic business incubators, are also being established.

PACTT Technology Database

- Catalogue of innovations
- Type of technology: e.g. know-how, software, patents/patent applications, utility models, industrial designs, work
- Research institution (please choose)
- Research institution (e.g. Poznań University of Life Sciences)
- Technology:**
 - Microbial preparation designed to solubilise insoluble forms of phosphorus contained in soil,
 - Vegetable analogue of sausage and method of production of vegetable analogue of sausage,
 - Office armchair assembly.

<https://pactt.pl/katalog-innowacji>

www.biorural.eu

Logos: CEE2ACT, hr, IUNG

Figure 87: Science-business PACTT technology database (detail from KEW3 presentation, Jurga, 2024)

3.4.16 RAMAS-Remote Agriculture Monitoring and Advisory System for improvement of agri production and resources optimization

The presentation is devoted to monitoring and advisory systems in agriculture, allowing for production improvement and resources optimisation, based on the example of RAMAS (Remote Agriculture Monitoring and Advisory System) developed by AgFutura Technologies. Digital technologies for agriculture bring about benefits such as efficiency, productivity, sustainability, and traceability. It helps to optimise the use of resources while maximising yields and their quality, to incorporate the robotics and replace difficult human labour with machinery.

The speaker presented how the RAMAS system works; it consists of 5 key layers: (1) farm and monitoring layer (installation and configuration of sensors on the field to collect data, supported with remote sensing sources), (2) data center/processing layer (producing information on the crops state on the field); (3) data analysis and reporting layer (producing recommendation for farmers); (4) recommendation adaptation layer (supporting implementation of recommendations); (5) calibration layer (continuous evaluation of reports and processes).

The benefits for farmers are as follows:

- i. Continuous expert support and advise
- ii. Crop health monitoring
- iii. Insight into all agrotechnical operations
- iv. Obtaining recommendations for irrigation, pesticides, fertilisation, and other practices to optimise effort and costs

Figure 88: Remote Agriculture Monitoring and Advisory System - RAMAS (detail from KEW3 presentation, Zhivachki, 2024)

Figure 89: Benefits of RAMAS (detail from KEW3 presentation, Zhivachki, 2024)

3.4.17 Remote sensing for land monitoring

The presentation focuses on the topic of satellite remote sensing in land monitoring. The speaker presented different types and methods of remote sensing depending on the height of observations conducted: terrestrial machinery, low altitude, aerial, and finally satellite remote sensing. Remote sensing can also be divided based on the mode of measurements into passive and active, the first one based on reflection received from the observed objects, and the second requiring emitting radiation and analysing the way it is reflected by the objects. Another characteristics of remote sensing is resolution offered by different sensors, presented on the example offered by Pleiades, Sentinel, and MODIS, offering resolution of 2 m, 10 m, and 250 m respectively. The first two can be useful for application in precision agriculture.

The speaker focused on the possibilities offered by the Sentinel imagery and presented how it can be useful for application in agriculture, e.g. (1) plant development monitoring; (2) drought/ flood/ frost/ hailstorm effect; (3) precision agriculture support; (4) Land use and Land use change mapping, and many others. Remote sensing can be used for developing monitoring and advisory systems, an example of which is FaST platform – an EU supported digital service platform which is a decision support system dedicated for farmers, advisors, administration, policy makers and other interested stakeholders.

Example of monitoring

Triticale

Monitoring of the development of vegetation

Correctness of the sowing date

State of vegetation before winter

Condition after wintering

The effects of :

- Drought / hail / frost
- Spring drench / frost
- Disease / pest shock
- Bad fertilisation
- Etc...

Figure 90: Example of remote sensing monitoring in agriculture (detail from KEW3 presentation, Pudętko, 2024)

Suggested additional reading:

- [Copernicus Services Data Hub](#)
- [FaST platform](#)

3.4.18 Satellite monitoring for agricultural drought

The presentation is devoted to Satellite monitoring of agricultural drought, based on sentinel imagery. Sentinel imagery is available free of charge thanks to the Copernicus Programme, a long-term EU observation and monitoring programme, which currently has seven satellites in orbit, offering: (1) and (2) – high resolution land and ocean monitoring; (3) – ocean and global monitoring; (4), (5) and (5P) – atmospheric composition monitoring; (6) sea level monitoring. Twelve more are already approved to launch. Satellite imagery has been used for agricultural application for almost 50 years.

It allowed to monitor natural phenomena, such as drought occurrence, crop conditions and identification, but was expensive until now, when Satellite-1 and -2 images are available free of charge. Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 high-resolution satellite images allow for permanent monitoring even of a single agricultural field in time and space. Sentinel-2 mission was designed to provide high-resolution optical images for land monitoring, but their availability depends on weather conditions, while Sentinel-1 mission provides high-resolution radar images in all weather conditions. The synergy of these two types of data creates opportunities for Earth observations that have never existed before. The speaker presented how the imagery can be used in practice, based on the conducted research regarding agricultural drought remote sensing in West Pomeranian Voivodeship in Poland, 2021.

The study included a comparison of agricultural drought seen from satellite and how farmers estimated their crop losses. When exploring the relationship between farmers' declarations and the vegetation condition, no cause-and-effect relationship was found. This may be caused by the fact that the vegetation condition depends not only on the soil and weather (drought), but also on a wide range of agrotechnical practices conducted by farmers. The agrotechnics influences the crops' condition, which is discussed based on the comparison of two neighbouring plots – differences are visible both in the RGB image as well as when comparing the average NDVI values.

EARTH OBSERVATION MISSIONS – SENTINEL MISSIONS – COPERNICUS PROGRAMME

The Copernicus programme is a long-term European Union Earth observation and monitoring program. Currently, the program has launched seven dedicated families, the so-called Sentinels.

Sentinel-1: high-resolution land and ocean monitoring

Sentinel-2: high-resolution land and ocean monitoring

Sentinel-3: ocean and global land monitoring

Sentinel-4: atmospheric composition monitoring

Sentinel-5 Sentinel-5P: atmospheric composition monitoring

Sentinel-6: sea level monitoring

now in orbit - 7 satellites: Sentinel-1A, Sentinel-2A, Sentinel-2B, Sentinel-3A, Sentinel-3B, Sentinel-5P, Sentinel-6A

approved to launch – 12 satellites: Sentinel-1C, Sentinel-1D, Sentinel-2C, Sentinel-2D, Sentinel-3C, Sentinel-3D, Sentinel-4A, Sentinel-4B, Sentinel-5A, Sentinel-5B, Sentinel-5C, Sentinel-6B

In preparation are six high priority candidate "expansion" missions.

Sentinel-7: Anthropogenic CO₂ emissions monitoring

Sentinel-8: High Spatio-temporal resolution Land Surface Temperature

Sentinel-9: Copernicus Polar Ice and Snow Topography Altimeter

Sentinel-10: Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment

Sentinel-11: Copernicus Imaging Microwave Radiometer

Sentinel-12: Radar Observing System for Europe - L-band SAR

Figure 91: Utility of the Sentinel missions for environmental monitoring (detail from KEW3 presentation, Jędrejek, 2024)

Article
Exploring the Potential Use of Sentinel-1 and 2 Satellite Imagery for Monitoring Winter Wheat Growth under Agricultural Drought Conditions in North-Western Poland

S-2 NDVI, NDWI

S-1 WV, VH, WV/VH

Figure 92: Possible use of satellite imagery for monitoring in plant production (detail from KEW3 presentation, Jędrejek, 2024)

3.4.19 Geographical Information System- for food biomass assessment

The presentation devoted to data integration in GIS for biomass monitoring. The speaker presents definition of Geographical Information System formulated by ESRI: system that creates, manages, analyses and maps all types of data. It is used in many fields, by many organisations. GIS helps users understand patterns, and relationships in geographical context. The speaker presents the components of GIS. Data is the basic component of GIS and comprise analogue, statistical, digital spatial, and remote sensing data, which are integrated into data management systems – spatial information systems enable the compilation of information that is usually grouped on different maps or in different databases.

A GIS software program supports the use of a geographic information system, providing the ability to create, store, manage, query, analyse, and visualize geographic data. The GIS software industry encompasses a broad range of commercial products but there is also more and more free software constantly updated and developed by the GIS community. Analyses performed in GIS environment have been used in many research projects presented. A series of spatial data and analytical models were collected and developed to create the “Biomass Estimation System”, which is based on components similar to the GIS components. The presented results in form of maps and geoportals are e.g.: BioBoost Platform presenting technical and theoretical potentials of various types of biomass for NUTS3 units, or Bioeconomy Platform – tool supporting the development of the bioeconomy in Poland and providing access to a set of geoportals.

An example on a national scale is the biomass monitoring system created as part of a targeted subsidy. In the case of agricultural biomass, it uses the annually updated database of the Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture (ARMA). This database contains information necessary for monitoring and modelling agricultural biomass resources in the field of plant and animal production. The detailed nature of this data made it possible to estimate individual potentials at the farm level, taking into account three production directions: farms with plant production, farms with animal production, mixed farms.

DATA

- analog data
- statistical data
- digital spatial data
- remote sensing data

Components of GIS

HARDWARE

ANALYSIS
-methods
-procedure

SOFTWARE

SPATIAL INFORMATION

<https://www.usgs.gov/media/images/gis-data-layers-visualization>

Figure 93: Organisation and GIS use of geospatial data in primary bioeconomy sectors (detail from KEW3 presentation, Kozak, 2024)

3.5 Workshop 4: Forestry and habitats

Table 7 presents summarized information of the KEW on Forestry and habitats that was held from 12th to 14th March 2024, with active links to relevant workshop materials on BioRural Toolkit and YT channel @BioRural.

Table 7: Agenda for the Knowledge exchange workshops on Forestry and habitats

Day 1 - Generic principles	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Forest characterization and opportunities	Valters Samariks (Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava")	Link to .pdf	Video
Forest protection and management (Fire, insects – North EU)	Āris Jansons (Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava")	Link to .pdf	Video
Forest fire protection and management (South EU)	Miguel Almeida (Association for the Development of Industrial Aerodynamics)	/	Video
Automation in forest operations	Janis Ivanovs (Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava")	Link to .pdf	Video
Day 2 - Theme-specific aspects	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Wood utilization in construction	Kristaps Cepulis (Latvian Wood Construction Cluster)	Link to .pdf	Video
The advantages and disadvantages of structural wood usage	André Dias (SerQ – Forests Innovation and Competences Center)	/	Video
Challenges and Perspectives of Timber utilization	Anna Andersone and Ilmārs Preikšs (Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies)	Link to pdf.	Video
Residual Biomass Collection Centres: Integrated Valorisation of Biomass & Management Digitalisation	Elisabete Silva and Isabel Brás (Polytechnic Institute of Viseu)	/	Video
Day 3 - Cross-cutting issues	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Biodiversity conservation in private forests of Latvia: involvement of landowners.	Ģirts Baranovskis (Nature Conservation Agency of Latvia)	Link to .pdf	Video
PEFC Certification in Latvia	Līga Jansone (Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava")	Link to .pdf	Video
Certified Forestry for Sustainable Production: The Portuguese Case Study	Raquel Martinho (Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification)	/	Video
Birch Bark Extractives and Their Potential	Jānis Rižikovs (Latvian State Institute of Wood Chemistry)	Link to .pdf	Video

3.5.1 Forest characterization and opportunities

In the presentation “Forest Characterization and Opportunities”, Valters Samariks discussed the diversity of forest ownership and coverage in Europe, along with EU policies regulating forests. It emphasized the significance of forests in capturing greenhouse gasses through tree biomass and soil carbon accumulation. The data showed stable annual CO₂ removals by European forests, while harvested wood products also played a notable role. Graphical representations illustrate substantial CO₂ removals achieved by forest land and harvested wood products in the EU, highlighting the tangible impact of forestry practices on carbon sequestration.

Projections reveal contrasting futures for North and Central Europe, with sustainability challenges looming large for the latter. Predictions suggest that 34% of Central European forests may become unsuitable for forestry due to climate change but Nordic/Baltic regions will remain suitable and contribute positively to carbon sequestration. Latvia serves as a case study for multifunctional forest management, characterized by small gap sizes, balanced species composition, and an increasing proportion of mature and old stands. A nuanced approach to forest protection is advocated, emphasizing strategic allocation of forest areas to meet diverse conservation objectives. Practical examples underscore the importance of informed forest management decisions, dispelling the notion that “doing nothing” is always the optimal choice.

Advocacy is made for a unified understanding of forest management practices to maximize carbon sequestration while enhancing forest resilience to natural disturbances. In conclusion, a holistic approach is presented to enhancing carbon storage in European forestry, emphasizing climate-smart management, prevention of carbon loss, and the substitution effect of wood products. By leveraging existing forest resources and implementing strategic interventions, European forests can serve as powerful allies in the fight against climate change.

Figure 94: Annual CO₂ removals in EU Forest Land (detail from KEW4 presentation, Samariks, 2024)

Ecosystem carbon potential

limiting factors for forest carbon:

- a) natural disturbances;
- b) **specific ecosystem potential to store carbon;**
- c) forest management

Figure 95: Potentials and limitations of forest-based carbon (detail from KEW4 presentation, Samariks, 2024)

Suggested additional reading:

- [Forest Biodiversity in Europe](#)
- [Old-growth forest carbon sinks overestimated](#)

3.5.2 Forest protection and management (Fire, insects – North EU)

In the presentation “Forest Protection & Management”, Latvian State Forest Research Institute “Silava” Senior Researcher and Professor Āris Jansons discusses the impact of climate change on forests, with a focus on natural disturbances such as drought, pests, and extreme weather conditions. Climate change, with its associated extremes, directly impacts the survival and growth of trees while amplifying the effects of natural disturbances. These disturbances, ranging from weather-related events like wind and fire to biotic factors, significantly alter forest dynamics and ecosystem services provision. Āris emphasizes the importance of local adaptation and understanding genotypic differences in response to weather extremes. Weather extremes, including wind and fire, pose immediate challenges to forest stability and carbon sequestration. Sustainable genotypes emerge as essential tools for enhancing forest resilience in the face of these disturbances.

By adopting low-density planting techniques and strategic forest management practices, the risks associated with such disturbances can be mitigated. Fires, often ignited by human activity and exacerbated by changing weather patterns, represent a significant threat to forest health. Āris highlights the multifaceted nature of fire risk, which is influenced by factors such as fire intensity, tree species composition, and forest structure. Adaptive management strategies that account for these variables are crucial for minimizing fire-induced damages. Biotic disturbances, including pests and diseases, are expected to escalate in frequency and severity in the future. Advocates are proactive forest management approaches that address stand composition and thinning practices to mitigate biotic damage risks effectively. Looking forward, Āris underscores the importance of embracing climate-smart forestry practices. These practices aim to enhance forest adaptation and resilience, contribute to climate change mitigation efforts, and sustainably increase forest productivity.

By leveraging improved forest reproductive materials and embracing diverse genotypes, forest managers can navigate the complexities of climate change while ensuring long-term ecological and economic sustainability. In conclusion, it is emphasized the need for collaborative and interdisciplinary approaches to forest management. Balancing biodiversity conservation with economic viability is achievable through informed decision-making and adaptive strategies. By working together, stakeholders can safeguard forest ecosystems for future generations.

Figure 96: Effect of natural disturbances in forestry (detail from KEW4 presentation, Jansons, 2024)

Future of forest management

Mitigation of climate change and its impact on society and biological diversity

Adaptation of forests and forestry

Main objectives of **climate-smart forestry** is to ensure forest adaptation and resilience to climate change, to rise contribution to climate change mitigation and sustainably increase forest productivity and incomes. (Nabuurs et al., 2017)

Figure 97: Importance of introducing climate-smart forestry (detail from KEW4 presentation, Jansons, 2023)

3.5.3 Forest fire protection and management (South EU)

In the “Forest Fire Protection & Management” presentation, Miguel Almeida, a senior researcher and invited professor at the University of Coimbra, discusses the importance of recognizing forest fires as a natural part of ecosystems and the different types of wildfires, including surface fires, underground fires, and crown fires. He emphasizes the significance of managing forest fuels to prevent the vertical and horizontal transitions of fire in the forest environment.

The speaker also suggests strategies for forest managers, such as selecting species with higher foliage moisture content, reducing leaf litter fuels, and increasing the crown base height to reduce the likelihood of crown fires. Creating forest mosaics and landscape plans, using less flammable trees, and managing surface fuels are also crucial in minimizing forest fire risk. Despite the role of different tree species in releasing firebrands, the goal is to manage forest fuels effectively to reduce fire intensity and prevent significant losses.

Figure 98: Suggested additional reading on forest fire protection: FirEURisk portal (detail from KEW4 presentation, Almeida, 2024)

3.5.4 Automation in forest operations

In the presentation “Automation in Forest Operations” by Latvian State Forest Research Institute “Silava” remote research development manager Jānis Ivanovs, the transformative impact of automation on forestry management is explored. Jānis highlights how automation reshapes traditional forest operations, emphasizing increased efficiency, sustainability, and conservation efforts. Remote sensing technologies, including satellite imagery and aerial surveys, provide invaluable data for assessing forest conditions. Predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms leverage this data to predict various forest inventory variables, offering detailed insights into forest ecosystems.

Utilizing GNSS enables precise rut detection, aiding in the identification of vehicle paths and minimizing environmental impact. This technology optimizes operational efficiency while contributing to sustainable forestry practices. Automation in forestry operations offers benefits such as increased efficiency, improved sustainability, and enhanced conservation efforts through accurate monitoring and optimized resource management. In conclusion, automation revolutionizes forestry management by harnessing the power of remote sensing and GNSS technologies. Through automation, greater efficiency, sustainability, and conservation can be achieved in forest operations, ensuring the preservation of forest ecosystems for future generations.

Remote Sensing in Forestry

Predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms can be applied to the data collected from remote sensing and GNSS technologies to predict many different forest inventory variables

Benefits of Automation

Enhanced Efficiency: Automation streamlines processes, reducing manual labor and time required for tasks like tree species classification and rut detection.

Sustainability: By utilizing remote sensing and GNSS data, automation promotes sustainable forestry practices by minimizing environmental impact and optimizing resource management.

Conservation Efforts: Automation facilitates accurate monitoring of forest conditions, leading to improved conservation efforts and biodiversity preservation.

Figure 99: Remote sensing and benefits of automation in forestry (detail from KEW4 presentation, Ivanovs, 2024)

3.5.5 Wood utilization in construction

In the presentation “Wood Utilization in Construction: Latvian Experience” by the Managing Director of the Latvian Wood Construction Cluster – Kristaps Ceplis, the extensive use of wood in construction is explored, drawing on Latvia’s rich forestry heritage and expertise in wood building techniques. Wood’s significance as a building material is emphasized, highlighting Latvia’s abundant forests covering over 50% of its territory. Pine and spruce, common tree species, are lauded for their excellence in construction, with sustainable forestry practices ensuring a steady supply of wood for building purposes. Historical landmarks like the Riga Cathedral, constructed with 400-year-old timber, exemplify wood’s durability and longevity. Similarly, St. Peter’s Church, once Europe’s tallest wooden building, underscores Latvia’s historical legacy in wooden architecture.

The presentation underscores Latvia’s prowess in wood construction, with nearly 100 enterprises specializing in this field. These enterprises, export-oriented and with extensive experience, collaborate with technical schools to advance technological capacity and innovation in wood building. In conclusion, the presentation celebrates Latvia’s embrace of wood in construction, driven by its abundant natural resources, expertise, and commitment to sustainability. Through wood utilization, Latvia continues to shape a resilient and sustainable built environment, fostering a legacy of innovation and excellence in wood construction for future generations.

Why wood?

- 50+ % of territory is covered by forest
- The most common tree species in Latvian forests are pine and spruce – excellent building material
- Half of Latvian forests are owned by the state
- Latvian forestry is sustainable
- Long history of building wooden houses

Wood construction – basic facts

- Almost 100 enterprises focusing on wood construction in Latvia
- Export oriented industry
- Long experience in wood building
- Technological capacity
- Cooperation with technical schools

Figure 100: Wood utilization for construction in Latvia (detail from KEW4 presentation, Ceplis, 2024)

3.5.6 The advantages and disadvantages of structural wood usage

In the presentation “The Advantages & Disadvantages of Structural Wood Usage”, André Dias discusses his expertise in wood construction, particularly focusing on glulam and cross-laminated timber (CLT) systems. They highlight historical examples of timber structures and how wood usage has evolved. The advantages of using wood products are emphasized, such as sustainability, cascading use, speed of construction with prefabrication, and modularity. However, challenges like ensuring sustainable forest practices for raw material supply, and addressing increasing prices due to lack of materials availability while optimizing cascading use to reduce costs are also discussed. Another challenge is maintaining durability through proper technical knowledge of specifications to prevent issues like fungal attacks that can compromise structural integrity.

Additionally addressed is fire prevention by incorporating sealing materials and considering the behaviour of wood during design stages. This comprehensive overview provides insights into both the benefits and complexities associated with modern-day wooden constructions.

Figure 101: Cross laminated timber and Glued laminated timber (detail from KEW4 presentation, Dias, 2024)

3.5.7 Residual Biomass Collection Centres: Integrated Valorisation of Biomass & Management Digitalisation

In the presentation “Residual Biomass Collection Centres: Integrated Valorisation of Biomass & Management Digitalisation”, Isabel Brás and Elisabete Silva outline the project Biovalor at the Polytechnic Institute of Viseu addressing rural fires in Portugal. The focus is on managing agro-forestry fuels to understand and reduce fire causes, particularly the intentional burning by farmers. Strategies include a residual biomass collection centre encouraging waste delivery instead of burning, with 1800 tons managed effectively. Initiatives also involve composting and mulching processes for sustainable waste use, reducing reliance on open-air burning that can harm the environment and human health. Exploring alternative energy sources from agro-forestry waste for local uses further decreases dependency on fossil fuels and lowers carbon emissions.

Life cycle assessments using SimaPro software evaluate methods such as wood chip valorization and power plant electricity generation compared to natural gas usage. Positive impacts were observed, particularly in global warming and ecotoxicity categories. The project fosters community engagement through data sharing and consciousness-raising efforts. Therefore, the strategy emphasizes collaboration among stakeholders, implementing eco-friendly solutions for the long-term preservation of ecosystems and community well-being.

Figure 102: Challenges arising from burning of residual biomass (detail from KEW4 presentation, Bras, 2024)

Figure 103: Beneficial uses of residual forest biomass (detail from KEW4 presentation, Bras, 2024)

3.5.8 Biodiversity conservation in private forests of Latvia: involvement of landowners

In the presentation “Biodiversity Conservation in Private Forests of Latvia: Involvement of Landowners” by the Head of Nature Conservation Agency of Latvia – Ģirts Baranovskis, the challenges and strategies for biodiversity conservation in Latvia’s private forests are explored, emphasizing the pivotal role of landowners in forest management and conservation efforts. Against the backdrop of the EU Forest Strategy and Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, which advocate for integrating ecosystem services and biodiversity-friendly practices into forest management, Latvia grapples with significant challenges. With over 50% of forests privately owned and diverse forest management goals, the conservation status of forest habitats remains unfavorable, necessitating innovative approaches to engage private landowners.

Understanding the opinions of forest owners is crucial in designing effective conservation strategies. A survey conducted in 2021 revealed varied attitudes among landowners, with smaller properties and those less dependent on forestry income showing greater openness to biodiversity conservation measures. In response to the survey findings, the “Living Forest” pilot-program was developed, offering voluntary participation for private forest owners. The program provides advisory and financial support, focusing on biodiversity conservation measures such as preserving old trees and creating multi-aged forest stands. The initial implementation of the pilot-program has seen positive engagement from biodiversity-focused forest owners, with diverse forests of varying sizes and species compositions participating. The presence of rare and specially protected species underscores the program’s potential for enhancing biodiversity conservation in private forests.

In conclusion, the presentation highlights the promising outlook for voluntary biodiversity conservation in private forests and proposes integrating such models into Latvia’s broader forest biodiversity conservation strategies. Through collaboration and innovative approaches, private landowners can play a significant role in safeguarding Latvia’s rich forest ecosystems for future generations.

How to involve private landowners?

Figure 104: Involving of private forest owners in biodiversity conservation (detail from KEW4 presentation, Baranovskis, 2024)

«LIVING FOREST»

Habitat conservation (A1)	Habitat creation (A2)	Nature-friendly forestry (B)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do not interfere (no logging in the protected habitat) • Preserve the buffer zone around the protected habitat polygons (selective logging is allowed) • No harvesting for economic purposes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create multi-aged forest stand structure • Preserve and create dead wood • Preserve the buffer zone • No harvesting for economic purposes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preserve the oldest and largest trees (20 trees/ha) • Preserve and create dead wood • Selective logging to mimic natural disturbances • Create multi-aged forest stand structure • Seasonal forestry restrictions • Harvesting of timber for economic purposes is allowed

Figure 105: Ecosystem benefits of biodiversity conservation in forests (detail from KEW4 presentation, Baranovskis, 2024)

3.5.9 PEFC Certification in Latvia

In the presentation “PEFC Certification in Latvia” by Līga Jansone, the implementation of the Program for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) in Latvia is discussed, highlighting its role in promoting sustainable forest management practices. PEFC, established in 1999 by small- and family forest owners in Europe, aims to endorse national forest certification systems globally. In Latvia, with its abundant forest cover and significant forestry industry, PEFC certification serves as a crucial tool for demonstrating social, environmental, and economic responsibility. In Latvia, with 52% of land covered by forests, PEFC certification offers accessible options for all forest owners. Latvia’s forestry area holds certificates for around 1.76 million hectares, showing increased adoption over time.

The latest iteration of Latvia’s forest management certification system adheres to ISO standards and includes new chapters addressing plantation forests and trees outside forests (TOF), reflecting a commitment to continuous improvement in forestry practices. Overall, the presentation underscores the importance of PEFC certification in promoting sustainable forest management practices in Latvia, enhancing market access for certified products, and contributing to the long-term conservation of Latvia’s forest resources. Through continued collaboration and adherence to international standards, Latvia remains committed to responsible forest stewardship for future generations.

PEFC – The Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification

PEFC – The Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification - is a leading global alliance of national forest certification systems. As an international non-profit, non-governmental organization, PEFC are dedicated to **promoting sustainable forest management** through independent third-party certification.

In 1999, small- and family forest owners from Europe came together to create a forest certification system that would enable them to demonstrate their excellence in sustainable forest management. 20 years on, PEFC is the largest forest certification system in the world! 56 national members.

The main reasons for certification

- Certification is one of the tools being used to demonstrate our social, environmental and economical responsibility.
- The main reason for certification is also market demand even though the industry is not willing to pay additional price premium for certified wood.

Figure 106: What is PEFC certification and what are its benefits? (detail from KEW4 presentation, Jansone, 2024)

3.5.10 Certified Forestry for Sustainable Production: The Portuguese Case Study

In the presentation “Certified Forestry for Sustainable Production: The Portuguese Case”, Raquel Martinho discussed the Portuguese Forest Certification (PFC) system, which ensures sustainable forest management and operates globally with international and national standards. Portugal’s forestry, with extensive private ownership of eucalyptus, maritime pine, and cork oaks, contributes significantly to the economy while maintaining social and environmental balance. PFC focuses on sustainability indicators like carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and socioeconomic functions to ensure certified entities follow good practices from forests to consumers.

Recent expansions include urban spaces, emphasizing holistic ecosystem management and balancing economic prosperity with societal well-being. By choosing PFC-certified products, consumers help preserve forests, support sustainable development goals, and contribute positively to environmental, social, and economic outcomes.

Protecting forests globally and locally

While the concept of sustainable forest management is global, its implementation is local. This is why we work with local organizations to advance responsible forestry through national forest certification systems.

Forests are highly diverse; as is their management, local traditions, cultural and spiritual expectations, average property sizes and support structures. This diversity means one size does not fit all when it comes to forest certification.

This is why PEFC do not set one international standard that all forest owners must follow in order to achieve [certification](#).

Instead, we work through national forest certification systems, enabling countries to tailor their sustainable forest management requirements to their specific forest ecosystems, the legal and administrative framework, the socio-cultural context and other relevant factors.

 UMA MARCA QUE IMPORTA

Figure 107: Certified forestry for sustainable provision of wood (detail from KEW4 presentation, Martinho, 2024)

Figure 108: Illustration of PEFC certification along the wood supply chain (detail from KEW4 presentation, Martinho, 2024)

3.5.11 Birch Bark Extractives and Their Potential

In the presentation “Birch Bark Extractives and Their Potential” by Jānis Rižikovs, the focus is on exploring the various applications and benefits of birch bark extractives, particularly betulin and suberin. The Latvian State Institute of Wood Chemistry, where the research is conducted, aims to develop environmentally friendly technologies for utilizing wood and plant biomass sustainably, contributing to economic, social, and ecological benefits. Birch bark, sourced from silver birch and downy birch trees, is a valuable resource used in furniture, pulp, and plywood production. It comprises extractives such as betulin and suberin, offering numerous beneficial properties. Betulin, a major component of birch bark extractives, exhibits various biological activities, making it suitable for applications in cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and even cancer research.

Suberin, another important extractive, possesses unique properties suitable for adhesive, coating, and polymer applications. Its renewable and eco-friendly nature makes it an attractive alternative to conventional additives. Experimental procedures involve fractionation and purification techniques to isolate specific components of birch bark extractives for further analysis and application development. The potential applications of suberinic acids extend to diverse industries, including cosmetics, bio-polymer production, organic synthesis, and eco-friendly construction materials. Despite challenges such as high viscosity and heterogeneous composition, efforts are underway to optimize extraction and processing techniques to maximize the utilization of birch bark extractives. The presentation underscores the value of interdisciplinary collaboration, research infrastructure, and industry partnerships in realizing the full potential of birch bark extractives for sustainable and innovative product development.

The diagram illustrates the 'Strategy' for Birch Bark Extraction, structured under the Biorural logo and 'Smart Specialization Strategies of Latvia'. It details three key areas of focus:

- Wood Materials:** Wider use of wood and wood-based materials in building and construction: improving the durability properties and providing a predictable service life. In the studies, ecological and economical products and technologies are sought for improvement of biodegradability and ageing resistance.
- Biorefinery:** The valorization of European and local plant biomass: mainly wood and its by-products, considering biorefinery and wasteless conceptions, is the vital conditions for the development of bioeconomy. The advanced analytical tools for chemical analysis of natural products and processes of their obtaining are directed to complete sustainable use of raw materials, through designing of a multi product or feedstock portfolio.
- Green Chemistry:** Renewable feedstock as raw materials for synthesis and production of chemicals and polymers: which substitute petrochemical origin materials. Ecologically and economically viable polymers synthesis method, up-scaling of polymer production. Life cycle analysis (LCA) of developed processes.

The diagram also includes a vertical sidebar 'T3.1 Presentations', a 'www.biorural.eu' URL, and a 'Smart Specialization Strategies of Latvia' header with icons for Knowledge, Smart Materials, Smart Energy, Bioeconomy, and Innovation and Digitalization Technologies.

Figure 109: Birch Bark Extraction Strategy (detail from KEW4 presentation, Rizikovs, 2024)

Figure 110: Potentials of birch bark in plywood industry (detail from KEW4 presentation, Rizikovs, 2024)

3.6 Workshop 5: Bioenergy

Table 8 presents summarized information of the KEW on Bioenergy that was held from 16th to 18th April 2024, with active links to relevant workshop materials on BioRural Toolkit and YT channel @BioRural.

Table 8: Agenda of the Knowledge exchange workshop on Bioenergy

Day 1 - Generic principles	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Bioenergy in the EU context	Manolis Karampinis (Bioenergy Europe)	/	Video
Biomass-based solid fuels production	Edmundo Marques (Polytechnic Institute of Viseu)	/	Video
Direct combustion heat-producing boilers	Juliana Maschmann (SCIVEN)	/	Video
Gasification - Technology relevance and case studies in Portugal	Octávio Alves (BioRef-CoLab)	Link to .pdf	Video
Sustainable pathways using Biogas and Biomethane under a circular economy approach	Dimitris Kourkoumpas (CERTH/CPERI)	/	Video
Day 2 - Theme-specific aspects	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Small scale, low temperature, biomass based CHP systems: A Case Study	Jorge André (University of Coimbra)	Link to .pdf	Video
Biogas lab operation , main characteristics, and the utilization of digestate	Themis Sfetsas (QLAB/BLAG)	/	/
Yilkins technology : integrated solutions to decarbonize energy production and bio-chemical industry	Juan Carlos Estrada (Yilkins)	Link to .pdf	Video
Energy Community producing pellets in Greece	Vasilis Filippou (ESEK)	/	/
Day 3 - Cross-cutting issues	Lecturer	Presentation	YouTube link
Life Cycle Assessment and associated methods for sustainability evaluation in bioenergy	Fausto Freire (University of Coimbra)	Link to .pdf	Video
Solar drying and gasification of Sewage Sludge to obtain bioenergy	Virginia Pérez (CEDER-CIEMAT)	/	Video
2nd generation bioethanol production from forest management and agriculture residues	Ana Brásio (Prio)	Link to .pdf	Video
Advanced biofuels for transportation	Kostis Atsonios (CERTH/CPERI)	Link to .pdf	Video
GAMS utilization on biogas sector : a case study	Stelios Rozakis (Technical University of Crete)	Link to .pdf	Video

3.6.1 Bioenergy in the EU context

Representing the Brussels-based trade organization of Bioenergy Europe, Manolis aimed to contextualize bioenergy in the European Union. He begins by addressing the usual misconception around the end uses of energy, where almost half of it is used for heating, the rest equally split between electricity and transportation. Bioenergy is present in all energy production, being most dominant in the heating sector, whilst also being the most meaningful contributor in the transport sector through biofuels. Half of the bioheat consumed yearly in the EU involves the residential sector, and another quarter is utilized by the industrial sector; the major end users in that sector are the paper, pulp and printing sector, wood and wood products, non-metallic minerals and food and beverages. These are industries that make good use of residual biomass resources.

As Manolis points out, modern bioheat solutions are mostly automated. They offer on-demand, cheap, close to zero-emissions, renewable energy, a key difference between them and other RE sources. Their size depends on the required application. In terms of the biomass supply, Manolis stressed that solid biomass is the largest contributor of biomass feedstocks. In 2021, forest biomass made up 71.37% of the total energy feedstock, with agricultural biomass at 15.34% and waste biomass at 13.29%. Manolis addresses the discussion around the restraints on biomass supply around the EU, contrasting with the example of open field burning of wild overgrowth in rural areas and wildfires. He argues that there would be major benefits of making use of that energy source in an organized way rather than waste it. Biomass can also aid in energy independence and defossilization, as most feedstocks are produced within the EU, and what is imported comes from trusted partners.

Additionally, since the EU is leading in the field of bioenergy technology, making use of related technologies promotes domestic EU industry. Manolis argues that bioenergy is poised to increase in consumption in the future, heading towards 2050, both relatively and in absolute terms. A key point would be to strive for a technological update on biomass appliances to improve energy efficiency. Next, Manolis discusses the criticism around bioenergy and EU legislation, and the argument that bioenergy is not sustainable; he affirms in contrast that bioenergy is the only sustainable RE source, accounting for RED II (2018) sustainability criteria. He also addresses the difficulties sometimes encountered by burgeoning bioenergy projects, which must familiarize themselves with complex and shifting legislation and regulations.

Concluding, he explains the manifesto of Bioenergy Europe towards energy transition, which contains 3 steps:

- i. a clear fossil fuels exit strategy,
- ii. sustainable and efficient bioenergy that enhances energy security,
- iii. a plan to unlock the potential of bioenergy with carbon capture and storage, utilization and biochar.

Figure 111: The EU's current energy system (Eurostat, 2024)

Bioenergy, a key for the future

FIGURE 1.2 Breakdown of total final energy consumption by energy carrier between 2020 and 2050 under the 1.5°C Scenario

- The role of bioenergy in future energy consumption is expected to increase, both in absolute terms, as well as in relative importance
- Important to move away from inefficient, traditional uses to modern uses of biomass

Image Source: IRENA World Energy Transitions Outlook 2023: 1.5°C Pathway

Figure 112: Potentials of bioenergy in the future energy system (Eurostat, 2024)

Suggested additional reading:

- [Bioenergy Europe](#)

3.6.2 Gasification - Technology relevance and case studies in Portugal

Dr. Alves begins his presentation with a brief mention of the institution he is employed by, BIOREF, a private non-profit association involved in bioenergy, renewable gases, and the sustainable bioeconomy. Dr. Alves goes over biomass gasification: he provides a definition, along with a visual schematic of the process and the chemical reactions that take place during it. The products of the process are demonstrated – gas, biochar, and tar – along with their properties and applications. Next, he demonstrates schematics for five common reactor configurations and discusses their basic setup and characteristics in terms of products, requirements, and applications.

Ensuing, he offers a detailed breakdown of the characteristics of the product gas from each reactor configuration and the conditions required to produce it, demonstrating the syngas’s composition in H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄ and its lower heating value. He then proceeds to discuss the pros and cons of gasification compared to combustion in terms of emissions, scale of application, energy efficiency, valorisation potential etc. He goes on in detail on the issue of contaminants present in the product gas and the problems they can pose such as catalyst poisoning, corrosion, formation of deposits, air pollution and health issues when inhaled by humans. To address this, he proposes an example of a gas cleanup system that utilizes various steps to capture particulates, tars, nitrogen, and sulphur components to even trace contaminants and can produce a cleaned syngas. He presents a case study, currently being developed in Portugal over a time span of 4 years, called HYFUELUP (Hybrid Biomethane Production from Integrated Biomass Conversion), and funded by Horizon Europe.

The goals and innovations of the project are then presented, along with a demonstration of a site located in Tondela (Viseu), Portugal, able to produce biomethane at a rate of 50 m³/h using digestate sludges and lignocellulosic wastes. Wrapping up, Dr Alves goes over the highlights and major points of interest of his presentation, along with suggestions for future national interventions to assist the gasification sector in its growth and further uptake by the industry and economy at large.

2 Gasification concepts and relevance

- Definition: **thermochemical conversion of biomass** using oxidant agents for partial oxidation at high temperature, generating a **product gas for energy applications**.
- General schematic, reactions and products:

Pilot-scale gasifier

Reactions	
Oxidation	Reduction
$C + O_2 \rightarrow CO_2$	$C + 2H_2 \leftrightarrow CH_4$ (hydrogasification)
$2C + O_2 \rightarrow 2CO$	$CO + H_2O \leftrightarrow CO + H_2$ (water-gas shift)
	$C + CO_2 \leftrightarrow 2CO$ (Boudouard)

Tar

Char & ash

Figure 113: The gasification process (detail from KEW5 presentation, Alves, 2024)

2 Gasification concepts and relevance (cont.)

▪ Product properties and applications:

Product	Properties	Applications
Product gas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High CO content (5-26 vol.%). • High H₂ content (13-27 vol.%). • Significant lower heating value (7-16 MJ/m³). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy generation (thermal and electric). • Renewable gases (biomethane and hydrogen). • Liquid biofuels (methanol, ethanol, dimethyl ether, Fischer-Tropsch diesel and gasoline).
Biochar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High carbon and ash contents. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catalysts. • Construction materials. • Remediation of effluents.
Tar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixture of liquid hydrocarbons (e.g., naphthalene, benzene, toluene). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recovery of chemical products. • Liquid fuels (through regeneration). • Recirculation to the gasifier.

Figure 114: Gasification products, their properties and applications (detail from KEW5 presentation, Alves, 2024)

3.6.3 Biomass-based solid fuels production

Professor Marques begins his presentation with an overview of the EU’s biomass supply. He explains that bioenergy is the largest contributor of renewable energy in the EU, simultaneously being the largest indigenous energy source. Forests also play a crucial role, that of carbon sinks; they are natural reservoirs that absorb and store carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, helping to mitigate climate change by reducing greenhouse gas levels. Due to recent natural disasters like wildfires, storms, insect outbreaks, the aging of ecosystems, and increased wood harvesting, this role has been undermined between the time span of 2010 to 2020.

Despite that, Prof. Marques points out that Portugal has great potential for solid biomass fuels production due to its vast coverage from forests and agricultural land, spanning 73% of its territory. Portugal is already producing 71% of its electricity from biomass sourced from its central regions. Prof. Marques stresses the importance of using such fuels towards the global efforts for carbon neutrality. Converting biomass into solid fuels can be done with various technologies, including pyrolysis, torrefaction and pelletization. Commonly, the raw materials used can include wood, crop residues and waste from agricultural or forestry activities.

In his scientific research and laboratory trials, he has utilized various species of grasses, shrubs, or trees, along with RDF-refuse, livestock farming residues and meat processing residues, various other agricultural or food residues such as vines from grapes and kiwi, nut shells, olive pits etc., to produce biomass pellets. He mentions that the biggest restraining factor for more widespread utilization of such resources remains the prohibiting legislation around them. Next, Prof. Marques lists the production steps pellet production requires and proceeds to explain the most common problems associated with pellet production, including temperature and moisture content. To address these, he elaborates on the measures they proposed to solve them: strict temperature and moisture control, and most importantly, size distribution, as particle size greatly affects the end product’s physical properties.

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Biomass-Based Solid Fuels Production

Biomass Supply

Bioenergy makes up the majority (55,7%) of renewable energy in the EU and is its largest indigenous energy source.

Bioenergy works by transforming the potential ENERGY STORED in BIOMASS into useful heat and electricity.

Figure 2 - Forest land carbon sink in the EU, MtCO₂eq (adapted from EEA)

Figure 1 - Distribution of the various biomass feedstock for energy in 2021 (Adapted from Eurostat estimate)

Recently, the EU’s Forest carbon sink has faced significant challenges... A decrease in the period between 2010 and 2020, can be seen!!!

Factors that contributed to this decline were: fires, droughts, storms, insect outbreaks, etc., the aging of these ecosystems, reducing the carbon absorption and increased wood harvesting.

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Figure 115: Biomass potentials for solid fuels production (detail from KEW5 presentation, Marques, 2024)

Biomass-Based Solid Fuels Production

Pelletization

Pelletization has to be performed at temperatures between 80 and 200 °C, to ensure lignin softness and plastic deformation, leading, after cooling, to stronger particle bounding.

Raw-material (sawdust) moisture content should be between 8 and 12%.

The particle size influences the durability of pellets; the smaller the particle size, the greater the pellets durability..

Pellets of good durability should be obtained from an average size between 0.5 and 0.7 mm, which usually appears as a breaking point from the above dimensions of 1.0 mm

Figure 4- Sieving results – mass vs mean diameter

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Figure 116: Pelletization as the most common strategy for biomass-based solid fuels (detail from KEW5 presentation, Marques, 2024)

3.6.4 Direct combustion heat-producing boilers

The focus of the presentation is on biomass direct combustion heat boilers. The presentation begins by explaining the basic principles of their operation, what types of fuels they utilize, leading up to how this technology will help transition to renewable feedstocks, like biomass. She briefly goes over the advantages and area of application of each technological category: biomass, natural gas, coal and oil fired boilers, and last, municipal solid waste boilers. Juliana then makes an overview of the European biomass boiler market, which is expected to grow at a Compound Annual Growth Rate of 7.8% from 2024 until 2032, ending up at a projected market value of 20.1 billion dollars.

This growth will be based on recent advances on emissions reduction, boiler efficiency and increased business and industry interest in bio-heat and electricity. An overview of the global biomass boiler market follows, based on the feedstocks, including woody biomass, agricultural waste, industrial waste, urban residues and others. The presentation explains how increasing decarbonization efforts are expected to expand woody biomass technology uptake.

Following, the challenges of such market growth are laid out:

- i. high initial investment costs, which can be addressed by financing schemes such as the Energy as a Service (EaaS) or other government incentives across the EU can help offset these expenses,
- ii. fuel availability, which is addressed by constructing more dependable and diverse supply chains to meet regional demands and ensure sustainability. Regarding the biomass value chain, Juliana makes breaks it down and elaborates on land use, biomass production, conversion, and end use.

The main contributors of biomass are following: forestry, agriculture, marine biomass, as well as the various residues from various human activities. Then there is also mention on the role it plays in the wider bioeconomy, as well as aiding towards the creation of a circular economy. Modern biomass boilers are poised to play an important role in the wider bioeconomy cadre, so Juliana breaks down the technical characteristics and operation of a typical automatic SCIVEN biomass boiler to demonstrate its properties and capabilities compared to outdated systems.

These systems are capable to replace natural gas boilers in terms of convenience due to modern automations, while offering a considerably lower cost of maintenance due to significantly less expensive feedstocks, even considering the time of the year as a factor, as demonstrated by a comparative analysis presented. The presentation closes with a virtual Q&A session which addresses some of the most commonly asked questions around biomass, bioheat, related technologies and the bio-based economy as an expert in the field, while also demonstrating SCIVEN's principles and approach around it.

Figure 117: Direct combustion heat boilers (detail from KEW5 presentation, Maschmann, 2024)

Figure 118: Biomass boilers market overview (detail from KEW5 presentation, Maschmann, 2024)

3.6.5 Sustainable pathways using Biogas and Biomethane under a circular economy approach

The presentation begins with a brief overview of CERTH and CPERI and his team’s role, activity, and capabilities. He goes on to elaborate on biogas as a gateway to high-value products, such as fertilizers, biopolymers, or more advanced fuels like biomethane. Biogas is part of all latest EU environmental plans like RED II and REPowerEU, as EU has emphasized decarbonization and energy security to combat climate change. Dimitris emphasizes how, to achieve the EU’s ambitious 2030 goals towards a greater biomethane adoption, there will have to be an upscaling of the production across it.

He goes on to a critique of some of the key issues REPowerEU will have to address to achieve its goals for a more energy independent Europe, namely diversifying its feedstock sources, unlocking the potential for more localized energy production, and prioritizing sustainability throughout all steps of the biogas production chain. Dimitris then presents a few key projects associated with the themes of biogas production, sustainable energy production and circular economy. These EU-funded projects reflect its greater efforts to address climate issues in a scientific and systematic way. First, BIOMETHAVERSE, a research project involving pilot technologies set out to boost biomethane production in the EU by reducing associated costs and increase production, in a sustainable way.

The project has 5 active pilots in 5 different countries: Greece, Italy, France, Sweden, and Ukraine. He goes on to present the technical characteristics of the Greek pilot project, located in Central Macedonia, Greece: inputs and outputs of biogas plant, along with its prospects and goals. Next, the ALFA project, another research project on the biogas potential of livestock farming, with a focus on designing a business portfolio and providing technical support services to parties interested in integrating biogas solutions, inside a cadre of increased community engagement and societal acceptance.

Last, the CO2SMOS project: Advanced chemicals production from biogenic CO2 emissions for circular bio-based industries, aims to develop a platform of technologies to transform the emissions produced by bio-based industries into high added value chemicals to be used in conjunction with other bio-based products. It focuses on gas fermentation, electrocatalytic reduction, bio-catalyzed conversion, liquid fermentation, and catalytic conversion technologies.

Figure 119: The multiple production pathways for biogas and biomethane (Source: IEA, 2024)

Figure 120: The role of biogas in a circular economy (Source: ECN, 2024)

3.6.6 Small scale, low temperature, biomass based combined heat and power systems: A Case Study

Jorge begins his presentations with a schematic explaining the basic principles of a micro or mini-CHP unit: how it differs from a separated heat or energy production unit, its inputs and outputs, while also explaining key terminology. He explains that the main benefit of this technology is economic, as it can cover a potential client's energy needs and give him independence from the electric grid. Jorge continues to elaborate on the various types of CHP technologies used, how they are differentiated and their main parts. He goes on to indicate the relation between thermal efficiency and electric efficiency on various technologies, including Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC), Stirling Engine (SE), Internal combustion Engine, Micro Gas Turbine (MGT) and Fuel Cell (FC).

Following, a detailed schematic of a typical ORC unit is presented, explaining the basic principles of its function and the biomass-fed laboratory prototype used in this case study. The main findings of the study are presented next, focusing on the relationship between electrical power output and thermal power output along with the factors that affect it.

Figure 121: Properties of micro/mini combined heat and power systems (detail from KEW5 presentation, Andre, 2024)

3.6.7 Yilkins technology: integrated solutions to decarbonize energy production and bio-chemical industry

The presentation begins with a brief overview of the company Yilkins, based in the Netherlands. Yilkins was founded in 2015, quickly upscaling its activities and production capacity in its main areas of interest, drying and carbonization technology (torrefaction, charcoal, biochar), all skid based. They also offer patented drying and torrefaction equipment. Yilkins’s success is based off the expertise of its founders, who are pioneers in the fields of torrefaction and inventors of various patterns. Yilkins quickly increased its output capacity in the timespan of 2016 to 2020 by a factor of 10 and aims to increase it by a further factor of 4 by 2026. The presentation argues that torrefaction, despite some recent criticism because of commercial or technical failures it encountered, has great potential, if its several relative parameters are optimized. To do this, Yilkins strives to improve the various factors affecting the thermochemical process.

The presentation elaborates on the various value chains they can build around this technology, demonstrating its broad spectrum of applications. Accordingly, a schematic of the torrefaction is presented, highlighting its advantages and wide applications for upgrading energy commodities. Various steps of the process are then discussed: drying, torrefaction and pelleting, each with their multiple technological advances and synergies with other systems. The potential benefits in terms of economic inputs are demonstrated next, as torrefaction technology can create significant savings. There are many torrefaction production chains, as discussed by Juan Carlos, each with its input, output and specific parameters; each end user must design their depending on their needs and aims.

The design of a logistics chain, in terms of energy efficiency is then elaborated on. Closing, the presentation goes over a few highlighted projects under Yilkin’s portfolio in various countries globally, demonstrating the increasing interest around green technologies like torrefaction.

Figure 122: Yilkins - scope of technologies and their positioning in the biobased value chains (Yilkins, 2024)

3.6.8 Energy Community producing pellets in Greece

Vasileios starts his presentation by introducing ESEK, an energy cooperative based in Karditsa, Central Greece that utilizes residual biomass for energy production. He paints a vivid picture of the land and topography of the surrounding area and the different types of biomasses it can provide. He then elaborates on the modus operandi of ESEK, its core values and goals. He also explains how community engagement is a big part of ESEK’s activities. ESEK’s history goes back to 2010. In 2016, they were founded as an enterprise, creating a biofuel plant that can process biomass residues and produce refined solid biofuels, in the form of pellets, and have been operating since 2017.

Vasileios presents a schematic of the supply chain they operate on, one using multiple feedstocks from local sources. They also formed a collaboration with the municipality of Karditsa, and continuously try to engage forest cooperatives and the wood industry for mutually beneficial collaboration. Vasileios elaborates on BECoop, an EU Horizon2020 program that aided them in expanding their activities. One of these activities was the valorization of coffee bean residues, sourced from local coffee houses. He explains how they mixed such residues with other types of biomasses to produce high quality biofuels. A big part of the effort was community engagement, to secure the coffee bean wastes thus aiding the municipality of Karditsa with waste management and providing a valuable source of renewable energy.

ESEK also worked with another local municipality, as Vasileios goes on to describe, to install biomass boilers in a school, and set up a supply chain to provide for its energy need and pellet boiler upkeep. ESEK also plans to expand its area of activities in other sectors of renewable energy, namely solar, always using a democratic scheme and striving for community engagement.

Figure 123: Energy community - schematic representation (Source: Reis et al., 2021)

3.6.9 Life Cycle Assessment and associated methods for sustainability evaluation in bioenergy

Professor Freire begins with a short introduction of the Centre for Industrial Ecology, based in Coimbra, in which he is mostly active. He goes on to offer an introduction to life cycle assessment (LCA), with a brief definition and mention of related ISO standards, along with their approach to it. Continuing, prof. Freire discusses the purpose of LCA, according to ISO 14040:2006, and offers a few practical examples. He then goes on to explain the basic differences between life cycle assessment, life cycle approach and life cycle thinking.

Prof. Freire discusses sustainability approaches based on LCA, namely Life-Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA), along with Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and SLCA or Social LCA. Prof. Freire then proceeds to how a LCA analysis is set up, starting with a schematic of the different phases it assumes: scope, life cycle inventory analysis, life cycle impact assessment, and life cycle interpretation. He also stresses how the goal and scope of LCA analysis is a crucial step. Next, he offers a visual schematic example of an LCA analysis to aid in understanding in a more practical way, along with some real-world examples of the analyses they have performed across various sectors.

Prof. Freire then elaborates on findings from an EU rape-seed methyl ester review they have performed using two different LCA models and the differences between their results. Closing, he uses more examples from recent analyses to demonstrate recent advances in LCA.

Figure 124: Areas of application of LCA for sustainability evaluation in bioenergy (detail from KEW5 presentation, Freire, 2024)

LCA of biodiesel:

- Virgin oils – rapeseed, palm, soybean, sunflower
- Microalgae
- Waste cooking oils
- Beef tallow

LCA of bioethanol:

- Wheat
- Sugar beet
- Sugarcane

- Well-to-Tank & Tank-to-Wheels analysis
- Heavy duty vehicles
- LUC
- Agriculture practices and pathways
- Uncertainty analysis
- **Multicriteria decision analysis**
- **Multi-objective optimization**
- Social impacts
- Water footprint
- **Multifunctionality**

Figure 125: Examples of LCA for sustainability evaluation of biofuels (detail from KEW5 presentation, Freire, 2024)

Suggested additional reading:

- [A meta-analysis of the life cycle greenhouse gas balances of microalgae biodiesel](#)
- [Life-cycle assessment of irrigated and rainfed sunflower addressing uncertainty and land use change scenarios](#)

3.6.10 Solar drying and gasification of Sewage Sludge to obtain bioenergy

Virginia begins her presentation by briefly introducing CEDER, the Centro de Desarrollo de Energias Renovables. She elaborates on what kind of issues it addresses, namely management of sewage sludge inside a cadre of stringent legislation combined with high logistics and management costs. She explains the solution the DRY4GAS project proposed, offering sustainable treatment for any sewage sludge from wastewater treatment plants, by producing gas and energy in the process. The process involves solar drying, gasification, and energy recovery via an ORC unit, while also giving resources that can find use in agricultural applications.

Ensuing, Virginia elaborates on the benefits of such technology: its circular nature, and the many products and by-products that the process produces and their end uses in various sectors. As she explains, this way they are also able to produce renewable energy and aid towards emissions reduction, along with numerous other environmental benefits.

Figure 126: The process of solar drying and gasification of sewage sludge (detail from KEW5 presentation, Perez Lopez, 2024)

3.6.11 2nd generation bioethanol production from forest management and agriculture residues

Ana begins by stressing the increasing importance of the issue of global greenhouse gas emissions, and the various measures the global community and the EU is taking in that direction. Ana introduces PRIO, a company that distributes and markets liquid fuels since 2006, based in Portugal. PRIO also owns a biodiesel production plant that uses vegetable oils to produce biodiesel, at a capacity of 113,000 tonnes/year. As she explains, since 2022 they only operate using residual oils, resulting at a greatly reduced carbon footprint. As Ana details, the bioethanol market is constantly expanding, so naturally PRIO exhibits increasing interest in its production.

Ana offers a definition of bioethanol, along with a schematic on how it is produced. She argues that bioliquids like bioethanol will continue to play a big role in future transportation technology, as electric vehicles will coexist with hybrid vehicles, especially as the technologies around them continue to evolve. Also importantly, ethanol will play a key role in the aviation industry. She introduces us to BioFlexPor, a project that aimed at using residual biomass to produce bioethanol. It began by assessing the availability of feedstocks, namely from corn, olive groves, and indigenous forests such as eucalyptus, maritime pine, and stone pine. She elaborates on the results from the project, which were then subsequently adopted by PRIO for an industrial project.

Ana closes her presentation with important messages towards the global decarbonization and the role bioethanol and biofuels by large will play in that sector, along with a more circular approach to economy in general.

Figure 127: Flexible small-scale technology for the production of 2G bioethanol - the process scheme (BIOFLEXPOR, 2024)

3.6.12 Advanced biofuels for transportation

Dr. Atsonios begins by stressing the role of biomass in sustainable transport. He demonstrates the various advanced biofuels production pathways, in terms of different feedstocks utilized, the conversion they undergo, the medium used, upgrading, and end use. He then presents renewable synthetic fuels production through another pathway, that of carbon dioxide (CO₂). He is currently involved in numerous EU-funded projects related to advanced biofuels production. One such project, BioSFerA, (concluded in March 2024) aimed to produce drop-in aviation and marine biofuels through a combined thermochemical-biochemical pathway.

Kostis then demonstrates the production chain of the project along with the key results, technological advancements it brought and its added value. Following, Kostis presents the CLARA project, another research project, involving the full chain 2nd generation biofuel production based on chemical looping gasification. After delving into the production process it developed, he explains the technological advancements it entailed. Next, he goes on to detail the FlexSNG project, a research project with the goal to develop and validate a flexible and cost-effective gasification-based process for the production of pipeline-quality biomethane, high value biochar and renewable heat from a wide variety of low-quality biomass residues and biogenic waste feedstocks. He explains the goals of the project and the innovations, especially in terms of cost savings it brought.

Last he introduces us to a more recent project, FUELPHORIA, aimed at demonstrating robust and cost effective technological solutions for the production of advanced biofuels and renewable fuels of non-biological origins from sustainable feedstocks and renewable energy. Wrapping up, Kostis offers several interesting conclusions on the future of advanced biofuels from his expert point of view.

Biomass and sustainable transport

- Transport is responsible for about 25% of the EU's total CO₂ emissions
- The EU aims to reduce by 90% the greenhouse gas emissions from transport by 2050, compared with 1990
- Biofuels are crucial for reducing emissions in the transport sector
- Major role on the so-called "hard-to-abate sectors" aviation and maritime decarbonization

Source: [European Environment Agency 2022](#)

Figure 128: Biomass and sustainable transport (EEA, 2022)

3.6.13 GAMS utilization on biogas sector: a case study

Professor Rozakis's work involves the development of models to relate bioenergy to the production phase. The case study he presents is related to the biogas industry in Poland, aimed at investigating the development of its bioeconomy through an economic lens. Prof. Rozakis lays out the background and motivations that drove him to this field of research in Poland, namely map out its current situation and assess supply and demand trends to assess the competition between bioenergy and other agri-food supply chains, and to consider the environmental impact.

Prof. Rozakis then proceeds to present a schematic of the Partial Equilibrium (PE) modeling framework used in this study. Two models were developed, one for agriculture and one for industry, which he presents in some detail. The professor explains the methodology of each model, along with its mathematical structure, while offering a description for each variable used. For the industry model, they used the General Algebraic Modelling System (GAMS), a high-level modeling system for mathematical programming and optimization and were able to assess potential profit and return of investment, as he explains. Prof. Rozakis details the various inputs and outputs of the model.

Following, he delineates the parameters and results of the Polish case study, made clear through maps and flow charts. One of the main results of the analysis was the investment appraisal, which he discusses. He also presents special distribution maps of the biomass supply, as well as graphs that contrast supply and demand trends, depending on the region of Poland in question. Closing, he discusses the various conclusions gleaned from the case study.

BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATIONS

- Biogas can supports bioeconomy development and may constitute a source of electrical and thermal energy supply
- Great potential of biomass in Poland (18,9 Mha of UAA) but about **130** agricultural biogas plants operating versus **7.000** in Germany
- Critical issues: **competition** between bioenergy and other agri-food supply chains? Additional **GHGs** emission due to LUC?
- We aim to develop a tool to comprehensively investigate:
 - i) consequences of biogas polices in Poland (feedstock used, biogas produced, LUC, effectiveness in reducing GHGs)
 - ii) Assess the most efficient incentive system for biogas production in Poland.
- By modeling the energy crops market for biogas: **supply**-side agricultural sector **Vs demand**-side biogas industry (**partial equilibrium micro-economic** framework).

Figure 129: Biogas potential and actual exploitation rate in Poland (detail from KEW5 presentation, Rozakis, 2024)

General Algebraic Modelling System

System Overview

GAMS is a high level modeling system for mathematical programming and optimization. It consists of a language compiler and a range of associated solvers.

The GAMS modeling language allows modelers to quickly translate real world optimization problems into computer code.

The GAMS language compiler then translates this code into a format the solvers can understand and solve. This architecture provides great flexibility, by allowing changing the solvers used without changing the model formulation.

www.biorural.eu

Figure 130: GAMS Overview (detail from KEW5 presentation, Rozakis, 2024)

4 Conclusions and recommendations

The Knowledge Exchange Workshops (KEWs) and learning materials derived from these workshops were conceived as a vital initiative to bridge the gap in knowledge and skills necessary to foster a circular bioeconomy in rural areas. These workshops were designed to cater to a diverse audience, including rural businesses, technology developers, and policymakers. By focusing on the valorization of biomass side-streams, these workshops aimed to convey easy-to-digest scientific knowledge to practitioners familiar with traditional biomass uses, such as food processing and wood products, but who may lack expertise in more innovative practices of biomass loop closure. The workshops, organized as three-day webinars, were structured to cover technological foundations, showcase successful commercial practices, and discuss cross-cutting topics crucial for the commercialization of innovative biomass valorization technologies. The learning materials, including video lectures and slides, are made publicly accessible through the [BioRural Toolkit](#) and the [BioRural YouTube channel](#).

Outputs, described in this report (knowledge exchange workshops, learning) offer a range of benefits tailored to the needs of different target groups within the rural bioeconomy.

1. Primary Producers in agriculture, forestry and aquatic systems

- **Access to Innovative Practices:** The workshops provided primary producers with insights into innovative practices such as carbon farming, agroforestry, and sustainable aquaculture. These practices enable them to enhance productivity while contributing to environmental sustainability.
- **Resource Optimization:** Through topics like nutrient recycling and efficient fertilizer use, producers learned how to optimize resource use, reducing costs and environmental impact.

2. Businesses Engaged in Biomass Transformation

- **New Market Opportunities:** The workshops highlighted commercial innovations in biochemicals, biomaterials, and bioenergy, offering businesses new market opportunities in the circular bioeconomy.
- **Technological Advancements:** Businesses gained knowledge of cutting-edge technologies, such as small-scale biorefining and AI in agriculture, which can improve their operational efficiency and product offerings.

3. Enabling Institutions (Investors, Banks, Policymakers)

- **Informed Decision-Making:** The workshops provided enabling institutions with a deeper understanding of the bioeconomy landscape, including regulatory frameworks and sustainability evaluation methods. This knowledge is crucial for informed decision-making in policy development and investment.
- **Supporting Sustainable Growth:** By engaging with the latest innovations and practices, enabling institutions are better equipped to support sustainable growth in rural areas, fostering the development of a robust circular bioeconomy.

The Knowledge Exchange Workshops and corresponding Training Materials therefore play important role in equipping stakeholders with the knowledge and tools necessary to unlock the potential of the bioeconomy in rural areas. By addressing the technological, commercial, and cross-cutting aspects of biomass valorization, these workshops have laid the groundwork for a more sustainable and circular bioeconomy, benefiting primary producers, businesses, and enabling institutions alike. Through the continued dissemination of these learning materials, the workshops' impact will extend beyond the initial participants, fostering innovation and sustainability across rural Europe.

To maximize the benefits of the Knowledge Exchange Training Materials, users are encouraged to broaden their professional horizons by exploring further the BioRural Toolkit. This portal offers a wealth of resources, including success stories, practice abstracts, business blueprints, and practice abstracts.

By engaging with these materials, users can deepen their understanding of innovative biomass valorization practices and apply these insights to their work.

Furthermore, users are invited to join the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN), a growing community of like-minded professionals dedicated to advancing sustainable rural development. By becoming part of ERBN, users can connect with peers, share experiences, and collaborate on projects that drive innovation in rural bioeconomy across Europe. This network provides a platform for continuous learning and professional growth, fostering a collective effort towards a more sustainable future.

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1 Annexes

This annex to Deliverable 3.1 contains a copy of all the presentations conducted.

Link to annex: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1hxzkDYX408h9twJOqM3MxVolLQ7IfzrL/view?usp=drive_link